

TRIFFID

Autonomous Robotic Aid For increasing First responders efficiency

D4.1: Robot perception, EO analysis, HRI and HCI 1

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Executive summary

Deliverable 4.1, “Robot perception, EO analysis, HRI and HCI 1”, constitutes the first comprehensive technical consolidation of Work Package 4: “Perception and Human-Robot Interaction”. The present deliverable reports on the design choices, methodological foundations, dataset contributions, implemented algorithms, and experimental evaluations carried out during the first reporting period, addressing tasks T4.1 to T4.4. Collectively, these activities aim to enable robust autonomous perception, intuitive interaction, and enhanced situational awareness for first responders (FRs) operating in complex, usually cluttered post-disaster environments.

Within Section 2 (where Task 4.1: “Visual scene analysis and EO data analysis” is discussed), the deliverable presents an extensive investigation of visual scene analysis and earth observation (EO)-based data processing for post-disaster scene environmental analysis. A structured review of publicly available disaster-related datasets across satellite, aerial, ground-level, and social-media sources is initially provided, highlighting their suitability with respect to TRIFFID operational requirements. Building upon the identified limitations of existing benchmarks, most notably the absence of high-quality pixel-level annotations for complex, real-world disaster scenes, we introduce a novel, richly annotated post-disaster dataset derived from the Incidents1M dataset. This contribution includes the introduction of a carefully designed semantic corpus aligned with TRIFFID use cases and a semi-automatic annotation pipeline. At the moment of writing, the contributed dataset, named Incidents1M-Seg, covers 63 unique semantic classes and contains 35,230 paired instance annotations distributed across 2,976 images. It needs to be highlighted that the formed dataset comprises internet-originated sceneries/images; hence, supporting significantly broader and heterogeneous operational environments than those to be encountered in TRIFFID. To this end, this newly created dataset will significantly boost the pre-training step of the AI perception modules to be developed, while it is planned to be made publicly available to support further research and development in the field.

Additionally, EO-based damage assessment, fire and smoke detection, and hazardous signs recognition methods are implemented and evaluated on representative benchmarks, with systematic comparisons across convolutional, transformer-based, and foundation-model-driven architectures. Across all experiments, the strongest results are consistently achieved by the highest-capacity or most context-aware models. For semantic segmentation, SegFormer delivers the top performance, achieving a mean Intersection over Union (mIoU) of 95.58% on RescueNet and 78.56% on FloodNet+, clearly outperforming all CNN-based baselines. In object detection, the YOLOv5 Large model achieves the highest score on the LADD benchmark with an mAP50 of 95.80%, while transformer-based models remain highly competitive, with RF-DETR Base close behind at 95.05% using fewer parameters. On the D-Fire dataset, the best overall detection performance is obtained by DEIMv2 Large, achieving 79.90% mean Average Precision (mAP) 50, followed closely by RT-DETR Large at 78.22%, highlighting the advantage of ViT-based and hybrid architectures for complex visual patterns such as fire and smoke.

Complementing aerial and satellite perspectives, ground-level visual scene analysis methods are also investigated, addressing object detection, instance and panoptic segmentation, and open-vocabulary perception. The deliverable documents the selection of baseline and advanced models, their adaptation to disaster scenarios, and experimental evaluation highlighting trade-offs between accuracy, robustness, and computational efficiency. Specifically, for multi-label classification on Incidents1M, EfficientFormer-L1 achieves the strongest overall results, with an mAP of 92.69%. In hazardous sign

detection on the HAZMAT dataset, performance is near saturation: YOLOv5 large and small variants both reach 99.10% mAP50, while YOLOv11 large achieves the best localisation accuracy with 86.30% mAP[50-95]. On the more challenging Incidents1M-Seg benchmark, DEIMv2 attains the highest detection performance with 38.40% mAP50, and in instance segmentation, Grounded SAM2 stands out with a notably high mIoU of 59.55%, demonstrating the advantage of decoupled detection and mask refinement in complex post-disaster scenes.

Section 3 (addressing Task T4.2: “Non-visual data analysis and information fusion”) focuses on non-visual data analysis and multimodal information fusion, with particular emphasis on 3D semantic mapping and Light Detection and Ranging-based (LiDAR) processing. D4.1 reports on the design and evaluation of 3D scene representations combining geometric reconstruction with semantic information, including SOTA Structure-from-Motion, Neural and Gaussian-based representations, and semantic Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) pipelines. Special attention is given to unmanned ground vehicle (UGV)-centric LiDAR-Inertial SLAM, traversability analysis, and occupancy mapping, all evaluated on public benchmarks and real-world experimental setups. A key contribution is the exploration of aerial-ground map alignment and fusion, enabling consistent multi-robot situational awareness. Across the reported Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) and 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) evaluations, the largest and most impactful numbers clearly demonstrate the runtime advantage of 3DGS for interactive use. In the published benchmarks, 3DGS achieves up to 197 Frames Per Second (FPS) on the Tanks & Temples datasets and 160 FPS on Mip-NeRF360, compared to 11-17 FPS for Instant-NGP and as low as 0.06-0.14 FPS for Mip-NeRF360, corresponding to speedups of up to 2667 \times in rendering and over 600 \times in training time relative to high-fidelity NeRF baselines. In terms of visual quality, high-capacity 3DGS configurations reach Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) up to 0.903 and Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) up to 29.41, closely matching or surpassing NeRF methods while operating at orders-of-magnitude higher frame rates. For map alignment, the strongest quantitative gains arise from photometric features: the Color+Opacity 3DGS-ICP configuration converges in only 8 iterations (1.29s) versus 44 iterations (4.18s) for geometry-only ICP, and maintains the highest registration success rate under all tested noise levels, confirming that photometric cues, rather than splat geometry, are the dominant contributors to robust and efficient multi-robot 3DGS alignment.

Moreover, Task T4.2 combines environmental sound analysis with synthetic soundscape creation as additional paradigms to sense situational awareness. The deliverable discusses the selection of large-scale audio datasets and the use of transformer-based methods, including the Audio Spectrogram Transformer (AST), to enhance robust acoustic event detection in a noisy post-disaster scenario. To address the scarcity of useful audio data in the target field, a parametric synthetic soundscape creation framework is proposed to allow parametric soundscape creation focused on relevant disaster events such as sirens, explosions, and building collapses. Experimental evaluation on the initial synthetic audio corpus demonstrates a top-5 event detection accuracy over 85% and average command accuracy over 90%. These preliminary results are proof of the potential of synthetic audio to achieve reliable non-visual sensing.

Under Section 4 (corresponding to Task T4.3: “HRI and human behavior analysis”), the deliverable addresses human-robot interaction and human behavior analysis, with a focus on gesture-based communication tailored to first-responder operations. After reviewing relevant public datasets, the deliverable documents the creation of a dedicated RGB-D hand gesture dataset, including semantic corpus definition, data collection protocol, and statistical characterization. Multiple hand gesture recognition (HGR) paradigms are implemented and experimentally evaluated, demonstrating their suitability for robust, contactless interaction in adverse conditions. In addition, a semantic abstraction

and reasoning framework is introduced to elevate low-level perceptual outputs into higher-level situational awareness concepts. Across the HGR experiments on public static HGR benchmarks, EfficientNet-B0 achieves the best result on HaGRID with an F1-score of 97.57% while using only 5.3M parameters, highlighting its excellent efficiency. On the smaller LRHG dataset, however, larger Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) dominate, with ResNet-18 reaching 97.60% accuracy and ResNet-50 achieving 97.14%, confirming that higher-capacity models are advantageous when sufficient discriminative detail is present. For dynamic HGR, skeleton-based approaches significantly outperform RGB-based methods: TD-GCN reaches 96.31% accuracy on SHREC14 and 93.69% on SHREC28, compared to 86.33% for the best RGB + optical flow (OF) model, demonstrating the strength of pose-based representations. Finally, on the project-developed custom static gesture dataset, ResNet-18 pretrained on HaGRID achieves a strong 93.91% F1-score on the test set, despite the limited data size, emphasizing the importance of transfer learning for small-scale gesture recognition tasks. Moreover, Task 4.3 further improves the robot's interaction capabilities through a voice analysis module, including knowledge-driven semantic reasoning. The deliverable presents a modular sound and speech analysis engine capable of voice analysis/activity and command detection, in adverse acoustic conditions, which has been evaluated on real as well as artificially-generated voices. Simultaneously, a knowledge graph-based semantic abstraction layer is also presented for low-level perceptual output abstractions, including semantically important scene objects, gestures, and voice commands, with a focus on enhancing high-level situational awareness. The implemented ontology layer, combined with a contextual reasoner, also allows the linking of agents, objects, and mission tasks, facilitating a rule-based reasoning process. Experimental analysis reveals more than 90% command analysis accuracy at a word level, while the knowledge-based reasoning process clearly shows its feasibility in achieving high-level human-robot interaction.

Finally, Section 5 (aligned with Task T4.4: "Intuitive AR-based human-computer interfaces") presents the design and implementation of intuitive AR-based human-computer interfaces for disaster management. The deliverable details the principles guiding the balance between situational awareness and cognitive load, real-time dynamic map updates, and multimodal cue integration. The implemented AR/VR prototypes are experimentally evaluated in terms of performance, responsiveness, and usability across different hardware configurations. For the AR dedicated evaluation, across the platform comparison, the largest and most decisive numbers clearly highlight the performance gap between desktop-class GPUs and mobile or standalone AR hardware. Rendering a 1.14M splat scene, the desktop system equipped with an RTX 3080 Ti achieves 72 FPS, meeting the refresh-rate requirements for comfortable immersive visualization. In contrast, the Meta Quest 3 peaks at only 9 FPS, and the mobile device at 7 FPS. These results demonstrate that, for high-fidelity disaster-scale reconstructions, only desktop GPUs currently provide sufficient throughput and memory bandwidth, while mobile and standalone VR platforms fall short by an order of magnitude in rendering performance; hence, simpler representation, visualization and abstraction schemes are foreseen to be developed.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
3DGS	3D Gaussian Splatting
ADR	European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road
AED	Acoustic Event Detection
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMR	Autonomous Mobile Robot
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AST	Audio Spectrogram Transformer
APE	Absolute Positional Error
ATE	Absolute Trajectory Error
BoO	Base of Operation
CDHGR	Continuous Dynamic Hand Gesture Recognition
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRBN	Chemical, Radiological, Biological, Nuclear
CSLR	Continuous Sign Language Recognition
CSP	Cross Stage Partial
CV	Computer Vision
DCS	Disaster Scene Commander
DoF	Degrees of Freedom
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DSP	Digital Signal Processing
DWC	Depth-Wise Convolution
EO	Earth Observation
FM	Foundation Model
FPS	Frames Per Second
FR	First Responder
GFLOPs	Giga Floating Point Operations
GIS	Geographic Information System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
H2R	Human-to-Robot
HAR	Human Action Recognition
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
HGR	Hand Gesture Recognition
HMI	Human-Machine Interaction
HRC	Human-Robot Collaboration
HRI	Human-Robot Interaction
ICP	Iterative Closest Point
IDHGR	Isolated Dynamic Hand Gesture Recognition
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
InfoNCE	Information Noise-Contrastive Estimation
IoU	Intersection over Union

ISLR	Isolated Sign Language Recognition
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LLM	Large Language Model
LOAM	Lidar Odometry and Mapping
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
mAP	Mean Average Precision
ML	Machine Learning
MiT	Mix Transformer
MLM	Masked Language Modeling
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MSE	Mean Squared Error
MVS	Multi-View Stereo
NAS	Neural Architecture Search
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLU	Natural Language Understanding
NMS	Non-Maximum Suppression
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OGM	Occupancy Grid Map
OF	Optical Flow
ORO	Open Robots Ontology
OVS	Open-Vocabulary Segmentation
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PAN	Path Aggregation Network
PMK	Perception and Manipulation Knowledge
POI	Point of Interest
PnP	Perspective-n-Point
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
R2H	Robot-to-Human
PQ	Panoptic Quality
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ROS	Robot Operating System
RPE	Relative Pose Error
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RUGD	Rugged Terrain Dataset
SA	Situational Awareness
SAM	Segment Anything Model
SAR	Search and Rescue
SD-SLAM	Semantic Dynamic SLAM
SED	Sound Event Detection
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Descent
SG-SLAM	Semantic Graph SLAM
SHGR	Static Hand Gesture Recognition
SfM	Structure-from-Motion
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SLR	Sign Language Recognition
SLT	Sign Language Translation
SLU	Sign Language Understanding
SPLU	Spoken Language Understanding
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio

SOTA	State-of-the-Art
SRWT	Speech Recognition with Word-level Timestamps
SSM	State Space Model
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index Measure
STA	Spatial Tuning Adapter
SuMa	Surfel-Based Mapping
SUMO	Suggested Upper Merged Ontology
SVR	Sparse Voxel Rasterization
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TCN	Temporal Convolutional Network
TF	Transformation Frame
TIR	Thermal Infrared
TSDF	Truncated Signed Distance Function
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
UI	User Interface
VAD	Voice Activity Detection
VHGR	Vision-Based Hand Gesture Recognition
ViT	Vision Transformer
VLM	Vision-Language Model
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The present deliverable presents the first formal technical report of Work Package 4 (WP4): “Perception and Human-Robot Interaction”. WP4 covers core perception, data analysis, and interaction capabilities that enable autonomous robotic reconnaissance and effective human-robot collaboration (HRC) in disaster-response scenarios. In particular, WP4’s main target is to transform the robot from a passive sensing platform into an intelligent, context-aware agent capable of transforming the incoming streams of raw multimodal data into actionable perceptual knowledge that supports situational awareness and decision-making. The activities reported herein focus on the development of algorithmic foundations, data representations, and interaction paradigms that are essential for robust autonomy and intuitive human oversight in complex, dynamic, and safety-critical environments.

The main objective of this document is to extensively document the state-of-the-art (SOTA) methodologies, the implemented algorithms, and experimental results that were attained during the first year of WP4 development through tasks T4.1 to T4.4.

The structure of the deliverable is organized as follows:

Section 2: This part addresses task T4.1 and outlines a comprehensive treatment of visual scene analysis and EO data processing. In this part we introduce the creation of a new pixel-level annotated post-disaster benchmark, the implementation of EO-based damage and hazard analysis methods, and extensive experimental evaluations on both aerial and ground-level imagery.

Section 3: This section refers to task T4.2 and includes methods related to non-visual data analysis and multimodal information fusion, such as the implemented techniques for constructing the 3D semantic map, the introduction of a novel LiDAR-based SLAM algorithm, traversability assessment, and aerial-ground map fusion. Additionally, the section introduces sound event detection as non-visual inputs, which contribute to the multimodal fusion and semantic mapping development. Moreover, the section introduces environmental sound analysis and audio-based event detection as complementary non-visual cues, as well as synthetic soundscape generation to address the scarcity of disaster-specific audio benchmarks.

Section 4: Section 4 discusses task T4.3, and addresses human-robot interaction (HRI) and human behavior analysis, with particular emphasis on intuitive multimodal audio and visual gesture-based communication and semantic abstraction for situational awareness. A knowledge-graph-based module and the underlying ontology are introduced, allowing the transformation of the perception module detections into high-level, interpretable situational understanding.

Section 5: This focuses on task T4.4 and describes intuitive augmented reality-based human-computer interfaces for FR operations. This section explores the integration of a 3D semantic map (that updates in real-time) to the developed module, while considering the fundamental cognitive load theory to maintain balance between situational awareness and cognitive load. It also highlights the way that mission-relevant annotations and non-visual cues are spatially anchored to the evolving semantic map.

Section 6: Finally, the last section summarizes the main conclusions and outlines the directions for our future work.

2 Visual scene and earth observation data analysis

Visual scene and Earth Observation (EO) data analysis is increasingly at the core of efforts to understand, monitor, and respond to the complex real-world post-disaster environments. Emerging sensing technologies, such as satellite and aerial drones, through as ground cameras, can capture rich visual data from multiple spatial scales and perspectives. Being able to analyse these data facilitates the extraction of meaningful information about land condition, the stability of the infrastructure, and the impact of disasters. During crisis management, these analytical capabilities provide essential insights for situational awareness, damage assessment, and informed decision-making, ultimately enabling the pursuit of more effective and timely response efforts.

2.1 Relevant public post-disaster datasets

This section presents and describes the most relevant publicly available datasets used for post-disaster scene understanding and search and rescue purposes. These range from satellite and unmanned air vehicle (UAV) imagery to ground-level captures, social media scrapped content, and unmanned ground vehicles, supporting diverse tasks such as building damage assessment, incident detection, monitoring wildfires and identifying hazardous materials. Table 1 gives an overview of the most significant public post-disaster benchmarks, including their most crucial metadata for describing them.

Table 1 Publicly available disaster datasets across sensing platforms and scenarios

No	Dataset	Year	Source	Use case	No. Classes	No. Samples	Annotation type	Modality
1	SpaceNet 8 [Hänsch22]	2022	Satellite	Flood	4	12	Segmentation masks	RGB
2	xBD [Gupta19]	2019	Satellite	Disaster response	4	22,068	Classification labels, Segmentation masks, bounding boxes	RGB
3	Next Day Wildfire Spread [Huot22]	2022	Satellite	Wildfire	3	18,545	Segmentation masks	Multimodal
4	FIgLib [Dewangan22]	2022	Ground cameras	Wildfire	2	24,800	Classification labels, Segmentation masks, bounding boxes	RGB
5	FloodNet [Rahnenoufar21]	2021	UAV	Flood	11	3,200	Segmentation masks	RGB
6	BRIGHT [Chen25]	2025	Satellite	Damage Assessment	4	4,246	Segmentation masks	Multimodal
7	DisasterM3 [Wang25A]	2025	Satellite	Damage Assessment	41	26,988	Segmentation masks,	Multimodal

							bounding boxes	
8	RescueNet [Rahnemounfar23]	2023	UAV	Damage Assessment	11	4,494	Segmentation masks	RGB
9	MSNet [Zhu21A]	2021	UAV	Damage Assessment	27	5,232	Segmentation masks	RGB
10	LADI v2 [Scheele25]	2025	UAV	Damage Assessment	12	9,963	Multi-label class tags	RGB
11	D'RespNet [Sirma25]	2025	UAV	Earthquake	28	205	Segmentation masks	RGB
12	LaDD [Tingaev21]	2021	UAV	Search & Rescue	1	1,365	Bounding boxes	RGB
13	NOMAD [Bernal24]	2024	UAV	Search & Rescue	1	42,825	Bounding boxes	RGB
14	C2A [Nihal24]	2024	UAV	Search & Rescue	1	10,215	Bounding boxes	RGB
15	PDD [Song23]	2023	UAV	Search & Rescue	1	1,146	Bounding boxes	RGB
16	D-Fire [deVenancio22]	2022	Various	Wildfire	2	14,496	Bounding boxes	RGB
17	Incidents [Weber20]	2020	Social-media	Incidents detections	43	446,684	Classification Labels	RGB
18	Incidents1M [Weber23]	2023	Social-media	Incidents detections	43	977,088	Classification Labels	RGB
19	CrisisMDD [Alam18]	2018	Social-media	Damage Assessment	10	18,000	Classification Labels	RGB
20	VIDI [Sesver22]	2022	Social-media	Incidents detections	43	4,534	Classification Labels	RGB
21	UMA-SAR [Morales21]	2021	UGV	Search & Rescue	N/A	77 min	Raw data	Multimodal
22	MEDIC [Alam23]	2023	Social-media	Incidents detections	16	71,198	Classification Labels	RGB

23	ADR2 Clone ¹	2024	Ground cameras	Hazardous Material Detection	4	1,638	Bounding boxes	RGB
24	ADR Labels and License Plates ²	2023	Ground cameras	Hazardous Material Detection	11	110	Bounding boxes	RGB
25	HAZMAT [Sharifi21]	2021	Ground cameras	Hazardous Material Detection	13	1,685	Bounding boxes	RGB

Among the reviewed datasets, those that best match the operational requirements of TRIFFID are in bold in Table 1. Notably, we found **D-Fire** [deVenancio22], **FloodNet** [Rahnemoonfar21], **RescueNet** [Rahnemoonfar23], **HAZMAT** [Sharifi21], and **Incidents1M** [Weber23], to correspond best to TRIFFID's core use cases. To start with, **FloodNet** is a high-resolution dataset of UAV imagery aimed at advancing the understanding of post-disaster scenes, specifically those captured after Hurricane Harvey. Unlike typical satellite-based datasets, which have low resolution, FloodNet includes drone images taken from 200 feet above ground level, thus enabling accurate identification of infrastructure damage. Consisting of 3,200 images annotated to support three distinct computer vision (CV) tasks, the dataset includes image classification to categorize scenes as flooded or non-flooded, semantic segmentation, which is pixel-wise labeling of 11 classes including flooded roads and buildings, water, amongst others, and visual question answering.

RescueNet is a high-resolution dataset of 4,494 post-disaster images captured by UAVs that covers the aftermath of Hurricane Michael. RescueNet focuses on comprehensive pixel-level annotations of as many as 11 distinct classes, including water, vehicles, pools, and trees. Among other things, this dataset performs damage assessment at a very granular level: buildings are categorised into four specific severity levels, ranging from superficial to total destruction, and roads are classified as "clear" or "blocked." The RescueNet benchmark aims to improve the accuracy of visual scene understanding tools used by FRs, combining semantic segmentation with image classification.

Similarly, for the fire use case, **D-Fire** is a comprehensive image dataset, with the goal of advancing object detection algorithms related to fire and smoke localisation applications. This dataset contains more than 14,000 images, labeled for four specific scenarios: solitary fire, solitary smoke, combined fire and smoke, and-even more important-more than 9,800 "negative" images that include neither of them, aiming at helping models reduce false positives. Intended for use in support of the development of automatic detection systems, especially those constrained by low power and resources, this dataset release includes supplementary videos for surveillance and pre-trained deep learning models.

On the hazardous material recognition, **HAZMAT** is a fully annotated dataset designed based on the European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road (ADR). It contains 1,685 images and 13 unique classes. Each image is annotated with bounding boxes, while

¹ <https://universe.roboflow.com/ai-bootcamp-kys8b/adr-2-clone>

² <https://universe.roboflow.com/masters-thesis-yolo-model/adr-labels-and-license-plates-detection-pxec2>

segmented masks are also provided, enabling both object detection and segmentation tasks. Its sufficient size and the class variety make HAZMAT the most suitable ADR benchmark for developing and evaluating models for visual hazard identification and situational awareness in TRIFFID-like operational environments.

The **Incidents1M** is a large-scale multi-label dataset containing approximately 1 million images labelled with at least one of 43 incident-related categories and 49 place categories. Scrapped primarily from social media and web imagery, this benchmark aims to support incident detection and disaster-type classification, which offers broad coverage across various disaster types and environmental settings. Because of its enormous scale and breadth, Incidents1M is particularly useful for training classification or image-filtering models that help flag disaster-related content. However, the dataset is limited to image-level labels, lacking bounding boxes or segmentation masks. The absence of spatial ground truth means that Incidents1M cannot be directly utilized from object detection or segmentation models, which is a crucial requirement for visual scene understanding in robotic disaster-response systems such as TRIFFID that must detect and localize hazards or structural damage within a crowded scene, rather than merely classifying scenes at a global level.

2.2 Creation of a pixel-level annotated post-disaster dataset

Having considered the absence of high-quality, pixel-level annotations in public post-disaster benchmarks, alongside the extensive coverage offered by the Incidents1M dataset, we contribute by providing precisely this type of rich annotation, tailored for real disaster-response applications.

2.2.1 Semantic corpus definition

The aforementioned dataset comprises detailed annotations (bounding boxes and segmentation masks suitable for panoptic segmentation) according to a list of classes/objects, which were considered to be useful, viewed from the following perspectives:

- General-purpose concepts, meaningful for the UGV navigation and situational awareness, including civilian vehicles, live-critical targets (e.g., humans, animals, and vegetation), as well as obstacles (e.g., mud and barriers) that the UGV should avoid.
- Objects related to infrastructure, some of which are strongly connected to specific use cases (for instance, detecting windows and doors may be crucial for entering a building during firefighting or for searching for survivors after an earthquake). Finding bridges and roads may also be useful for path planning of FR vehicles.
- Disasters and damages, including flame, smoke, debris, and holes in the ground. Destroyed buildings and vehicles were also included to enable FRs or automated systems to assess the total damage caused by the disaster.
- FR vehicles, such as fire trucks, police vehicles, and ambulances. Army vehicles and heavy machinery also fall into this category, as they are frequently deployed to post-disaster environments to support SAR operations. For example, drills and excavators are often used to remove debris (Figure 1) and armoured personnel carriers assist in floods (Figure 2).
- Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), such as masks and helmets, as well as other tools used by firefighters, including chainsaws and shovels. Detecting such objects facilitates the interaction of the UGV with them; for instance, if it is capable of manipulating objects, it can fetch and transfer a mask to a FR.

Figure 1 Several excavators and cranes are frequently deployed to SAR operations.

Figure 2 Army vehicles are often leveraged to support FRs.

As mentioned earlier, this corpus was created targeting to enhance FRs' situational awareness, to enable the UGV to navigate itself through debris or other terrain irregularities, and enhance HRI capabilities. Other classes were also considered but finally not incorporated, including potentially toxic emissions (gas & liquid), regarding the difficulty of recognizing hazardous materials relying only on visual data. Subdividing the FR vehicles into more fine-grained categories (for instance, fire trucks can be categorised into brush trucks, ladder trucks, fire engines, and hazmat vehicles) was also proposed, but the high inter-class similarity would pose significant challenges regarding both the annotation process and the development of an efficient model.

This corpus was obtained through a systematic procedure; images contained in the Incidents1M dataset were sampled randomly and examined to determine various concepts of interest. These classes or carefully designed keywords were utilized to prompt open vocabulary segmentation models (in particular, DINO-X [Ren25] and Grounded-SAM [Ren24A]). These models were also used in a prompt-free setting, providing new classes, which were then filtered, aiming to enrich the corpus classes. Furthermore, the quality of the initially proposed classes was evaluated to reduce the inter-class similarity and improve the corresponding definitions through prompt engineering.

Additional concepts were defined by examining video footage from real SAR operations or searching on related websites (e.g., PPE markets). The obtained corpus was extensively discussed with end-users and other partners to identify potential weaknesses and issues. During the dataset annotation process, as discussed in Section 2.2.2, additional recommendations were also taken into account, and the corpus was updated accordingly. The final version is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Corpus of TRIFFID-relevant classes derived from Incidents1M

SN	Class	Description or Comments	Image
GENERAL-PURPOSE			
C1	Civilian vehicle	All vehicles belonging to private individuals, as well as public services that are NOT involved in FRs' operations, such as taxis, private cars, vans, municipal vehicles, and garbage trucks.	
C2	Bicycle	Two-wheeled human-powered vehicle, metal frame with tires, handlebars, and saddle.	
C3	Boat	Boat in general (either of rescue services or a civilian one)	
C4	Aerial vehicle	Includes helicopters and aircrafts.	
C5	Citizen	People who are not involved in the operations, namely, victims or survivors of the disaster.	
C6	FR	Firefighters, rescuers, volunteers (with visible identification, such as distinctive clothing), police officers, and Emergency Medical Services (EMS).	
C7	Military personnel	Individuals wearing camo uniforms or similar attire. It is not necessary to carry weapons, as they are assisting as rescuers.	
C8	Animal	Any animal, whether injured, dead, or not.	
C9	Dirt road	Unpaved road. Passage may be limited to off-road vehicles only.	

C10	Water	Large masses of water, such as lakes, flooded places, rivers, sea, etc.	
C11	Mud	Muddy areas.	
C12	Green grass	Very low-lying vegetation.	
C13	Dry grass	Brown-yellow coloured vegetation, thin and dry, often sparse.	
C14	Green tree	Tree with a full green canopy, visible trunk and branches.	
C15	Dry tree	Tree without leaves, gray or brown branches, dry bark.	
C16	Green plant	Small green vegetation, shrubs or low plants, healthy appearance, such as flowers.	
C17	Dry plant	Yellow or brown non-woody vegetation, wilted and thin.	
C18	Tank	Tank (plastic or not) containing any kind of substance (water, toxic liquid etc).	

C19	Barrel	Cylindrical structure, typically smaller than a tank.	
C20	Barrier	Any obstacle that impedes vehicle passage (rocks on the road, barricades).	
C21	Bag	Backpacks, handbags and sandbags are included.	
INFRASTRUCTURES			
C22	Window	Windows of buildings.	
C23	Door	Door of buildings.	
C24	Stairs	Stairs of buildings.	
C25	Furniture	Man-made indoor or outdoor objects for sitting, resting, or storage.	
C26	Building	Houses, churches, markets, hospitals, bridges, etc.	

C27	Wall	Typically, a rectangular structure made of concrete, stone, or bricks, which either supports something or serves as a barrier.	
C28	Fence	Primarily a metal or wooden mesh/wall that serves as a barrier.	
C29	Pole	Elongated structure supporting electric power infrastructure.	
C30	Tower	A bulkier and more complex structure than a standard pole, primarily used by telecommunications providers and in industrial settings.	
C31	Silo	Concrete cylindrical structure used for storing fuel or chemicals.	
C32	Pavement	Hard-paved pedestrian surface, concrete or stone.	
C33	Road	Asphalt road.	
DISASTERS			
C34	Flame	The typically orange-red emission of light from a fire.	

C35	Smoke	Smoke in general, regardless of its source.	
C36	Debris	Chunks of concrete, fallen trees from a storm, and generally debris resulting from the destruction of other objects.	
C37	Destroyed building	Building with severe structural damage, debris and exposed materials.	
C38	Destroyed vehicle	Vehicle heavily damaged or burned, often without windows or tires	
C39	Hole in the ground	Ground subsidence, hole in the pavement, etc.	
C40	Burnt grass	Blackened or gray ground after fire, no visible green vegetation.	
C41	Burnt tree	Tree trunk and branches blackened or ash-gray after fire.	
C42	Burnt plant	Low vegetation with blackened or gray remains after fire.	
FR VEHICLES			
C43	Ambulance	Ambulances - regardless of whether they belong to a fire department (like in some countries) or not.	

C44	Fire truck	Ladder trucks, brush trucks, command vehicles, hazmat vehicles etc	
C45	Police vehicle	Includes motorcycles, police patrols etc	
C46	Army vehicle	Military ground vehicle, armored or camouflaged.	
C47	Excavator	Drilling rigs, bulldozers, and other heavy-duty excavation/earth-moving machinery.	
C48	Crane	Mobile and stationary cranes.	
PPE AND OTHER EQUIPMENT			
C49	Protective glasses	Eye protection worn by responders or citizens, typically transparent lenses that shield from debris, smoke, or hazardous materials.	
C50	Helmet	Head protection gear used by FRs, construction workers, or citizens. Usually hard-shell, often with identifiable colors or markings.	
C51	Glove	Hand protection made of fabric, leather, or specialized materials (e.g., heat-resistant or cut-resistant). Worn by responders or civilians during operations.	

C52	Boot	Protective footwear, often reinforced, used for stability and safety in hazardous or uneven environments.	
C53	Mask	Full-face or half-face, oxygen or gas mask	
C54	SCBA	Self-Contained Breathing Apparatus (SCBA)	
C55	Shovel	Hand tool with a shaped blade and handle, used for digging, clearing debris, or moving soil or rubble.	
C56	Ax	Hand tool with a sharp metal head and handle, used for cutting wood, breaking obstacles, or rescue operations.	
C57	Chainsaw	Motorized cutting tool with a rotating chain, used for cutting trees, clearing debris, or accessing blocked areas.	
C58	Cone	Cone-shaped traffic sign used to indicate hazards, block areas, or direct movement of vehicles and pedestrians.	
C59	Ladder	Portable climbing equipment with rungs, used by responders to reach elevated areas or access buildings.	
C60	Lifesaver	Buoyant rescue device, typically ring-shaped, used for assisting people in water emergencies.	

C61	Extinguisher	Portable device containing pressurized firefighting agent, used to suppress small fires.	
C62	Fire hydrant	Metal roadside fixture with valve and nozzle for water supply	
C63	Fire hose	Includes also simple hoses used for firefighting by volunteers etc.	

2.2.2 Semi-automatic annotation pipeline

This work produced **Incidents1M-Seg**, a curated and pixel-level annotated subset of the Incidents1M dataset designed primarily for instance segmentation, with bounding boxes included as a complementary type of annotations. Overall, the pipeline followed a simple end-to-end process that starts with candidate image retrieval and manual curation/quality filtering, continues with mask-first instance annotation in Label Studio³ - one segmentation mask plus its corresponding bounding box per object - and iterative review/corrections, and concludes with COCO [Lin14] export for downstream training and evaluation.

It needs to be highlighted that the formed dataset comprises internet-originated sceneries/images; hence, supporting significantly broader and heterogeneous operational environments than those to be encountered in TRIFFID. To this end, this newly created dataset will significantly boost the pre-training step of the AI perception modules to be developed, while it is planned to be made publicly available to support further research and development in the field. To the best of our knowledge, there does not exist a directly comparable publicly available dataset that provides pixel-level segmentation annotations for diverse post-disaster scenes at this level of detail. This thus indicates a clear scientific gap that Incidents1M-Seg is designed to address.

³ <https://github.com/HumanSignal/label-studio>

Figure 3 Incidents1M-Seg annotation example in Label Studio: original image (top-left), instance masks (top-right), bounding boxes (bottom-left), and combined masks + boxes (bottom-right)

The construction of this dataset involved a multi-stage selection process. Candidate images were first retrieved by keyword-based filtering using disaster-related terms, such as fire, flood, collapse, rescue, and smoke. A subsequent **manual verification** stage removed irrelevant or low-quality content due to insufficient resolution, strong compression artifacts, non-contextual watermarks, or lack of disaster context. Images were retained only when they showed distinct visual evidence of either damage, emergency response activity, or post-disaster conditions. The curation decisions were documented with comparative examples that illustrate typical accepted versus discarded samples.

Figure 4 Accepted images depict active disaster scenes. Discarded images lack evidence of damage or emergency activity

Labeling was carried out in Label Studio in a dedicated project ("Incidents-1M -Seg- Disasters") set up to export high-fidelity segmentation masks for each object instance at the end. Labeling was performed explicitly manually and mask-centric, with every instance delineated by an annotator using a pixel-accurate segmentation mask, followed by refining the corresponding bounding box to tightly enclose the final mask. The interface allowed for zoom, rotation, and mask overlays for careful boundary tracing and refinement; there was also a comment field that allowed annotators to document ambiguous cases or ontology-related conflicts. Particular emphasis was placed on correcting challenging regions such as

thin structures, partial occlusions, and visually diffuse boundaries since these cases strongly affect segmentation training quality.

Figure 5 Representative raw Incidents1M-Seg samples (top row) and the corresponding instance-segmentation annotations (bottom row)

The primary aim was to enhance throughput, so auxiliary pre-annotation with Grounded-SAM [Ren24A] was used to create initial draft boxes or masks whenever useful. These outputs were handled strictly as starting proposals and never accepted by default; all the annotations in this dataset have been manually validated and further refined to meet the segmentation standard of Incidents1M-Seg, focusing on mask completeness and boundary accuracy. Images were labeled in Label Studio by manually refining or creating segmentation masks, adjusting the corresponding bounding box, verifying class labels, and removing false positives. Whenever necessary, overlapping phenomena like Flame and Smoke were annotated as separate instances; this was followed by a short per-class review prior to submission to reduce omissions.

Annotation guidelines and quality control

The guidelines for annotating incidents in Incidents1M-Seg emphasized completeness of segmentation, semantic consistency, and geometric precision. The first and foremost rule was that each instance of a physical object had to be represented with a paired annotation, where the segmentation mask was to be considered the authoritative geometry, supported by a bounding box as a consistent auxiliary label. Masks were supposed to closely adhere to object boundaries while preserving visible details and maintaining consistency across similar instances. Labels followed the ontology strictly, with particular attention given to commonly confused categories, like smoke versus flame, and structurally similar classes, such as building versus destroyed building. In cases where phenomena overlapped visually, annotators maintained semantic separation by creating distinct instance masks whenever the objects were physically different.

Figure 6 Example of produced annotation in Incidents1M-Seg: original scene (left) and the corresponding segmentation mask (right)

Quality control was performed as a two-layer process. First, annotators are iteratively self-checked, including class-by-class inspections to confirm the correctness of the labels, mask boundary quality, and box-mask completeness. Then, supervising QA reviewed a sampled subset of finished tasks, assessing both semantic correctness and geometric fidelity, with particular focus on segmentation quality: boundary adhesion, missing regions, background leakage, and consistency across similar instances. Where inconsistencies were found, the supervisor issued targeted correction requests, revising the relevant images and creating an iterative correction loop. The re-correction rate was kept around 5-7%. Common error modes included incomplete box-mask pairs, missing instances within complex scenes, or incorrect class assignment despite correct geometry; these were explicitly targeted during revision to ensure standards were uniform throughout Incidents1M-Seg.

2.2.3 Dataset statistics and class distribution

The final dataset, Incidents1M-Seg, consists of 2,976 **images** and **35,230 paired instance annotations** over **63 classes**. Each annotation is one box+mask pair that describes a single physical object instance, so the dataset contains 35,230 uniquely annotated objects (counted here as a single instance per pair, rather than as separate box and mask counts).

This corresponds to an average density of about **11.84 instances per image**, which reflects the complexity in post-disaster scenes due to co-occurring hazard-related elements with contextual infrastructure and environmental components. This provides Incidents1M-Seg with a wide segmentation coverage across both foreground actors/hazards and background context classes.

Class frequency exhibits a pronounced long tail: the few frequent categories are dominated by recurring contextual and structural elements such as Green tree, Window, Building, and Citizen, while categories related to specialized equipment and operational tools-Extinguisher, Chainsaw, Lifesaver, Ax, Army vehicle, Shovel-are found only rarely due to both genuine sparsity and visibility constraints such as distance, occlusion, and viewpoint. From a modeling perspective, this class imbalance motivates class-aware training strategies for Incidents1M-Seg, including reweighting, balanced sampling, and targeted enrichment of underrepresented categories to help improve rare-class generalization.

Figure 7 Class distribution of IncidentsIM-Seg

2.3 Earth observation data analysis

2.3.1 Review of state-of-the-art methods

The rise in both the frequency and severity of disasters has created a need for faster and more advanced methods in post-disaster assessment. Existing post-disaster assessment methods have reached their limits for addressing the increasing scale of disasters [Kucharczyk23]. Remote sensing technologies, such as UAVs and EO satellites offer valuable aerial data, however the sheer volume of high-resolution imagery they create introduces increased processing demands. These cannot be efficiently resolved through human manual analysis. As a result, current workflows are being strained, and delays in analysis are being introduced. Current workflows struggle to handle the volume efficiently, leading to delays in analysis. This challenge is being addressed through the application of deep learning, which is

enabling a transition from traditional, passive image collection to a more dynamic and intelligence-driven reconnaissance process [Boroujeni24]. Automation of key tasks has led to improvements in situational awareness and more efficient resource allocation. This section reviews the underlying CV methods that support these advancements, with particular attention to two core applications: object detection, which identifies and locates specific elements such as survivors or vehicles, and image segmentation, which provides detailed, pixel-level insights into damage and environmental conditions [Gui24].

Key challenges for aerial and earth level perception

Unique perception challenges are encountered when CV models are deployed in post-disaster environments, which differ markedly from typical urban settings. Chaotic conditions, debris, and extreme variability common in disaster zones create substantial obstacles for achieving reliable object detection and segmentation.

- **Scale variance and small object detection:** A primary challenge in aerial reconnaissance is presented by the extreme scale variance of objects. Imagery is often captured from high altitudes by UAVs and satellites, causing critical targets, such as survivors or structural cracks, to occupy very few pixels. The issue is exacerbated in maritime or wide-area searches where targets are minute compared to the vast background. Meaningful features are often difficult to extract from low-resolution representations by standard detection architectures, resulting in high false-negative rates for small objects.
- **Occlusion and environmental complexity:** Disaster environments are naturally unstructured. Complete feature sets are often complicated by critical entities being frequently partially occluded by debris, collapsed structures, or vegetation. Environmental noise, including smoke, fog, or shadows, can significantly impair the performance of optical sensors. In flood situations, surface reflections and waves create additional visual noise that obstructs accurate detection.
- **Domain shift and generalization:** Failures are often experienced by models trained on pre-disaster imagery or specific geographic regions when they are applied to new, unseen disaster events. This phenomenon, referred to as domain shift, is caused by the radical differences in visual characteristics between damaged and intact infrastructure, as well as the significant variations in topography between events (e.g., an earthquake in an urban area versus a flood in a rural region). Cross-event generalization, where a model trained on one disaster performs well on another without retraining, remains a persistent difficulty.
- **Class imbalance and data scarcity:** A severe scarcity of high-quality, annotated datasets for rare or specific disaster types is being experienced. Even within existing datasets, a significant class imbalance is often observed; for instance, pixels representing “survivors” or “flooded buildings” are vastly outnumbered by “background” pixels. Models are biased toward the majority class by this imbalance, leading to reduced sensitivity to the critical smaller classes necessary for effective response.

2.3.1.1 Object detection architectures

Current SOTA methodologies for disaster response and remote sensing are dominated by the evolution of the “You Only Look Once” (YOLO) family for real-time edge computing, the emergence of Transformer-based set prediction, and the recent integration of Vision-Language Models (VLMs) for reasoning tasks.

The YOLO family and one-stage variants

The YOLO [Redmon16] series remains the standard for balancing speed and accuracy in resource-constrained environments. The progression from YOLOv1-v8 has transitioned from grid-based approaches to anchor-free architectures with improved backbones (e.g., CSPDarknet) and feature fusion, widely adopted for real-time generic detection. Recent iterations focus on architectural efficiency, with YOLOv9 introducing the Programmable Gradient Information and GELAN to resolve information bottlenecks [Wang24A, Hakani24]. YOLOv10 [Wang24B] optimizes end-to-end detection for edge deployment, balancing accuracy with resilience [Ciccone25]. YOLO11 [Khanam24] utilizes advanced convolutional layers for feature extraction in aerial disaster response, enabling real-time identification of rescuers and victims [Pattankudi25]. YOLO-NAS [DECI25] employs Neural Architecture Search (NAS) to optimize structures for high recall in post-disaster ruins [Song24]. Finally, Yolo-Edge [Li25A] adapts the backbone (MobileNetV3) for small-target wildfire detection on edge hardware [Li21A].

Figure 8 The network architecture of YOLO-Edge

Transformer-based detectors

Transformers have shifted detection toward direct set prediction, eliminating the need for anchors and non-maximum suppression (NMS). The DETR [Carion20] model introduced the transformer encoder-decoder architecture with bipartite matching. Subsequent iterations addressed convergence and small-object performance: DDETR [Zhu21B] utilizes deformable attention for faster convergence, while DAB-DETR [Liu22] introduces dynamic anchor boxes as queries with positional priors. Currently, DINO [Zhang22] achieves SOTA results via contrastive denoising and mixed query selection. STPM_SAH [Lin22] combines a Swin Transformer backbone with slicing aided hyper inference to improve small-target forest fire detection.

Figure 9 The structure of the forest STPM_SAHl model used for forest fire detection

Global-local strategies

Addressing the scale challenge in drone-view detection, the GLSAN [Deng21] method employs a two-step process: roughly recognizing objects in down-sampled global images, then dynamically selecting crowded regions for high-resolution fine detection.

Vision-language and Foundation models

Foundation models (FMs) are increasingly leveraged for zero-shot detection and complex reasoning in disaster scenarios. The Segment Anything Model (SAM) [Kirillov23] allows for zero-shot identification of damage via visual prompting [Zhao25]. PSALM [Zhang24] utilizes a multi-modal backbone to generate mask proposals for referring segmentation tasks. Models like LISA [Lai24] interpret complex instructions to segment objects in disaster scenes. Furthermore, Vision-Language Models (VLMs) such as Qwen2.5-VL [Bai25] and InternVL3 [Zhu25] are now evaluated for their ability to reason about object relationships and count damaged structures in post-disaster imagery [Wang25A].

Figure 10 VLM capabilities showcased by the DisasterM3 dataset

2.3.1.2 Image segmentation architectures

Segmentation architectures in remote sensing and disaster response have evolved from standard CNN-based encoder-decoder structures to complex, attention-driven transformer models and FMs capable of zero-shot reasoning.

CNN-based and classic architectures

Foundational architectures continue to serve as baselines or backbones for modern applications. SegNet [Badrinarayanan17] provides a basic trainable structure with pixel-wise classification layers [Ahmed24, Li24A]. U-Net [Zetout25], originally for biomedical imaging, utilizes symmetric skip connections to preserve fine spatial features, making it a staple in aerial domains [Ronneberger15]. The DeepLab Family (v1-v3+) [Chen15, Chen18A] applies atrous convolutions to enlarge receptive fields without increasing parameters, and DeepLabv3+ improves boundary refinement through its decoder. PSPNet [Zhao17] uses pyramid pooling to collect multi-scale context. Real-time processing has been

supported by ENet [Paszke16] through bottleneck modules, LinkNet [Chaurasia17] through efficient encoder-decoder transmission, DenseNet-C [Huang17] through feature map compression, and EfficientNet [Tan19] through optimized scaling. R-CNN derivatives include HTC [Chen19A] which exploits both local and global context, MaskLab [Chen18B] which improves mask refinement, and Panoptic FPN [Kirillov19A], which combines semantic and instance segmentation in a single framework.

U-Net variants and domain-specific hybrids

The U-Net architecture has seen extensive modification to handle the spatiotemporal and environmental challenges of disaster scenarios. Several U-Net variants have been adapted for remote sensing tasks. U-Net++ [Zhou18] has been designed with nested dense convolutional blocks to reduce the semantic gap between encoder and decoder and has been applied to general aerial imagery. FFS-UNet [Shahid23] integrates a temporal transformer module into a lightweight U-Net and has been used for video semantic segmentation in forest fire scenarios. FlameTransNet [Chen23A] combines a MobileNetV2 backbone with a transformer module and a DeepLabV3+ decoder, and has been applied to forest flame segmentation. FBC-ANet [Zhang23A] relies on an Xception encoder and separable convolutions to reduce the number of parameters, targeting forest fire data. Deep-RegSeg [Ghali22] uses RegNet backbones to operate in challenging environments and focuses on fire pixel segmentation. SiameseDiffUNet [Jia24] employs a shared-weight encoder to compute element-wise absolute differences for change detection in high-resolution imagery [Cha25]. SiamAttnUNet [Adriano21] extends Siamese U-Net with attention mechanisms for building damage assessment. CSDNet [Zetout25] incorporates lightweight transformers and detection-guided feature fusion for context-aware segmentation. SFBSNet [Song21] is built on SqueezeNet with depthwise separable convolutions and has been applied to binary fire image segmentation.

Transformer, Mamba-based, and hybrid models

Recent architectures have shifted toward Transformers for global dependency modeling and State Space Models (Mamba) for efficiency. SegFormer [Xie21] is based on a hierarchical transformer encoder combined with a lightweight (Multi-Layer Perceptron) MLP decoder, and positional encoding is not required [Nugraha25]. OneFormer [Jain23] introduces a unified transformer architecture for different segmentation tasks. Mask2Former [Cheng22] applies masked attention, which allows small objects to be segmented more reliably. Emerging models like ChangeMamba [Chen24] and RS3Mamba [Ma24A] leverage spatiotemporal state space models to balance long-range modeling with computational efficiency. Hybrid models such as TransUNet [Chen21A] and UNetFormer [Wang22A] integrate U-Net architectures with vision transformers to effectively capture both local and global dependencies. Additionally, DamageFormer [Chen22A] utilizes a pseudo-Siamese Swin-Transformer-Tiny encoder for the purpose of damage assessment.

Figure 11 The DamFormer architecture

YOLO-based real-time instance segmentation

The YOLO framework has been successfully adapted from pure detection to instance segmentation, offering a balance of speed and accuracy critical for UAVs. The evolution from YOLOv5-Seg to YOLOv9-Seg illustrates a trajectory of increasing accuracy and architectural refinement, such as GELAN in v9, with YOLOv8-seg noted for providing bounding boxes and masks via a lightweight head [Zou24, Sirma25]. Methods like YOLACT [Bolya19] (prototype masks) and SOLO (grid-based location prediction) provide alternative single-stage segmentation pathways [Gui24].

Figure 12 The YOLOACT architecture

Vision-language and Foundation models

The integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) allows for promptable and reasoning-based segmentation. The SAM [Kirillov23] has standardized zero-shot segmentation via points, boxes, or text. SEEM [Zou23] extends this by encoding diverse prompt types into a joint representation space. Models like LISA [Lai24] and PSALM [Zhang24] interpret complex text instructions to generate masks, effectively bridging the gap between natural language and pixel-wise segmentation. GeoPixel [Shabbir25] and HyperSeg [Wei25] utilize adaptive dividers and fine-grained encoders, respectively, to handle the unique high-resolution demands of aerial imagery in referential tasks.

Figure 13 The pixel grounding capabilities of GeoPixel

2.3.2 Implemented solutions

The methodological framework adopted in this work builds upon the findings of the dataset analysis in section 2.1 and the review of SOTA deep learning architectures for remote-sensing applications in section 2.3.1. Given the diversity and complexity of the use cases, covering wildfires, floods, and earthquakes, special attention has been placed on selecting approaches that can operate reliably across heterogeneous sensing conditions, varying spatial resolutions, and multi-hazard scenarios. The adopted methods address two core objectives: (i) assigning a class to every pixel in the image through semantic segmentation, and (ii) detecting and localizing important objects or structures through object detection. Model selection for both tasks was based on findings from the literature on disaster-related remote sensing and on preliminary benchmarking.

The following subsections present the selected approaches in detail. Section 2.3.2.1 describes the segmentation strategy and the deep learning architectures evaluated for identifying flooded regions, damaged buildings and other classes. Section 2.3.2.2 outlines the adopted object detection methodology, including the detector architectures and backbone choices to localize assets, structural elements or hazard indicators pertinent to the use-cases.

2.3.2.1 Image segmentation methods

The selection of segmentation models for the experiments was driven by two principal criteria. First, each selected architecture has been established in the literature as a SOTA or near SOTA method on disaster-oriented datasets, such as RescueNet [Rahneemoonfar23] and FloodNet [Rahneemoonfar21]/FloodNet+ [Zhao24A]. Second, the chosen models represent complementary architectural paradigms (CNN-based, transformer-based, hybrid attention-based), which enable a systematic comparison of their respective inductive biases in the context of disaster analysis.

Experiments on RescueNet employed SegFormer [Xie21], PSPNet [Zhao17] and Attention-UNet [Oktay18], as these models are adopted as baselines in UAV-based disaster segmentation literature [Rahneemoonfar23, Asad23, Safavi22]. For the FloodNet+ [Zhao24A] dataset, additional models DeepLabV3+ [Chen18A] and CCNet [Huang19] were incorporated to assess the behaviour of context-aggregation and global-attention architectures on large-scale flooding imagery. Across both datasets, each model serves a distinct conceptual purpose, enabling a representative evaluation of SOTA segmentation design patterns.

SegFormer

SegFormer [Xie21] is a transformer-based segmentation architecture that couples the Mix Transformer (MiT) hierarchical encoder with a lightweight MLP decoder. This design provides strong global contextual reasoning while keeping computational cost relatively low. SegFormer is widely reported as SOTA on remote-sensing and disaster-related benchmarks, where it consistently outperforms CNN models in capturing long-range dependencies, an essential capability for differentiating large homogeneous regions such as water bodies or mudfields.

Figure 14 SegFormer architecture diagram

PSPNet

PSPNet [Zhao17] represents a foundational SOTA model for multi-scale semantic segmentation. Its Pyramid Pooling Module aggregates contextual information over multiple spatial extents, which is particularly effective when segmenting flooded areas, shadows, and regions with large intra-class variation. PSPNet is frequently reported in the literature as a benchmark model for FloodNet and other aerial disaster datasets, thus providing a reliable, reproducible point of comparison against more recent transformer-based architectures.

Figure 15 PSPNet architecture diagram

Attention-UNet

Attention-UNet [Oktay18] extends the classical encoder-decoder architecture with attention gates that suppress irrelevant background information and highlight semantically important regions. This characteristic aligns well with the challenges in RescueNet, where small-scale objects (vehicles, debris

patches, narrow road segments) require high spatial precision. As UNet-type models remain highly competitive for medical and remote-sensing images with strong structural regularities, Attention-UNet provides an interpretable, lower-complexity baseline relative to the more advanced models tested.

Figure 16 Attention-UNet architecture diagram

DeepLabV3+

DeepLabV3+ [Chen18A] integrates Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling with an encoder-decoder refinement module, offering strong boundary delineation and multi-scale feature extraction. It has been extensively used as a SOTA model in the flood-segmentation literature, including in experiments on the FloodNet benchmark. Its ability to maintain fine edges while simultaneously capturing large receptive fields makes it well suited to the heterogeneous classes of FloodNet+, where both large, flooded regions and fine structural elements must be accurately identified. Its inclusion ensures the representation of high-resolution CNN-based segmentation approaches in the comparative evaluation.

Figure 17 DeepLabV3+ architecture diagram

CCNet

CCNet [Huang19] introduces a recurrent criss-cross attention mechanism that efficiently aggregates global contextual information without the computational cost of full self-attention. This architecture addresses limitations observed in CNN-only models when dealing with highly cluttered or spatially complex environments, which are typical in post-disaster imagery. CCNet has been applied in multiple remote-sensing segmentation tasks with strong results, particularly in scenarios with dense urban

structures and occlusions. Its behaviour on FloodNet+ provides insight into the performance of global-attention CNNs relative to transformers such as SegFormer.

Figure 18 CCNet architecture diagram

2.3.2.2 Object detection methods

The experimental procedure was based on architectures utilizing CNNs, transformer-based models, and hybrid models. Each of these models serves a clearly differentiated conceptual role across the selected datasets, making sure our evaluation does indeed capture the diversity of modern design paradigms and provides a representative assessment of how SOTA methods behave under various conditions. For the selected datasets, models that reported the highest mAP values in the literature were selected, so as to establish the strongest possible benchmark baseline. The SOTA results of D-fire [Jiang25, Li25B] include the Nano variants of YOLO10-12, as well as RT-DETR. These models were chosen for their low parameter count and suitability for real-time deployment on UAV platforms. The SOTA results [Siouras22, Wang25B] on the LADD dataset were achieved using larger CNN model variants, which delivered the highest performance metrics at this benchmark. The validity of these benchmark results is confirmed by considering only experiments that reported high metrics and provided published code, rather than attempting to reproduce every experiment.

YOLO

The YOLO [Redmon16] family models, and more so the recent ones, incorporate a minimalistic one-stage detector structure optimized with efficient convolutional architectures such as CSPDarknet. Fast and dense feature extraction capabilities make these models ideal candidates for environments with-the-need rapid identification and localization of small or very localized objects, as may be witnessed in a post-disaster scenario. More specifically, YOLOv5 provides a solid baseline, combining a Cross Stage Partial (CSP) backbone with Mosaic and AutoAugment data augmentation techniques. In the next YOLO benchmark, YOLO11 enhances the convolutional layers and feature-extraction blocks while also improving multi-scale fusion within the PAN/FPN structure, resulting in better cross-resolution consistency and smoother gradient flow. YOLO12 continues and further strengthens the architecture by adding attention-based feature aggregation, a redesigned neck for more efficient spatial and semantic mixing, and refined box regression losses, which optimize object localization under occlusions or crowded scenes. YOLO10, despite its earlier numbering, focuses on reducing computational load through pruning, narrower channel widths, and simpler connections between the backbone and neck, thereby achieving faster inference without sacrificing accuracy. Within various remote sensing and aerial imagery problems, it has been noticed that various variants of YOLO perform impressively on identifying fine features such as debris, roofs, and isolated objects. Evaluator experiments on FloodNet+ make it easier to evaluate the relevance of high-speed CNN detectors compared to global-attention CNN hybrids and transformer architectures on segmentation tasks.

Figure 19 Key architectural modules in YOLOv11

RT-DETR

RT-DETR [Zhao24B] was developed as a real-time detector capable of achieving the performance of YOLO-based approaches, in order to address the issues of slow inference and NMS faced by the original DETR models. This is a hybrid model that introduces significant improvements for increasing accuracy and speed. It is based on the DETR architecture with a ResNet backbone. It handles multi-scale features efficiently through an effective hybrid encoder, which prevents bottlenecks and ensures smoother feature integration. The selection of queries with minimal uncertainty reduces redundancy and enhances prediction reliability by giving priority to those with high localization confidence. RT-DETR offers variable inference speed without compromising performance, while retaining the multi-layer decoder of DETR. The above enhancements allow RT-DETR to provide reliable bounding boxes and class scores, while maintaining the effectiveness required for real-time object recognition applications.

Figure 20 RT-DETR architecture

RF-DETR

RF-DETR [Robinson25] is a real time transformer object detection model created by Roboflow that balances accuracy and efficiency. Its core is a pretrained DINOv2 backbone, which extracts rich, multistage feature representations suitable for a variety of domains. Its backbone allows effective adaptation to domain specific tasks, such as small object detection or agricultural scenarios, without retraining from scratch. Like RT-DETR, it shares the core DETR’s style architecture, based on an encoder/decoder transformer design. The model uses an anchor free and NMS free transformer encoder/decoder, allowing it to focus on spatially relevant features and handle occlusions, clutter, or camouflage. A multilayer decoder iteratively refines the predictions, and the detection heads generate the final bounding boxes and class scores.

Figure 21 The overview of RF-DETR architecture

DEIMV2

DEIMv2 [Huang25A] is based on the DETR family and further expands the earlier DEIM/RT-DETR architecture by including stronger backbone choices and better multiscale feature processing. The larger variants are based on DINOv3 or DINOv3-distilled ViT backbones, while the Spatial Tuning Adapter transforms their originally single-scale feature outputs to multiscale representations suitable for dense detection. More lightweight variants, on the other hand, use pruned HGNetv2 backbones in order to maintain architecture efficiency on resource-constrained platforms. Transformer decoder optimization for real-time performance includes shared positional embeddings and streamlined attention operations that reduce computation but with no degradation in accuracy. Further improvement in training includes Dense O2O supervision, along with the Copy-Blend augmentation strategy for enriching object-level learning. DEIMv2 also adjusts the set and weighting of loss components across its model scales-omitting certain auxiliary losses in the smallest variants for avoiding over-regularization and better matching their reduced capacity. This design allows DEIMv2 to further reach competitive accuracy while maintaining low latency across model sizes and hence serves as a representative example of modern efficient transformer-based detectors.

Figure 22 Overview of the DEIMv2 architecture

2.3.3 Experimental evaluation

This section presents the experimental configuration and the quantitative results obtained for the vision components. The focus is on evaluating deep learning models for semantic segmentation and object detection on the curated datasets, which comprise representative remote-sensing imagery for wildfires,

floods, and earthquakes. The goal is to compare SOTA architectures under a common, controlled setup and to assess their suitability for inclusion in the TRIFFID processing pipeline.

The segmentation and detection experiments share the same high-level protocol: data are split into training, validation, and test sets following the conventions established in the corresponding dataset publications, models are trained using standard optimization settings recommended in the original papers and performance is reported using widely adopted metrics for dense prediction and object detection. The semantic segmentation setup and results of two post-disaster datasets, RescueNet and FloodNet+, are detailed in Section 2.3.3.2, while Section 2.3.3.3 focuses on the object detection experiments conducted on two datasets: LADD and D-Fire.

2.3.3.1 Evaluation metrics

The primary evaluation metric for semantic segmentation is the mIoU, computed across all semantic classes in the dataset. For a given class t , the IoU is defined as:

$$IoU_t = \frac{\text{Area of Overlap}}{\text{Area of Union}}$$

where the numerator corresponds to the number of correctly predicted pixels for that class (true positives), and the denominator corresponds to the total number of pixels assigned to that class in either the prediction or ground truth (true positives, false positives, and false negatives).

Given C semantic classes, the mean IoU is obtained by averaging the per-class IoUs:

$$mIoU = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{t=1}^C IoU_t$$

In addition to the global mIoU, reporting per-class IoU values is critical for understanding model behaviour on specific semantic categories. This is particularly relevant in aerial post-disaster imagery, where class imbalance is pronounced: large-area classes (e.g., water, grass) dominate pixel distributions, while small, sparse classes (e.g., vehicles, pools) are substantially underrepresented and thus more challenging to segment.

For object detection, the evaluation metric employed is mAP50, which quantifies the mAP at an IoU threshold of 0.50. A detection is considered a true positive when the IoU between the predicted and ground truth bounding boxes meets or exceeds 0.50. For each object category, the \mathbf{b} (AP) is computed as the area under the precision-recall curve:

$$AP = \int_0^1 P(r) dr$$

The overall detection performance is reported as:

$$mAP50 = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{t=1}^m AP_t$$

where m denotes the number of object categories. The mAP50 metric captures the model's capability to accurately localize and classify objects with sufficient spatial overlap, with higher values indicating stronger detection performance.

2.3.3.2 Results for the segmentation task

The selected methods performing semantic segmentation were evaluated on two datasets, each dedicated to a separate use case: RescueNet for post-earthquake damage assessment and FloodNet+ for large-scale flood analysis. These datasets allow evaluation of model performance under the distinct visual and structural conditions characteristic of each hazard type.

Results for the RescueNet dataset

The architectures were evaluated: SegFormer, PSPNet and Attention-UNet. For each architecture, the training configuration followed the respective reference implementation. Specifically, SegFormer was trained for 500 epochs. PSPNet and Attention-UNet trained for 100 epochs. We implement data augmentation for all models to avoid overfitting, implementing scaling, flipping, random shuffling and zooming.

Table 3 RescueNet: comparison of model performance

Model	Backbone	mIoU
SegFormer	MiT-B4	95.58%
PSPNet	ResNet101	93.39%
Attention UNET	-	89.46%

Overall, the results confirm the expected hierarchy between architectures. SegFormer achieves the highest mIoU. Its performance is particularly strong on large-area and mid-scale classes, such as debris, water, trees, sand and the various building damage levels. The only systematically weaker category is vehicles, with an IoU of 86.23%, which remains significantly lower than the large structural classes. This gap is consistent with the characteristics of the dataset: vehicles appear as small objects in top-down imagery, frequently occluded by debris or shadows, and are thus more sensitive to coarse sampling and transformer patch size.

Figure 23 Bar diagram of per-class IoU performance on the RescueNet dataset across the different methods. PSPNet attains a slightly lower mIoU but still maintains high performance on homogeneous, large-scale classes, e.g. water, tree, road-clear. The Pyramid Scene Parsing module effectively aggregates multi-scale context and is well suited to distinguishing flooded versus non-flooded surfaces and different road states. However, the CNN-only backbone has more difficulty capturing subtle differences among the multiple building damage classes compared to the transformer-based SegFormer, and IoU for vehicles drops further. This suggests that while contextual pooling is effective for global structure, the limited

global receptive field compared to transformers can lead to less robust representations for small, cluttered objects.

Attention-UNet yields the lowest mIoU in this comparison. On RescueNet, the architecture still performs adequately for large classes, but struggles more significantly on the intermediate and difficult classes, e.g. medium and major building damage around 84.2-84.3% IoU, road-blocked at 74.56%. Architecturally, the encoder-decoder with attention gates is well suited to highlighting salient regions, but lacks the explicit multi-scale context fusion and global attention present in SegFormer and PSPNet, which appears to be critical for robust performance on complex, multi-class urban damage scenes.

These results indicate that SegFormer provides the best trade-off between overall accuracy and robustness across class scales on RescueNet. PSPNet offers a strong, well-understood CNN baseline, while Attention-UNet remains valuable for comparison as a compact architecture with interpretable attention mechanisms, yet is less competitive in this particular multi-class, post-disaster setting.

Results for the FloodNet+ dataset

Four architectures were assessed on FloodNet+: SegFormer (MiT-B4), DeepLabV3+ (ResNet-101), PSPNet (ResNet-101) and CCNet (ResNet-101). SegFormer was trained using the same configuration as in the RescueNet experiments, including the 700x700 input resolution, learning rate schedule and augmentation pipeline. For DeepLabV3+, PSPNet and CCNet, all images were resized to 512x512 and training followed a polynomial learning-rate policy with a base learning rate of 1×10^{-2} , using SGD optimisation. Data augmentation, consisting of random flips, scaling, random shuffling and cropping was applied across all models to improve generalisation on the highly variable flood imagery. Their overall mIoU scores are shown in Table 3.

Table 4 FloodNet+ comparison of model performance

Model	Backbone	mIoU
SegFormer	MiT-B4	78.56%
PSPNet	ResNet101	72.88%
CCNet	ResNet101	72.47%
DeepLabV3+	ResNet101	72.25%

Figure 24 Bar diagram of per-class IoU performance on the FloodNet+ dataset across the different methods SegFormer again achieves the highest overall mIoU (78.56%), its per-class IoUs confirm strong performance on both large homogeneous regions and more complex classes. As in RescueNet, the weakest class is vehicles, with an IoU of 63.35%, and to a lesser extent pools with an IoU of 66.16%.

Both represent small, frequently occluded structures whose footprint occupies only a small fraction of the image, making them sensitive to resolution, class imbalance and annotation noise.

The three CNN-based models, DeepLabV3+, PSPNet and CCNet, achieve very similar overall mIoU, in the 72-73% range. Among the CNN-based models, CCNet achieves the highest mIoU, slightly surpassing both DeepLabV3+ and PSPNet. This suggests that the criss-cross attention mechanism successfully captures long-range dependencies in the flood scenes without incurring the full complexity of a transformer encoder. In terms of per-class performance, the three CNN architectures show similar trends: high IoU for grass and trees, good performance on water, and noticeably lower IoU for vehicles and pools. For example, vehicle IoU ranges from 41.68% for DeepLabV3+ to 46.32% for CCNet, with pool IoU between 55.99% and 60.91%. These results underline the intrinsic difficulty of small-object segmentation in aerial flood imagery, where vehicles and pools often appear as a few pixels and may be partially submerged or obscured.

Comparing SegFormer with the CNN-based models on FloodNet+ highlights the benefits of hybrid transformer architectures for this type of dataset. SegFormer provides consistently higher IoU for all large and mid-scale classes (buildings, roads, water, trees, grass), while also improving performance on vehicles and pools relative to the CNN baselines. The MiT backbone's ability to integrate global context across the scene appears particularly beneficial in distinguishing flooded from non-flooded surfaces under complex lighting and reflection conditions, where local texture alone is insufficient.

2.3.3.3 Results for the object detection task

The selected object detection methods were evaluated on two datasets, each corresponding to a distinct application scenario: LADD for aerial human detection and D-Fire for wildfire-related fire and smoke detection. These datasets enable the assessment of detection performance under the different visual characteristics associated with each use case.

Results for the LADD dataset

The experimental setup adopts a three-way split of the LADD dataset, allocating 70% for training, 20% for validation, and 10% for testing. All models were initialized with pretrained weights. The YOLO variants were trained for 100 epochs using model checkpoints. RF-DETR was fine-tuned via transfer learning with a pretrained checkpoint and employed early stopping with a patience of 10. RT-DETR was trained for 80 epochs, while DEIMv2 was trained for 60 epochs. All models used an input image resolution of 640, except RF-DETR, which was trained with a resolution of 672.

Table 5 Overall detection performance for each evaluated model on the LADD

Model	Parameters (M)	Method/ Approach	Backbone	mAP50	mAP[50-95]
YOLO-v5 Small	7.20	CNN-based	CSPDarknet53	74.20%	46.30%
YOLO-v5 Large	46.50	CNN-based	CSPDarknet53	95.80%	51.90%
YOLO-v11 Large	25.30	CNN-based	CSP-based (Conv + C3k2 + SPPF + C2PSA)	86.10%	51.00%
RF-DETR Base	29.0	Transformer-based	Small DINOv2 with	95.05%	56,40%

			Windowed Attention		
DEIMv2 Medium	18.0	Transformer -based	ViT-Tiny+ (DINOv3-distilled, 12 layers, hidden dim = 256)	85.50%	51.40%
DEIMv2 Large	32.0	Transformer -based	ViT-Small (DINOv3 pretrained, 12 layers, hidden dim = 384)	93.40%	55.30%
RT-DETR Large	42.0	Hybrid	Resnet50	92.00%	58.30%

The experimental evaluation of the models on the LADD Dataset reveals clear differences in the performance strategies of the examined architectures. The YOLO family demonstrated notable scalability: YOLOv5 Small provided a stable baseline, where we achieved an mAP of 74.20%. In contrast, YOLOv5 Large variant achieved the highest absolute performance in the comparison, reaching 95.80% mAP. The use of the largest YOLOv5 variant served to directly compare it with one of the most modern models of the YOLO family, YOLO11 Large. This model, featuring a CSP architecture, reached 86.1% mAP.

Transformer and hybrid models' performance demonstrated the necessity of large scale pretraining (DINO). RF-DETR Base, which included a DINOv2 pretrained backbone and an anchor free DETR's style decoder, obtained a high mAP accuracy of 95.05%. This result is comparable to YOLOv5-Large but requires much fewer parameters, demonstrating ViT backbones' better efficiency in learning robust representations for small objects. Similarly, DEIMv2 Large with a ViT-Small backbone (DINOv3 pretrained) produced 93.40% mAP. In contrast, the DEIMv2 Medium variation (ViT-Tiny+ backbone) achieved just 85.50% mAP, highlighting the cost of distillation.

Overall, the results indicate that the YOLOv5 Large variant slightly outperforms even the most modern Transformer-based architectures, such as the DEIMv2. This can be explained by two primary factors. First, YOLOv5 Large has a very strong CNN backbone, CSPDarknet53, which is optimised for dense, local feature extraction, which is optimal for small targets. On the other hand, transformers are performing well on capturing global attention relationships of a scene. Second, transformer architectures are data-hungry. Since the LADD dataset, is relatively small, YOLOv5-L is able to learn the important features more effectively than the Transformer-based architectures, where the additional attention mechanisms do not provide proportional benefits.

Nonetheless, RF-DETR is the second most competitive choice in terms of performance, since it combines a smaller parameter count with sophisticated Transformer components to achieve accuracy comparable to YOLOv5-L while being more efficient. The results demonstrate the advantages of RF-DETR, including its effective training dynamics, which include noticeably faster convergence, and its strong localisation accuracy in crowded and partially obstructed scenarios. The foundational DINOv2 backbone is largely responsible for these performance improvements as it enhances feature extraction quality.

Results for the D-Fire dataset

The experimental split on the D-Fire dataset that was adapted in this work is 80% training set and 20% test set. The evaluation consisted of two main stages: reproducing the previous research's results and extending them with more powerful models. In the first stage, the nano variants of the YOLO models YOLO10, YOLO11, and YOLO12 were trained with shared hyperparameters: a batch size of 20, 100 epochs, an image resolution of 640, and a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} . Apart from the nano variants, the larger version of the most modern YOLO architecture was also used with the same hyperparameters. The second stage expanded the experiments by incorporating large variants (YOLO11) as well as more advanced architectures. The RT-DETR model used the same settings except for a reduced batch size of 8. RF-DETR was trained at a resolution of 672 with a batch size of 8 for 100 epochs, using early stopping with a patience of 8 epochs and a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} . The most current model, DEIMv2, was trained for 60 epochs with a batch size of 8 and a learning rate of 5×10^{-4} .

Table 6 Overall detection performance for each evaluated model on the D-Fire

Model	Parameters (M)	Method/ Approach	Backbone	mAP50	mAP [50-95]
YOLO-v12 Nano	2.7	CNN-based	CSPDarknet-Nano	71.10%	47.20%
YOLO-v11 Large	25.3	CNN-based	CSPDarknet-Large (v11)	75.70%	47.00%
YOLO-v11 Nano	2.7	CNN-based	CSPDarknet-Nano (v11)	71.60%	46.70%
YOLO-v10 Nano	2.6	CNN-based	CSPDarknet-Nano (v10)	72.50%	46.00%
RF-DETR Base	29.0	Transformer-based	Small DINOv2 with Windowed Attention	69.62%	44.50%
RT-DETR Large	42.0	Hybrid	ResNet-50	78.22%	45.30%
DEIMv2 Large	32.0	Transformer-based	ViT-Small (DINOv3-pretrained)	79.90%	44.20%

Figure 25 Bar diagram comparison of fire and smoke detection performance across models

Table 6 indicates that the model with the highest overall mAP50 accuracy on the D-Fire dataset is the DEIMv2, achieving an mAP equal to 79.90%. That confirms the superior ability of the DINOv3 backbone to extract richer and more generalizable features. It is closely followed by RT-DETR, with an mAP of 78.22%, a hybrid architecture utilizing ResNet50.

The results show that high-performance CNN-based detectors continue offering strong accuracy, especially larger models. For example, YOLO11-Large achieves one of the best overall balances between accuracy and model size, with an AP of 75.70 despite containing only 25.3M parameters. Even the lightweight YOLO Nano variants consistently offer competitive results in the 71-72 AP range, which further reinforces that CSPDarknet-based backbones are still very effective, providing an excellent trade-off between efficiency and performance. Interestingly, the YOLOv10-Nano slightly outperformed the YOLO11-Nano. This means that, sometimes, incremental changes in architecture across versions may not always manifest as an improvement at the tiniest model scale.

By comparison, results for Transformer-based architectures are decidedly more mixed. Despite strong global modeling and pretraining on DINO backbones, RF-DETR and DEIMv2 lag behind the top-performing CNNs on AP, reflecting the challenges that Transformers often face when applied to small datasets. Stronger results obtained with RT-DETR Large, a hybrid model relying on a CNN feature extractor combined with Transformer decoding, hint at hybrid architecture as the way towards a better balance between global context and sensitivity to localized features. Overall, the comparison underlines the fact that whereas Transformers do bring interesting improvements in terms of convergence speed and context modeling capabilities, high-quality CNNs retain a distinct advantage when training data are limited and the detection targets are small and spatially dense.

In fire detection, Transformer and Hybrid models appear to outperform the others, with DEIMv2 (75.9%) achieving the highest performance. This demonstrates that attention mechanisms are more effective in capturing the shapes of fire.

In contrast, the CNN Nano variants dominate smoke detection, with YOLO12 Nano (86.0%) outperforming all others, closely followed by YOLO11 Nano (85.5%). RT-DETR also demonstrated competitive performance, due to its ResNet backbone. This consistent strength in architectures based on CNN backbones highlights their effectiveness in smoke detection tasks. The satisfactory extraction

of textural and color patterns achieved by CNN backbones makes them particularly effective for this specific problem.

Table 7 Per-class detection performance for evaluated models on D-Fire

Model	Fire mAP50	Fire mAP[50-95]	Smoke mAP50	Smoke mAP[50-95]
YOLO-v12 Nano	72.00%	39.20%	86.00%	55.10%
YOLO-v11 Large	69.10%	37.10%	82.40%	54.70%
YOLO-v11 Nano	71.60%	38.70%	85.50%	51.50%
YOLO-v10 Nano	71.10%	38.10%	83.90%	54.00%
RF-DETR Base	61.60%	37.10%	77.65%	51.30%
RT-DETR Large	73.60%	38.30%	85.30%	52.20%
DEIMv2 Large	75.90%	41.22%	83.89%	53.62%

2.4 Ground-level visual scene analysis

2.4.1 Review of state-of-the-art methods

The urgency of modern SAR missions is emphasized by the strong time dependence of victim recovery. Most disaster-related casualties occur within the first 72 hours, which means that rapid response has a direct effect on survival outcomes [Cafolla26]. Risks linked to traditional human-led operations in dangerous settings have been reduced through the use of UGVs. These platforms provide immediate situational awareness and allow responders to operate without direct exposure to hazards [CruzUlloa21]. This section examines the state of the art in object detection and segmentation models used in post-disaster conditions. The focus is placed on ground-level observations needed to locate victims and evaluate structural damage.

Key challenges for ground-level perception

Deploying CV models on UGVs for SAR presents unique difficulties that differ significantly from standard object detection. The effectiveness of perception algorithms is fundamentally constrained by the chaotic nature of post-disaster environments, hardware limitations, and data scarcity. The primary challenges include:

- **Environmental and visual degradation:** UGVs must operate in unstable, collapsed structures often containing toxic materials. In these unstructured zones, visibility is drastically compromised by smoke, dust, and the complete absence of light, causing the performance of standard vision systems to degrade significantly.
- **Occlusion and perspective:** Victims are frequently occluded by debris, located in confined spaces, or camouflaged by surrounding rubble. Furthermore, the ground-level viewpoint of a UGV introduces severe perspective distortion and scale variations that are not typically present in general surveillance datasets.
- **Sensory limitations:** No single sensing modality provides a complete solution. While RGB cameras provide intuition, they fail in low light. Thermal sensors address this but become unreliable when victims are near competing heat sources, such as fires or running machinery.
- **Data scarcity and domain shift** remain major limitations. A critical shortage of high-quality, disaster-specific datasets has been reported. Models trained on generic benchmarks such as COCO or PASCAL VOC often fail to generalize to the visual characteristics of damaged structures. The

creation of specialized datasets is labor-intensive and usually depends on expert supervision to limit annotator disagreement.

- **Computational constraints:** Complex deep learning models must be deployed on resource-constrained mobile robots. This creates a critical need to balance high accuracy with the inference speed required for on-board, real-time processing, necessitating lightweight architectures that avoid latency-heavy components.

Figure 26 Sensor modality comparison. (a, c) RGB sensors fail in cluttered or low-light environments, while (b, d) thermal imaging successfully detects victims in identical conditions

2.4.1.1 Object detection architectures

The field of object detection has recently shifted toward architectures that combine CNNs with transformers. Earlier systems were mainly built on CNNs, but their limited ability to capture global context and their reliance on post-processing have motivated new designs. Current approaches integrate transformer modules to address these constraints and improve overall detection performance. The field is currently defined by three major trends: the rise of real-time detection transformers that eliminate NMS, the integration of attention mechanisms into efficient CNN backbones, and the emergence of open-vocabulary FMs.

Real-time detection transformers

The introduction of the DETR challenged the reliance on anchor boxes and NMS, but initially suffered from high computational costs. Recent works have successfully adapted this architecture for real-time applications. RT-DETR [Zhao24B] pioneered this direction by proposing a hybrid encoder that decouples intra-scale interaction (using attention) from cross-scale fusion (using CNNs), allowing it to surpass YOLO speeds while maintaining global context. This architecture was further refined in RT-DETRv3 [Wang25C], which introduced hierarchical dense positive supervision to address the sparse supervision issues inherent in one-to-one matching, significantly accelerating training convergence. Parallel to this, D-FINE [Peng24] redefined the fundamental regression task in DETRs. Instead of regressing fixed bounding box coordinates, it employs Fine-grained Distribution Refinement to predict probability distributions for box boundaries, achieving superior localization for small and occluded objects without the computational overhead of heavy backbones. Most recently, RF-DETR [Robinson25] leveraged NAS and a “receptive field” attention mechanism to optimize the trade-off between accuracy and latency, achieving industry-leading performance on COCO by effectively treating detection as a set prediction problem on a DINOv2 backbone.

Figure 27 Overview of the RT-DETR architecture

Evolution of CNN-based detectors

The YOLO series has evolved from pure CNNs into sophisticated hybrid architectures to maintain dominance in edge deployment. YOLOv8 [Jocher23] set a strong baseline with its anchor-free, decoupled head design, becoming a standard for practical deployment. However, subsequent iterations have focused on architectural efficiency and NMS elimination. YOLOv10 [Wang24B] introduced a consistent dual assignment strategy (using one-to-many assignment for training and one-to-one for inference), enabling NMS-Free end-to-end detection that drastically reduces inference latency. The focus then shifted toward feature richness with YOLOv11 [Jocher24], which integrated the C3k2 block and Spatial Attention (C2PSA) to enhance multi-scale feature extraction. The latest iteration, YOLOv12 [Tian25], represents a move toward “Attention-Centric” designs, replacing standard kernels with 7×7 separable convolutions and introducing the R-ELAN backbone with Area Attention. This design captures wider spatial contexts similar to transformers but retains the efficiency of CNNs. Concurrently, YOLO-NAS [DECI25] demonstrated the power of automated design, utilizing NAS to generate Quantization-Aware Blocks, ensuring that models retain high accuracy even when quantized to INT8 for resource-constrained edge devices.

Open-vocabulary and foundation models

Beyond closed-set detection, the field has moved toward generalized perception capable of detecting arbitrary objects via language prompts. Grounding DINO [Liu25A] merged the DINO detector with grounded pre-training, aligning visual and textual feature spaces to allow for zero-shot detection of novel concepts. Its successor, Grounding DINO 1.5 [Ren24B], optimized this architecture for edge scenarios, enabling efficient open-set detection on limited hardware. These FMs serve as critical components in modern “auto-labeling” pipelines, where they are used to annotate data for training smaller, distilled models like YOLO-World [Cheng24], which achieves real-time open-vocabulary detection by fusing vision and language features through a re-parameterizable path aggregation network.

2.4.1.2 Image segmentation architectures

Image segmentation research from 2023-2025 bifurcated into two complementary trends: (1) promptable FMs that prioritize broad zero-shot and interactive capabilities, and (2) unified transformer architectures that consolidate semantic, instance, and panoptic tasks into single trainable models.

Figure 28 Overview of the SAM architecture

Promptable foundation models

SAM introduced a promptable, class-agnostic paradigm trained on SA-1B and decoupled a large image encoder from a lightweight prompt decoder [Kirillov23]. Domain adaptations followed rapidly: MedSAM targets medical imaging and addresses domain generalization issues [Ma24B], while efficiency-driven variants such as FastSAM and FasterSAM replace or simplify the encoder for real-time or mobile deployment [Zhang23B, Zhao23A]. Subsequent extensions expanded promptable segmentation to video and concept-conditioned scenarios: SAM 2 adds streaming memory for temporal segmentation [Ravi24], and SAM 3 incorporates exemplar- and concept-level prompting [Carion25].

Unified transformer architectures

Transformer-based universal segmentors matured into widely adopted SOTA systems. Mask2Former introduced masked attention as a universal decoder [Cheng22], establishing a strong baseline across semantic/instance/panoptic tasks. Mask DINO integrated mask prediction into the DINO [Zhang22] detector and advanced SOTA instance and panoptic performance [Li23A]. OneFormer unified these tasks by using task-conditioned queries within a single architecture [Jain23]. Subsequent refinements, including MP-Former’s mask-piloted training and DI-MaskDINO’s improved detection-segmentation balancing, further stabilized training and improved benchmarks [Zhang23C, Nan24].

Open-vocabulary and multimodal segmentation

Scaling segmentation beyond closed label sets leveraged vision-language alignment. OpenSeg aligned visual regions with text embeddings to support arbitrary concept segmentation [Ghiasi22]. SEEM broadened the prompt space (text, visual, audio) to support interactive multimodal segmentation [Zou23]. Practical open-set pipelines frequently couple Grounding DINO with SAM, as in Grounded-SAM, enabling robust text-guided segmentation in diverse scenes. Work such as UniDetector decouples proposal generation from classification to detect novel categories under open-world conditions [Wang23A].

Generalist / in-context segmentation

A parallel line of work reframes segmentation as an in-context inference problem. SegGPT treats segmentation as a coloring task conditioned on example mappings, enabling rapid adaptation to new segmentation tasks without finetuning [Wang23B]. OMG-Seg extends this unification goal by supporting a wide range of segmentation modalities, such as semantic, instance, video, and interactive within one architecture via task-specific queries [Li24B].

Applied ground-level perception strategies

Generic architectures form the basis for object detection, but their direct use in SAR settings is limited. Specialized adaptation is required because post-disaster scenes introduce visual noise and irregular conditions. Recent work concentrates on three directions. The domain gap is reduced through datasets

that reflect the visual properties of damaged environments. Robustness is increased by combining information from several sensing modalities, which offsets incomplete or unreliable visual input. FMs are used for label-free segmentation to support scene understanding when annotated data is limited.

Domain-specific adaptation has moved toward data-centric methods because disaster-related training data remain scarce. Recent works have improved dataset quality, refined annotations, and created synthetic data samples instead of proposing new architectures. This aims to reduce the mismatch between generic datasets and the appearance of damaged environments so that existing models can perform more reliably in post-disaster scenarios. Addressing urban vulnerability, AlleyFloodNet [Lee25] established a benchmark for narrow, clutter-filled environments, validating the use of ConvNeXt-Large for ground-level flood detection. Similarly, to manage the visual noise of post-disaster scenes, [Zafar24] demonstrated that standard architectures like YOLOv8 can be effectively deployed without structural changes if trained on rigorously annotated “Human Detection” datasets containing simulated debris and smoke. Beyond detection, [Luo24] used ViTs to classify wildfire damage severity. The results verified that attention mechanisms can generalize across varied residential structures even when only limited training samples are available.

Multi-modal fusion and geometric integration have been used to address the limits of single-sensor systems. Recent studies combine RGB input with depth and thermal data to improve reliability in cluttered or low-visibility post-disaster environments. [Wang23C] integrated YOLOv4 with binocular depth data, fusing pixel coordinates with 3D point clouds to accurately project targets like fire extinguishers in 3D space. A progressive evolution of this strategy is evident in the work of Cruz-Ulloa et al., who initially employed geometric post-processing on YOLOv3 to distinguish lying victims from rescuers based on bounding box ratios [CruzUlloa21]. This approach evolved to encompass multispectral analysis, utilizing a novel Green-Red-NIR index with YOLOv5 to isolate human signatures [CruzUlloa23], and most recently adapting YOLOv8m to process concurrent RGB and thermal streams via channel replication [CruzUlloa24].

Real-Time Optimization for Edge Deployment: Deploying these models on resource-constrained UGVs requires a delicate balance between throughput and precision. In subterranean environments, [Lu22] benchmarked segmentation architectures, revealing a critical trade-off: while Mask R-CNN offered superior accuracy for survivor detection, it lacked the speed for real-time control, whereas real-time alternatives like Yolact suffered from noise sensitivity. To bridge this gap, [Ge25] proposed an optimized YOLOv7 for concrete crack detection, integrating Convolutional Block Attention Modules and K-means++ anchor initialization to improve feature extraction on embedded hardware without the computational penalty of heavier transformers.

Figure 29 Damaged area detection results comparison from DASeg

FMs and Interactive Segmentation: The most recent trend involves moving away from fixed-label training toward interactive, prompt-based perception. DASeg [Huang25B] introduced a domain-adaptive pipeline that unifies DINOv2, Grounding DINO, and a frozen SAM. This framework enables label-free segmentation via text and point prompts, significantly outperforming traditional CNN-based models like DeepLabV3+ and even supervised transformers like Mask2Former in identifying complex damage patterns. However, reliance on frozen backbones remains a bottleneck for low-contrast features. Parallel to this, SegFormer has been adopted for earthquake damage assessment, where its hierarchical transformer encoder effectively differentiates debris from undamaged structures without the complexity of positional encodings [Zhang25].

2.4.2 Implemented solutions

The methodological framework adopted for UGV scene analysis draws on the survey of SOTA ground-level vision methods in Section 2.4.1. Given the variability and complexity of ground-based disaster imagery, ranging from densely cluttered environments and irregular object geometries to large variations in scale and illumination, particular emphasis was placed on selecting architectures that reflect the principal modelling paradigms used in contemporary CV. The selected methods span CNN, transformer-based methods, FMs, and VLMs, ensuring architectural diversity and technical representativeness.

The following subsections detail the chosen approaches according to the three task categories defined for UGV visual analysis. Section 2.4.2.1 presents the multi-label classification models employed to characterise and validate the current sample of the Incidents1M dataset. Section 2.4.2.2 outlines the object detection methods used for hazardous-label recognition in ground imagery. Section 2.4.2.3

describes the methods deployed for the evaluation of the Incidents1M-Seg dataset, which is under development, comprising transformer-based segmenters, two-stage detectors, FM segmentation systems, and vision-language detectors.

2.4.2.1 Multi-label classification methods

For our classification experiments, we evaluated a range of diverse deep learning architectures representing different families of visual encoders: ResNet as a convolutional baseline, EfficientNet as a parameter-efficient CNN, ViT as a transformer-based model that relies on self-attention, and EfficientFormer as a hybrid architecture. All taken together, they span different inductive biases (convolutional vs. attention-based vs. hybrid) and model sizes, allowing us to study how these factors affect multi-label disaster classification performance.

ResNet

ResNet [He16] is used as a standard convolutional backbone in our experiments. This CNN consists of blocks, which are also referred to as shortcut connections. Every residual block has a connection to add the input directly to the output. To put it differently, rather than forcing the model to pass information through every single layer, these shortcuts allow it to carry important details forward more directly. In that way, ResNet solved one of the main problems in deep networks, known as the degradation problem: important information can get lost as it moves through many layers, making it hard for the model to learn, thus leading to a rapid performance degradation. Thanks to the residual connections, deeper networks can be trained reliably. Because of this, ResNet assures solid accuracy over a wide range of tasks, making it a trusted benchmark.

Figure 30 The ResNet-50 architecture

EfficientNet

EfficientNet [MTan19] is a lightweight CNN architecture that does not require powerful hardware, making it practical for real-time use. The network was found using NAS and is part of a family where depth, width and input resolution are scaled together in a balanced way (compound scaling). Its architecture consists of repeated Mobile Inverted Bottleneck blocks, which are small building blocks that use depthwise separable convolutions and squeeze-and-excitation, leading to a network that achieves a balance between computational efficiency and accuracy.

Figure 31 Architecture of EfficientNet-B0

ViT

ViT [Dosovitskiy21] is a transformer designed for CV tasks. ViT employs the self-attention mechanism to model global relationships across image patches. Every image is treated as a sequence of small patches instead of pixels. Each 16x16 patch is converted into a vector, and these vectors are processed together with self-attention layers, which allow the model to relate information from distant regions in the image. A special “class” token is added to the sequence and acts as a summary representation of the whole image. Positional embeddings are also added so that the model knows where each patch is located in the original image. A final classification layer uses the resulting global representation to predict one probability for each category.

Figure 32 The ViT architecture

EfficientFormer

EfficientFormer [Li22A] represents a hybrid architecture that effectively balances speed and accuracy by combining convolutional and transformer-like computations. It is specifically optimized for both speed and memory efficiency. In terms of architecture, this model relies on early convolutional layers to extract local visual features and gradually reduce the image resolution. Later on, it introduces lightweight transformer-inspired blocks that mix information across different regions of the image. Thanks to the design, EfficientFormer can capture both local details and broader context while keeping the computational cost low.

Figure 33 Overview of EfficientFormer

2.4.2.2 Object detection methods for hazardous material signs

The research strategy for the object detection tasks, such as hazardous signs detection and Incidents1M-Seg, adopts almost the same strategy that is used for EO object detection experiments, as described in Section 2.3.2.2. For the first object detection task, hazardous label detection implements a scalable modeling strategy, maintaining a common data partitioning scheme to ensure methodological comparability. In the initial stage of the methodology, the YOLO family models are applied. These architectures are specialized for applications in environments with limited computational resources, optimized for speed and low latency to achieve real time detection. In our subsequent experimental approach, hybrid models are extended, with the main model being RT-DETR. As a final step, optimal performance was targeted through the use of fully Transformer based architectures, including RF-DETR and DEIMv2, which are supported by powerful foundation backbones.

2.4.2.3 Segmentation methods

The selection of methods for UGV scene analysis experiments was guided by the need to establish a representative set of baselines for the tasks defined in this work. The objective was to include architectures that are representative of their respective design paradigms, and sufficiently diverse to enable meaningful comparison across tasks. To this end, the selection comprises: (i) classical two-stage instance segmentation, (ii) transformer-based segmentation architectures, (iii) FM segmentation systems, and (iv) vision-language detectors capable of text-conditioned inference. This set provides a structured and representative sample of modern techniques.

Mask2Former

Mask2Former [Cheng22] is a transformer segmentation framework built around a masked-attention mechanism that restricts attention to predicted mask regions. Because of this design, the model can use the encoder's global context while reasoning locally about object boundaries. Each mask is represented by a learned embedding, and the model iteratively refines these embeddings to produce coherent masks. The architecture is particularly well suited to scenes with overlapping objects, variable scales and irregular shapes, that are common in UGV incident imagery. Mask2Former was selected because its mask-based formulation and transformer backbone provide a modern, high-capacity segmentation framework against which other approaches can be meaningfully compared.

Figure 34 Mask2Former architectural overview

SAM2

SAM2 [Ravi24] is a FM segmentation architecture designed around a high-capacity image encoder and a lightweight, prompt-conditioned mask decoder. The encoder produces dense high-resolution visual embeddings using a large transformer backbone, trained on extensive segmentation pretext tasks. The decoder then generates masks by attending selectively to those embeddings based on user prompts such as points or bounding boxes. Due to the fact that segmentation is performed in this prompt-driven manner rather than through class-specific supervision, SAM2 can produce detailed and consistent masks even when annotations are incomplete. The method was therefore selected for its ability to provide reliable structural masks independently of current taxonomy, offering a stable architectural reference during the dataset’s development.

Figure 35 The SAM2 architecture

Cascade Mask R-CNN

Cascade Mask R-CNN [Cai19] is a two-stage object detection and instance segmentation architecture that extends Mask R-CNN [He17] by introducing a sequence of detection heads trained at progressively higher IoU thresholds. Each step improves the bounding boxes generated by the step before it, leading to more accurate localization and consequently, better mask predictions. Due to this iterative refinement, its architecture is designed to progressively correct errors that occur when objects are hard to detect, making it suitable for objects with irregular shapes, broken edges or partially occluded objects, all common in post-disaster imagery. The model was chosen because it is a well-established and extensively used two-stage segmentation framework that serves as a benchmark for contrasting traditional region-based techniques with more recent transformer-based and FM approaches.

Figure 36 The architectures of different frameworks, where “I” is the input image, “conv” is the backbone convolutions, “pool” is the region-wise feature extraction, “H” is the network head, “B” is the bounding box, and “C” is the classification. “B0” is a proposal in all architectures

Grounded SAM2

Grounded SAM2 [Ren24A] adopts a modular design that combines an open-vocabulary detector, in our case Grounding DINO [Liu24A], with a high-quality prompt-based segmentation model, SAM2 as described earlier, improving upon the original Grounded SAM framework. The detection component identifies regions of interest using text or category embeddings, enabling open-set localization that is not restricted to a closed label set. These detected regions are then passed to the SAM2 segmentation module, which produces masks conditioned on the proposed boxes of the detection component. This two-part design allows the system to segment objects defined through natural language descriptions, making it well suited for evaluating categories that are still being defined or adjusted during dataset development. Grounded SAM2 was included as it represents a leading approach to text-driven detection and segmentation and offers insights into how open-vocabulary methods respond in complex ground-level disaster imagery.

Figure 37 The modular design of Grounded SAM and by extension Grounded SAM2

YOLOE

YOLOE [Wang25D] is based on the same architecture as modern YOLO models (backbone/neck/task head), but it extends its functionality with an additional open-vocabulary head (text projection head). Specifically, it includes a CLIP style text and image alignment mechanism that enables it to recognize

objects from text prompts. Even when it uses only the closed head in non-open-vocabulary tasks, this YOLO family model has been trained with more data, with open-vocabulary alignment, and with additional loss objectives. These enhance the overall quality of the feature maps. Finally, because it is trained to connect images with text, this makes the backbone capable of a much more general understanding of images and consequently provides more mature pretraining checkpoints for fine-tuning.

Figure 38 The overview of YOLOE architecture

YOLOv11 Segmentation

YOLOv11-seg extends the YOLOv11 detection framework with a lightweight segmentation head, enabling joint object detection and instance mask prediction within a single, efficient architecture. It follows the standard YOLO paradigm of a convolutional backbone, multi-scale feature aggregation, and task-specific heads, producing masks through a prototype-based formulation. YOLOv11-seg was selected for the Incidents1M-Seg experiments as a strong one-stage baseline for joint detection and segmentation, allowing assessment of how tightly coupled localisation and mask prediction perform under the cluttered scenes, scale variation, and high intra-class variability characteristic of ground-level post-disaster imagery.

2.4.3 Experimental evaluation

This subsection defines the baseline experiments that represent the point of comparison against which the incident-classification models must be evaluated. Our goal is to establish reproducible, well-defined baselines using standard pretrained architectures trained on a controlled subset of the dataset. For each experiment, models were trained and evaluated under identical hardware, software, and preprocessing conditions to ensure fair comparison.

2.4.3.1 Evaluation metrics

We report the same evaluation metrics as in Section 2.3.3.1 and, in addition, introduce these metrics for the multilabel classification setting.

Let K be the number of classes, and for each class k :

$$TP_k = \text{true positives}, FP_k = \text{false positives}, FN_k = \text{false negatives}$$

- Macro precision measures how many of the predicted positive labels are actually correct, averaged equally over all classes.

$$\text{Macro Precision} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FP_k}$$

- Macro recall measures how many of the true positive labels the model successfully finds, averaged equally over all classes.

$$\text{Macro Recall} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FN_k}$$

- Macro F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall for each class, averaged equally over all classes.

$$\text{Macro F1} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{2 \cdot \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FP_k} \cdot \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FN_k}}{\frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FP_k} + \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FN_k}}$$

2.4.3.2 Results for the multi-label classification tasks

Results for the Incidents1M dataset

The subsection that follows explains the experimental setup and results for the multi-label classification task. We conduct a multi-label image classification experiment on a filtered subset of the Incidents1M [Weber22] dataset, focusing only on images depicting disaster scenarios relevant to the project’s use cases. To align with the TRIFFID corpus, we manually map the original Incidents1M labels into a smaller, semantically coherent set of high-level disaster categories (e.g., grouping all vehicle-accident labels into “destroyed vehicle”). The final label space consists of 15 target classes (water, hole, debris, smoke, flame, mud, landslide, collapsed, earthquake, destroyed building, destroyed vehicle, barrier, drought, burned) and is used only for this classification experiment. This was required to align the task with our corpus, as mentioned in Table 2. In particular, **after examining samples corresponding to each class of the Incidents1M, we ended up merging** the different classes as can be seen in Table 8.

We ran our experiments using an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 Ti GPU. All considered models were initialized using ImageNet-pretrained weights [Deng09]. Their final classification layers were replaced with custom multi-label heads matching the dimensionality of our reduced label space. Each model was finetuned end-to-end using Binary Cross-Entropy with Logits⁴ for multi-label prediction, and optimized the networks with the Adam optimizer [Kingma15] using a low learning rate to preserve generalizable features. Random flips, rotations, and light data augmentation techniques were also implemented to improve robustness across diverse disaster scenes.

⁴ <https://docs.pytorch.org/docs/stable/generated/torch.nn.BCEWithLogitsLoss.html>

Table 8 Clustered Incidents1M classes to align with TRIFFID’s semantic corpus

Adopted Incidents1M classes	Classes for multi-label classification
Flooded, tropical cyclone, heavy rainfall, storm surge	Water
Wildfire, on fire, fire whirl	Flame
Blocked, rockslide, rockfall	Barrier
Van accident, car accident, train accident, ship accident, airplane accident, bus accident, bicycle accident, motorcycle accident, truck accident	Destroyed vehicle
Sinkhole	Hole
With smoke	Smoke
Mudslide mudflow	Mud
Under construction	Destroyed building
Dirty contaminated	Debris
Volcanic eruption, nuclear explosion	Flame, smoke
Earthquake	Earthquake
Landslide	Landslide
Collapsed	Collapsed
Drought	Drought
Burned	Burned

The dataset was randomly divided into 70% training, 15% validation, and 15% test sets. All the experiments had the same setting: images resized to 224×224 pixels with a batch size of 64, Adam optimizer [Kingma15] and a learning rate of $1e-4$, and BCEWithLogitsLoss for multi-label classification. During inference, the pre-processing pipeline and batch size were set similarly to those during training. As mentioned in Section 2.4.2.1, the selected models for evaluating on the Incidents1M dataset are: ResNet-50 [Zhang16], EfficientNet-B0 [Dosovitskiy21], ViT-B/16 [MTan22], EfficientFormer-L1 [Li22A].

Table 9 Performance comparison of the implemented methods Incidents1M

Model	mAP	Precision	Recall	F1-score
ResNet-50	91.78%	88.64%	85.28%	86.86%
ViT-B/16	91.98%	90.51%	84.95%	87.44%
EfficientNet-B0	92.53%	90.64%	86.67%	88.54%
EfficientFormer-L1	92.69%	91.63%	87.36%	89.41%

We report the following key metrics: mAP, precision, recall, and F1-score. The results of the classification experiments are summarized in Table 9. As we can see, performance across all models is consistently high. EfficientFormer-L1 has the best overall performance, achieving the highest mAP of 92.69% and F1-score of 89.41%.

2.4.3.3 Results for hazardous sign detection

The experiments on the HAZMAT benchmark were executed on a single NVIDIA A100 GPU. The dataset was split into 80% for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing. Each YOLO model was trained for 100 epochs using a 416×416 input resolution, batch size of 16, and a learning rate of 1×10^{-2} . Similarly, the transformer-based detectors followed method-specific schedules: RF-DETR was trained for only 18 epochs at 560×560 pixels with a batch size of 8 and early stopping, while RT-DETR’s training lasted 60 epochs with early stopping. Finally, DEIMv2 was trained for 50 epochs with a batch size of 8 and a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} .

Table 10 Detection performance for evaluated models on HAZMAT

Model	mAP50	mAP[50-95]
YOLO-V5 Small	99.10%	78.37%
YOLO-V5 Large	99.10%	83.50%
YOLO11 Large	99.00%	86.30%
RF-DETR Large	98.00%	79.00%
RT-DETR Large	98.60%	80.60%
DEIMV2 Medium	98.46%	79.20%

The results shown in Table 10 indicate that the evaluated methods achieve mAP50 scores above 98%, confirming that ADR label patterns in this dataset are easily captured by modern object detection models. The YOLO family consistently achieves slightly higher performance compared to transformer approaches (RF-DETR, DEIMv2) and hybrid designs (RT-DETR). The hybrid RT-DETR architecture occupies a middle position, reflecting the influence of the ResNet50 backbone, which exploits the extraction of local features from the CNN. This behavior is reasonable, as CNNs are more effective at capturing local features. For transformers, the lower mAP[50-95] measurement compared to YOLO variants is evident, indicating challenges in detailed localization. At the same time, the above evaluation results highlight the advantage of the YOLO11 architecture over YOLOv5, emphasizing the enhancement achieved in the latest generation of YOLO detectors.

Figure 39 Per-class detection performance on the HAZMAT dataset

Similarly, the per-class results confirm that the HAZMAT dataset is not challenging for modern detectors. As shown in Figure 39, almost every ADR category achieves near-perfect AP scores. It is worth noting that the YOLOv5 and YOLO11 large variants demonstrate highly robust performance across all classes. At the same time, certain categories, such as Spontaneously Combustible, Flammable Solid, and Dangerous, exhibit a slight drop in performance. Nevertheless, all models maintain AP values above 93.13% across every class. These results also reveal the specific categories in which transformer-based models encounter greater difficulty, further highlighting the relative advantage of CNN based YOLO architectures.

2.4.3.4 Experimental evaluation of open-vocabulary segmentation methods

For this study, we evaluated a representative set of open-vocabulary segmentation (OVS) methods: MaskCLIP [Dong23], HIPIE [Wang23D], FC-CLIP [Yu23] and OSIDE [Xu23], to cover the main design approaches in current OVS. All methods exhibit generally low performance across all metrics, indicating consistent difficulty in assigning these categories correctly under open-vocabulary settings. While some models produce reasonable mask quality, overall recognition accuracy and PQ remains

limited. These findings suggest that current **OVS approaches do not yet provide the robustness necessary for ground-level post-disaster scene analysis.**

2.4.3.5 Results for Incidents1M-Seg dataset

The segmentation and detection experiments on the Incidents1M-Seg were conducted on an early-stage sample of the dataset, corresponding to approximately 15% of the final expected size, consisting of around 3 thousand annotated images. At this stage, the dataset is undergoing refinement in terms of class definitions, annotation guidelines and overall structure. The purpose of these preliminary experiments is therefore not to establish definitive performance benchmarks, but rather to obtain an early understanding of model behaviour on the developing corpus and identify weaknesses in current annotations and taxonomy.

Despite the limited amount of labelled data, these early evaluations provide useful insight into how existing architectures generalise to post-disaster ground-level scenes and highlight areas where annotation consistency, class granularity or dataset balancing may need further adjustment. All models were trained and evaluated using the unified experimental setup described earlier to ensure compatibility across methods.

Object detection

In the Incidents1M-Seg experiment for the object detection task, the split applied was 80% train set and 20% test split, utilizing transfer learning, that is, training from pretrained checkpoints of each selected model. An exception is YOLOE, where zero shot inference with text prompts was conducted, and fine tuning was applied only to the detection head. For the models available from the Ultralytics framework (YOLOv8, YOLO11, RT-DETR), specific values were set for the hyperparameters: epochs 100, batch size 8, and learning rate 1×10^{-3} . For YOLOE, a different hyperparameter design was used for the two fine tuning experiments. When training only the detection head, epoch 80 and learning rate 1×10^{-3} . When training only the detection head, epoch 80 and learning rate 1×10^{-2} were adopted, while in fine tuning the entire network, the epochs were changed to 60 and the learning rate was 1×10^{-3} . For DEIMv2 and RF-DETR, as two stage architecture models with transformer backbones, epoch 60, a batch size of 8, and learning rates of 5×10^{-4} and 1×10^{-3} , respectively, were applied.

Table 11 Performance comparison of the object detection methods on Incidents1M-Seg

Model	Parameters (M)	Backbone	mAP50	mAP[50-95]
YOLO-v11	25.3	CSP-based (Conv + C3k2 + SPPF + C2PSA)	26.20%	17.30%
RT-DETR	42.0	Resnet50	27.80%	19.20%
RF-DETR	29.0	DINOv2-small with Windowed Attention	31.80%	22.70%
DEIMv2	32.0	ViT-Small (DINOv3)	38.40%	27.00%
YOLO-v8	55.0	CSPDarknet53	25.20%	17.60%
YOLOE-v11 (zero-shot)	26.0	CSP-based	22.30%	15.70%
YOLOE-v11 (FT head)	26.0	CSP-based	32.40%	20.20%
YOLOE-v11 (FT)	26.0	CSP-based	37.60%	27.20%

Focusing on mAP50, it is observed that YOLO based methods, with the exception of YOLOE have the lowest values. This can be attributed to the strong inductive bias of purely CNN-based architectures,

which are optimised for efficiency and real-time inference but may struggle to capture the high-level semantic variability and long-range context present in complex disaster scenarios. Of particular importance are the results of zero-shot performance of YOLOE using text prompts, where the performance matches the trained YOLOv8, demonstrating the strong generalisation capabilities of vision-language representations without task-specific fine-tuning. Fine-tuning YOLOE, substantial gains in accuracy are exhibited, with the fully fine-tuned variant approaching the performance of Transformer-based detectors, indicating that multimodal pretraining provides a strong foundation that can be effectively adapted to domain-specific object detection tasks.

Figure 40 Bar diagram of per-class mAP50 detection performance on Incidents1M-Seg

Impressive is the difference between YOLOE and YOLOv11, which, despite using almost the same architecture, shows that the backbone of the former produces feature maps with more knowledge, as the open vocabulary training of YOLOE forces the backbone to learn more semantically clean features. Also, YOLOE, even in closed set tasks where it uses only the closed set head, has been trained with more data and additional loss objectives, something that enhances its performance when used in transfer learning tasks.

On the other hand, the transformer architectures (DEIMv2, RT-DETR, RF-DETR) demonstrate their own dynamics. At mAP50, they achieve high results, something expected due to the global attention mechanism that allows them to model the overall structure of the image better. Transformers seem to have the tendency to excel in scenes with many overlapping objects, such as Incidents1M-Seg. RT-DETR appears to have the lowest performance among all the other transformer models, which is logical since the other two have stronger transformer backbones that provide the rest of the DETR architecture with better feature maps. DEIMv2 performs best, as expected, due to its DETR-based architecture and the modern DINOv3 backbone.

The observed low performances of each model must be evaluated in relation to the current state of the Incidents1M-Seg dataset. The dataset is still under development, which limits the ability of the models to generalize. A primary constraint is the relatively small size of the dataset so far (based on the number of images), which, combined with the 63 different categories, inevitably leads to an imbalance in the number of samples per category. This long-tailed distribution of classes results to low mAP for the categories with fewer instances. Consequently, the performances do not fully reflect the capabilities of the architectures, but rather the limitations imposed by incomplete and unevenly distributed, due to the lack of data at this stage, training information.

From the analysis of the results and the number of instances per class in the train/test set, it emerges that classes with a large number of instances in the training set and clear characteristics, such as water, green tree, citizen and buildings, generally demonstrate better detection performance. In contrast,

classes with few samples or with small, detailed objects, such as specialized safety equipment, rare vehicles, or essential items, exhibit significantly lower performance. Moreover, certain classes with distinct shapes or prominent features can achieve relatively good performance despite the limited number of samples, while others with complex or less visible characteristics, remain difficult to detect.

Instance segmentation and joint methods

This section focuses on the methods evaluated for instance segmentation and joint detection-segmentation, encompassing architectures that either prioritize mask prediction directly or integrate bounding box and mask estimation into a unified framework. This architectural variety not only provides insight into architectural behaviour, but more importantly, into the limitations of the current sample of the Incidents1M-Seg dataset, providing insights into our next steps in refining and improving the dataset creation protocol.

The same split was used as in the object detection experiments. For YOLO-E we first trained for 80 epochs, by freezing the backbone, and then trained only the detection head following the same experimental setup. Mask2Former, Cascade Mask R-CNN, and YOLOv11L-seg were all trained from pretrained checkpoints for 100 epochs. In contrast, due to its large size and stronger capabilities, SAM achieved strong performance with only 20 epochs. For Grounded SAM2, the detector, Grounding DINO, was trained for 60 epochs while keeping the backbone and language model frozen. During inference, detections were filtered using a confidence threshold of 0.5 and a maximum of 300 predictions per image, followed by NMS (Non-Maximum Suppression). The resulting proposals were then passed to SAM2 to generate the final segmentation masks.

Table 12 Performance comparison of the implemented solutions on Incidents1M-Seg. With “*” are denoted all methods that do both object detection and segmentation tasks

Model	Detection		Segmentation		
	mAP50	mAP[50-95]	mAP50	mAP[50-95]	mIoU
YOLOv11L-seg*	28.04%	19.14%	27.25%	15.89%	18.59
Mask2Former	-	-	22.40%	13.20%	17.06
SAM2	-	-	29.54%	12.44%	31.58
Cascade Mask R-CNN*	25.40%	14.80%	25.30%	15.00%	16.07
Grounded SAM2*	21.75%	12.27%	20.36%	13.34%	59.55
YOLOE-v11 (FT head)*	15.40%	11.20%	14.60%	8.05%	11.93
YOLOE-v11 (FT)*	18.30%	14.00%	17.70%	10.60%	16.30

Figure 41 Bar diagram of per-class mIoU performance on Incidents1M-Seg across transformer models

Figure 42 Bar diagram of per-class mAP50 segmentation performance on Incidents 1M-Seg

Table 12 summarises the detection and segmentation performance of the evaluated models on the current Incidents1M-Seg sample. Overall, the results indicate that both tasks remain challenging, with consistently low mAP[50-95] values across all architectures. This trend suggests that, while models are often able to localize objects or regions coarsely, precise boundary delineation and robust instance separation remain difficult.

Among the detection-capable models, YOLOv11L-seg achieves the highest detection mAP50 (28.04), followed by Cascade Mask R-CNN (25.40). However, the corresponding mAP@50-95 values remain below 20, indicating sensitivity to object scale variation, occlusion, and irregular shapes. Vision-language-based YOLOE variants exhibit lower detection performance overall, suggesting that text-aligned representations do not yet translate effectively to precise localisation in this domain, due to the naturally high intra-class variance of post-disaster settings.

For segmentation quality, clear differences emerge between architectures. Models that tightly couple mask prediction with detection and classification, such as Mask2Former and Cascade Mask R-CNN, achieve relatively low mIoU values (around 16-17), indicating difficulty in recovering consistent pixel-level structure. These architectures rely on clear semantic separation and consistent instance definitions, which appear to be limited in the current dataset sample. In contrast, SAM2-based approaches exhibit substantially stronger mask quality, with SAM2 achieving the highest mIoU among standalone segmenters (31.58), while Grounded SAM2 attains an even higher mIoU of 59.55, which can be attributed to its modular design, where detection and mask generation are decoupled, allowing accurate boundary refinement once a coarse region proposal is available.

Detection-oriented architectures provide complementary insight as YOLOv11L-seg achieves the highest detection performance (28.04 mAP50 and 19.14 mAP[50-95]) among the joint models, indicating that object localisation is feasible when using strong one-stage detectors with dense feature representations. However, its segmentation quality remains comparatively lower (mIoU = 18.59), reflecting the limitations of jointly optimising detection, classification, and mask prediction under complex scene conditions. YOLOE follows a similar trend: fine-tuning improves detection performance, but segmentation accuracy remains limited, suggesting that vision-language alignment does not yet translate into precise spatial reasoning for this dataset.

Collectively, these architectural responses serve as early indicators of where the dataset needs refinement. The observed gaps, ranging from class imbalance, that may be solved naturally by the expansion of the dataset, and inconsistent object visibility to insufficient variation in environmental conditions, provide actionable guidance for expanding the dataset toward its final form. As additional

data is collected, these diagnostic signals will help shape a more complete, diverse, and domain-representative dataset suitable for reliable post-disaster scene understanding.

Figure 43 Bar diagram of per-class mAP50 segmentation performance on Incidents 1M-Seg

3 Non-visual data analysis and information fusion

3.1 Relevant public datasets

To benchmark TRIFFID’s pipeline in a reproducible and comparable way, we evaluate key subsystems (stream ingestion, frame synchronisation, pose estimation, dense reconstruction, semantic labelling, and incremental 3DGS updates) on a curated set of public datasets that provide ground-truth trajectories, calibration, geometry, and/or dense semantic labels.

Pose estimation and sensor synchronisation are validated on visual(-inertial) benchmarks such as the “TUM RGB-D dataset” [Sturm12], which provides time-aligned imagery and ground-truth trajectories. For large-scale outdoor motion and calibration stress tests, the “KITTI Vision Benchmark Suite” [Geiger12A] is used as an established reference benchmark for odometry and visual SLAM evaluation.

Reconstruction quality is evaluated on multi-view benchmarks that provide high-quality reference geometry and established protocols, notably “Tanks and Temples” [Knapitsch17] (realistic indoor/outdoor trajectories with laser-scan reference) and “ETH3D” [Schops17] (high-resolution multi-view and video data with accuracy/completeness evaluation). For RGB-D reconstruction and 3D semantics, “ScanNet” [Dai17A] provides RGB-D sequences with camera poses, surface reconstructions, and semantic annotations suitable for end-to-end validation of depth-aware pipelines.

Semantic models used for foreground/background separation and object-centric processing are validated on UAV/aerial datasets. “UAVid” [Lyu18] provides 4K oblique-view UAV sequences with dense semantic labels and moving-object classes, while “VisDrone” [Zhu18] provides large-scale annotated imagery/video for drone-based detection and tracking. For aerial orthophoto/Digital Surface Model (DSM) semantic labelling (useful for pretraining and cross-validating mapping semantics), the “ISPRS 2D Semantic Labeling benchmarks (Vaihingen/Potsdam)” [ISPRS14] provide high-resolution data with pixel-level ground truth. For 3D point-cloud semantics over urban scenes derived from UAV photogrammetry, “SensatUrban” [Hu21A] provides per-point semantic labels over city-scale reconstructions. Where additional coverage of long-tail urban classes and diverse geographies is required, “Cityscapes” [Cordts16] and “Mapillary Vistas” [Neuhold17] can be used for pretraining or domain-bridging evaluation of segmentation backbones.

Table 13 Relevant datasets for pose estimation, reconstruction accuracy, and semantic understanding in indoor, outdoor, and aerial scenarios

Dataset	Modality / sensors	Ground truth	Used in TRIFFID for
TUM RGB-D	RGB-D	Ground-truth trajectory	Pose accuracy (ATE/RPE), RGB-D alignment, reconstruction sanity checks
KITTI	Stereo/RGB (+ LiDAR in variants)	Odometry ground truth / calibration	Large-scale outdoor trajectories; robustness regression testing
Tanks and Temples	Multi-view images/video	Laser-scan reference	Surface accuracy + completeness (F-score-style evaluation)
ETH3D	High-resolution multi-view + video	Laser-scan reference	Accuracy/completeness; regression testing of multi-view reconstruction
ScanNet	RGB-D video	Camera poses + surfaces + semantics	End-to-end RGB-D + semantic mapping validation
UAVid	UAV video (4K oblique)	Pixel-wise semantic labels	UAV semantic segmentation; moving-object masking
VisDrone	Drone images/video	Bounding boxes + labels	Object detection/tracking components; UAV domain coverage
ISPRS Vaihingen/Potsdam	Orthophoto + DSM	Pixel-wise semantic labels	Aerial semantics pretraining; DSM-informed class separation
SensatUrban	UAV photogrammetry point clouds	Per-point semantic labels	3D semantic labelling and evaluation at urban scale

3.2 3D semantic map

The reconstruction subsystem developed for the TRIFFID project transforms live UAV video into a semantically annotated 3D representation using a combined SfM/MVS [Schonberger16] and 3DGS [Kerbl23] pipeline. Incoming RGB or RGB-D streams are captured over RTMP and undergo low-latency decoding, pre-processing, semantic segmentation, and precise temporal synchronization with (Inertial Measurement Unit) IMU, Global Positioning System (GPS), and telemetry data. These aligned inputs feed a reconstruction backend that extracts camera poses, generates dense geometry, and trains a compact 3DGS model enriched with semantic labels. The system operates on continuous video segments, enabling incremental updates to the scene and providing a consistent, high-quality representation suitable for multi-UAV and real-time applications.

3.2.1 Review of state-of-the-art methods

This subsection reviews representative families of 3D reconstruction methods relevant to the TRIFFID use case, with an emphasis on real-time processing from UAV streams and AR visualization. We focus on techniques that have influenced the design of the proposed system and that serve as baselines in the model analysis and selection presented later in Section 3.2.2.

Real-time 3D reconstruction

Real-time 3D reconstruction from video streams typically involves estimating camera motion and fusing observations into a coherent geometric representation. Traditional systems such as KinectFusion rely on Iterative Closest Point (ICP) alignment of depth frames and fusion into a volumetric truncated signed distance function (TSDF) [Newcombe11]. While these approaches can deliver accurate reconstructions at high frame rates, they are best suited to limited workspaces and depth sensors, and struggle with large outdoor environments and rapid UAV motion.

Structure-from-Motion (SfM) and multi-view stereo (MVS) methods offer greater flexibility by using multiple images from varying viewpoints to estimate camera poses and dense geometry. Modern SfM/MVS pipelines, as implemented in tools like COLMAP [Schonberger16], perform robust feature detection and matching, global or sequential pose estimation, and bundle adjustment, followed by dense stereo reconstruction [Furukawa10]. Sparse point clouds produced by SfM provide reliable anchor points for later stages, including the initialization of Gaussian splats.

To cope with dynamic scenes, it is common to distinguish between static background and moving foreground. Separate processing paths can be used: a slower, high-quality reconstruction for static structures, and faster, approximate pipelines for objects that move or change appearance rapidly [Runz18]. This division reduces computational load and allows resources to be focused where temporal consistency is most critical (e.g., on objects of interest in the AR view).

Motion tracking of multiple objects can be achieved by combining neural detection, OF, and instance-aware segmentation. This enables not only geometric but also semantic reconstruction, which is important for downstream AR interactions. Simple point clouds can be rendered quickly but often suffer from aliasing, gaps, and flickering. Point-based neural methods [Aliev20] and Gaussian Splatting extend this concept by assigning richer features (shape, scale, color, semantics) to each point or Gaussian and by using sophisticated splatting algorithms for higher visual quality.

RGB-D and structure-from-motion data

Combining RGB-D data with SfM techniques is an effective strategy for robust 3D reconstruction. RGB-D sensors provide per-pixel depth alongside color, which stabilizes geometric reasoning, especially under difficult photometric conditions. Depth can be used to validate or refine SfM-derived 3D points, correct scale ambiguities and improve pose estimation [Chandrashekar21].

In purely RGB-based pipelines, pose and structure estimation are vulnerable to lighting changes, low texture regions, and repetitive patterns. Depth information introduces an extra dimension for consistency checks and outlier rejection. For instance, if a potential matching pair of points is inconsistent in depth, it can be discarded early.

Instance segmentation on RGB channels, using methods such as Mask R-CNN, yields object masks that can be applied to depth maps to produce object-specific point clouds. This reduces data volume and enables per-object modelling. When depth is not available, SfM acts as the primary reconstruction technique, using multiple overlapping frames to recover a sparse 3D point cloud and camera poses. The combination of semantic segmentation, RGB-D data and SfM makes it possible to run dual pipelines: a slow but precise one for the static background and a faster, more approximate one for foreground objects.

Dynamic scenes pose additional challenges. Moving objects can be erroneously integrated into the static map, causing ghosting and inconsistencies. Semantic-driven separation of foreground and background

mitigates this by ensuring that SfM for the static map ignores moving entities [Bescos18]. At the same time, moving objects can be tracked and reconstructed in their own local coordinate systems, facilitating their later integration into the AR experience.

Efficient transmission formats such as HDF5 allow storing both geometric and semantic attributes per point, along with motion metadata, enabling rapid loading on client devices and selective updates. This is particularly important when operating over limited bandwidth between the reconstruction backend and Unity/AR clients [Folk11].

3D Gaussian splatting: principles of operation and mathematical background

3DGS represents a scene as a set of anisotropic Gaussian distributions in 3D space. Each Gaussian is described by a mean position μ and covariance Σ , often factorized as $\Sigma = RSS^T R^T$, where R is a rotation matrix and S is a diagonal scale matrix. During rendering, these 3D Gaussians are projected through the camera model into the image plane, where they appear as 2D Gaussian splats whose size, shape, and orientation depend on the viewing configuration.

Let x denote a 3D point in world coordinates, and $T_c = [R_c | t_c]$ be the SE(3) transform of camera c . The point in camera coordinates is:

$$x_c = R_c(x - t_c)$$

The covariance can be transformed accordingly, and the projection to the image plane is derived using the Jacobian J of the projection function. The projected 2D covariance $\Sigma_{img} = J\Sigma J^T$ defines the anisotropic Gaussian footprint of the splat on the image. Visibility-aware depth sorting and alpha blending are used to composite many overlapping splats into the final colour value of each pixel.

Appearance is modelled using spherical harmonics (SH) coefficients attached to each Gaussian, which encode view-dependent color. An opacity parameter controls the contribution of each Gaussian to the rendered image. Training is performed by minimizing a photometric loss between rendered images and ground-truth frames over multiple viewpoints. Crucially, unlike NeRF-type methods [Mildenhall20], 3DGS operates directly on explicit Gaussian primitives and does not require per-ray volumetric sampling, resulting in significantly faster training and rendering.

The splatting algorithm is implemented as a tile-based GPU rasterizer. For each tile in the target image, the set of Gaussians whose projection intersects the tile is determined (e.g., via spatial hashing). Their contributions are accumulated in depth order using a visibility-aware blending scheme. This approach is highly parallel and well suited to modern GPUs.

The model is dynamic in nature. New Gaussians can be added in regions that exhibit high reconstruction errors or that become visible later in a sequence; existing Gaussians can be modified or removed as the scene evolves. For dynamic scenes, Gaussians can be associated with deformable meshes and animated with skeletal motion, with residual transformations learned per Gaussian to capture non-linear deformations and local lighting effects.

Semantic information (labels, instance IDs, higher-level descriptors) can be added as additional channels per Gaussian and optimized jointly with color. This allows the renderer to output not just RGB images but also semantic or instance maps, enabling rich AR interactions.

Comparison with other reconstruction techniques

3DGS differs from other reconstruction approaches in both representation and computational behavior. Compared to NeRF-like implicit neural representations, which model the scene as a continuous function mapping (position, direction) to color and density, 3DGS uses explicit primitives. NeRF approaches require ray marching along each viewing ray and evaluating a neural network at many samples, resulting in high computational cost for both training and rendering, especially at high resolutions. 3DGS avoids per-ray sampling and instead uses forward splatting of Gaussians, which is more efficient and scales better for interactive applications.

Volumetric voxel-based methods, including TSDF grids and sparse voxel structures, offer straightforward fusion of depth measurements but suffer from high memory requirements when fine resolution is needed over large areas. Even with sparse data structures, the memory and compute cost grows quickly with scene size. Gaussian Splatting operates on sparse sets of primitives whose number grows linearly with scene complexity, providing better scalability.

Simple point-based rendering uses point primitives without shape and with limited support for view-dependent effects. This can introduce aliasing and “holes” in the rendered image, especially when viewpoints change rapidly. Gaussians, by contrast, have continuous spatial support and can be anisotropic, which helps bridge gaps and produce smoother images. Soft blending between overlapping Gaussians alleviates artefacts when zooming or viewing from grazing angles [Zwicker01].

Mesh-based methods reconstruct surfaces as polygonal meshes. They provide excellent sharpness at edges and are suitable for CAD-like objects but are less natural for volumetric or translucent structures such as foliage, smoke, or semi-transparent materials. They also require watertight or near-watertight surfaces for robust rendering, which is difficult to guarantee in real-world UAV data. Gaussian Splatting manages such situations more gracefully by not imposing explicit topological constraints.

Regarding semantics, both implicit and explicit models can embed features per spatial location that can be decoded into labels. However, the explicit nature of Gaussians makes editing straightforward: individual Gaussians can be repositioned, removed, or recolored without global side effects. In implicit networks, even small parameter changes have non-local effects across the scene.

Finally, for dynamic scenes and incremental updates, 3DGS is naturally suited: Gaussians associated with newly observed regions can be added incrementally, and local updates do not require retraining a large global model. This property is particularly important in TRIFFID, where UAVs continuously explore and revisit areas, and where the AR map must evolve over time while maintaining low latency.

3.2.2 Implemented solutions

The dynamic reconstruction pipeline transforms continuous UAV video streams into an incrementally maintained 3DGS representation. Instead of processing the mission as a single monolithic dataset, incoming video is segmented into manageable chunks-typically corresponding to flight segments or time windows. Each chunk triggers its own reconstruction session, which executes frame extraction, camera pose estimation, dense reconstruction, and Gaussian Splatting training.

This chunk-based strategy enables the map to be extended or refined over time without reprocessing previous data. Local changes can be updated efficiently by re-running only the affected sessions. Each session stores detailed metadata-capture time, UAV identity, processing parameters, and quality metrics-allowing operators to audit results, reprocess sessions with different settings, or roll back

undesired updates. Sessions can also be fused to create large, continuously improving 3D maps, even when sourced from multiple UAVs or repeated passes over the same area.

3.2.2.1 Semantic map integration and real-time model distribution

The first subsection describes how live video streams and sensor data are acquired from UAVs, pre-processed, temporally aligned, and converted into inputs suitable for SfM/MVS and Gaussian Splatting. The goal is to deliver geometrically and temporally consistent, semantically enriched data to the reconstruction modules while maintaining low end-to-end latency.

Data collection subsystem and RTMP server integration

The proposed architecture is built around a data collection subsystem that receives live streams from UAVs equipped with RGB-D or multispectral cameras. Each UAV uses hardware-accelerated H.264/H.265 encoding to compress the video and transmit it over a reliable RTMP channel. Offloading compression to onboard hardware reduces Central Processing Unit/Graphics Processing Unit (CPU/GPU) load on the flight controller, leaving resources available for navigation, IMU processing and light-weight on-board pre-processing.

Network design is critical in this context. Control, telemetry and video data are transmitted over separate channels to avoid congestion, especially from heavy I-frames that could delay flight control packets. In multi-UAV scenarios, each drone publishes its own RTMP stream to a common media server, which is typically implemented using Nginx with the RTMP module or a comparable solution capable of sustaining multiple persistent TCP connections. The server is configured for low-latency operation by limiting buffer sizes and carefully tuning retransmission and queuing behavior, aiming at end-to-end video latencies on the order of a few hundred milliseconds. Where required, RTMPS (RTMP over TLS) and access control mechanisms are used to secure the transmission and prevent unauthorized access.

On the server side, incoming RTMP streams are decoded into raw frames using tools such as FFmpeg. The decoded frames can be passed directly to Python-based processing pipelines or to C++ modules via shared memory or Inter-Process Communication mechanisms. At this stage, the system may also perform adaptive bitrate or resolution adjustments based on backend load and network conditions: when the reconstruction pipeline becomes saturated or bandwidth drops, the server can dynamically reduce the outgoing resolution or bitrate to maintain responsiveness.

Frames are fed into a queue structure that separates processing paths for reconstruction, direct AR overlay, and preview. This prevents slow operations (e.g., dense reconstruction) from blocking the flow of frames required for immediate visual feedback. Overall, the RTMP server is not a passive receiver, but a vital component of a broader data integrity and latency management strategy that strongly influences the final visual quality and temporal consistency of the AR experience.

Once a reconstruction session completes, its output—either a newly generated Gaussian model or an incremental update to an existing one—is delivered to Unity clients through WebSocket connections. This push-based mechanism ensures that Unity applications receive the most recent map representations without manual refresh or polling. Clients can choose how to handle updates: replacing their current model, merging the new splats into an existing scene, or selectively loading regions of interest.

This integration allows operators and users in Unity to view a continuously updated 3D environment, where changes captured by UAVs are reflected in near real time. It provides a seamless bridge between the backend reconstruction system and the interactive visualization or simulation layers built in Unity.

Frame extraction and synchronization

Accurate frame extraction and temporal synchronization are crucial to ensuring that the various data streams (video, IMU, GPS, telemetry, segmentation results) are consistent in time. RTMP delivers compressed multimedia streams that must be decomposed into discrete frames suitable for subsequent analysis.

Using FFmpeg or equivalent libraries, the system decodes the incoming stream into raw RGB/BGR buffers. Each frame is assigned to a timestamp, either extracted from the video stream metadata or generated by a high-precision clock on the server. In parallel, IMU readings, GPS fixes, telemetry messages, and segmentation outputs arrive through other channels (often UDP or WebSocket-based). All these data are converted to a common time base established by Network Time Protocol (NTP) or PTP synchronization across all nodes.

The synchronization module maintains queues for each data type and aligns frames with their nearest sensor samples within a configurable time window. If some sensor values are missing within the window, interpolation or extrapolation is applied where possible. For example, IMU measurements may be integrated to bridge small gaps, while GPS positions can be linearly interpolated between fixes.

Frame rate reduction is performed when necessary to match downstream processing capacity or network limitations. This can be done uniformly (e.g., taking every n -th frame) or adaptively, selecting frames that correspond to significant changes in scene content, as indicated by motion magnitude (e.g., OF) or segmentation dynamics. Conversely, for certain tasks, such as animating fast-moving objects or training dynamic Gaussians, all intermediate frames may be preserved to capture fine-grained temporal evolution.

Because video frames often experience higher latency than telemetry data (due to RTMP/TCP buffering), the synchronization system maintains a small temporal buffer for all streams and aligns them based on timestamps rather than arrival order. Multi-threaded implementations are used: one thread oversees decoding, another performs synchronization, and one or more threads feed frames and aligned metadata into the reconstruction and rendering pipelines. This architecture maintains the temporal consistency required for geometrically accurate and visually stable AR overlays.

Camera pose estimation

Camera pose estimation translates the temporally aligned data into a sequence of 6-Degrees of Freedom (DoF) poses that define the position and orientation of each camera frame in a global reference frame. The quality of these poses directly affects the fidelity and stability of both the reconstructed geometry and the final Gaussian representation.

In scenarios where RGB-D data is available and the UAV trajectory is smooth, visual odometry and RGB-D SLAM systems such as RTAB-Map can be used to estimate camera motion by combining depth and visual features [Labbe19]. These systems integrate new frames into a global map incrementally and reduce drift through loop closures and pose-graph optimization.

For monocular RGB data, Structure-from-Motion (SfM) techniques are employed. Feature detectors and descriptors (e.g., SIFT) identify salient points in each frame, which are then matched across views. Robust geometric verification (e.g., RANSAC-based essential/fundamental matrix estimation) filters out mismatches. Tools such as COLMAP provide automated pipelines that perform feature extraction, feature matching, initial pose estimation, and bundle adjustment, resulting in a coherent set of camera poses and a sparse 3D point cloud.

In challenging UAV scenarios with large altitude changes or aggressive maneuvers, additional sensors are helpful. A downward-facing tracking camera can provide more stable visual odometry over textured ground, while a forward-facing RGB camera supplies detailed near-field geometry. For wide field-of-view or panoramic setups, spherical imaging and binocular spherical stereo can be used to recover depth over large solid angles, exploiting parallax between two spherical views. In such setups, depth can be approximated as a function of the vertical parallax, the sensor resolution, and the baseline distance between viewpoints.

Dynamic objects, such as vehicles and people, can introduce inconsistency if used for pose estimation. To mitigate this, semantic segmentation masks from the preprocessing stage are used to filter out points belonging to moving entities, ensuring that pose estimation is based primarily on static background features. IMU and GPS data further stabilize the solution: IMUs provide high-rate angular velocity and acceleration that can be integrated over brief time windows for dead reckoning, while GPS offers global position fixes when available. These signals are fused with visual estimates through Kalman filtering or non-linear optimization, reducing long-term drift [Qin18].

The outcome of this stage is a sequence of SE(3) transformations, one per frame:

$$T_i = [R_i | t_i],$$

where R_i is the 3×3 rotation matrix and t_i is the 3D translation vector of camera i in the global coordinate system. These poses are later used by the Gaussian Splatting renderer to project 3D Gaussians into each camera view without spatial or temporal discontinuities.

Figure 44 The internal operation of a COLMAP-like SfM pipeline

3.2.2.2 Training and deployment of 3D Gaussian splatting model

In the final stage of the reconstruction backend, the synchronized frames, estimated camera poses and any available depth and segmentation information are converted into a 3DGS model. The scene is represented as a set of anisotropic 3D Gaussians, each defined by a mean position μ , a covariance matrix Σ or an equivalent decomposition into a rotation matrix R and scale matrix S ($\Sigma = RSS^T R^T$), and additional appearance and semantic attributes.

Initial Gaussians are typically seeded at the positions of points in the sparse or dense point cloud produced by the SfM/MVS pipeline. For each seed point, an initial Gaussian is created with a small isotropic scale and initial color derived from the underlying image observations. During training, the parameters of each Gaussian (position, scale, orientation, opacity, and spherical harmonic coefficients describing view-dependent color) are optimized using a differentiable rasterizer.

The differentiable renderer projects the Gaussians into each camera view, based on the corresponding T_i , and evaluates a photometric loss between the rendered image and the ground-truth frame (e.g., L2 loss, SSIM or a combination). Gradients are propagated back to the Gaussian parameters via backpropagation. Unlike NeRF-style volumetric methods that perform costly per-ray sampling, the 3DGS renderer uses tile-based rasterization and visibility-aware splatting: for each image tile, only

Gaussians that project into the tile are considered, and their contributions are blended in depth order using alpha compositing. This yields significant training and rendering speedups.

The optimization process is dynamic. A densification stage identifies regions where reconstruction error remains high or where added details appear in later frames, and spawns additional Gaussians in those regions. Conversely, a pruning stage periodically removes Gaussians that contribute little to the final images or remain occluded from all viewpoints. This keeps the model compact while adapting to scene changes.

For dynamic objects, Gaussians may be bound to deformable mesh templates via UV mapping. The meshes are driven by skeleton-based animation or non-rigid deformations, and each Gaussian carries a residual transformation on top of the mesh motion (e.g., residual translation, rotation, and scale). This mechanism allows the system to render animating characters or moving machinery without retraining the entire model for each new sequence.

When semantic labels from preprocessing are available, they are attached as additional feature dimensions to each Gaussian (e.g., class probabilities or instance IDs). During rendering, these semantic features can be projected along with color, enabling the generation of semantic maps, instance masks, or category-based visual effects in real time.

Training proceeds in mini-batches of frames to maximize GPU utilization, typically using mixed-precision arithmetic to reduce memory usage and increase throughput. Learning rate schedules (e.g., cosine decay) are employed to rapidly obtain a rough approximation and then finely adjust details. Constraints on scales and position regularizers are applied to prevent Gaussians from growing overly large or drifting, which would introduce blurring and artefacts.

The optimized model is stored in a compact binary format, usually consisting of contiguous arrays for positions, scales, rotations, opacity, spherical harmonic coefficients, and semantic vectors. Spatial tiling information is also preserved to support efficient culling on the client side. The binary model is then streamed to the Unity/AR client via TCP or loaded through Unity asset bundles.

In live deployments, training is not a one-off batch process: the model is continuously updated as new frames and chunks arrive. Instead of retraining from scratch, the system performs online optimization focused on regions affected by the new data, achieving a continuously updated and spatially consistent 3DGS representation.

Figure 45 The main steps of the 3DGS pipeline from point cloud seeding to training and streaming

3.2.3 Experimental evaluation

The experimental setup for evaluating the reconstruction subsystem is designed to replicate TRIFFID-like operational conditions, with an emphasis on how the pipeline behaves when processing real UAV video streams and sensor data. The primary goal is to characterize the end-to-end performance of the 3DGS-based reconstruction backend rather than provide a comprehensive benchmark. The experiments simulate inspection and situational-awareness scenarios involving one or more UAVs surveying urban areas, industrial infrastructures, or regions affected by disasters. UAVs capture RGB or RGB-D video alongside IMU and GPS telemetry, which is streamed to a ground station via RTMP and decoded in near real time. The prototype backend executes on a commodity workstation equipped with a multi-core CPU, a discrete GPU, and sufficient RAM to handle several concurrent reconstruction sessions. The software pipeline integrates FFmpeg decoding, Python-based preprocessing and semantic segmentation, COLMAP-style structure-from-motion and MVS algorithms, and a high-performance GPU implementation of 3DGS. The reconstruction experiments concentrate on three major categories.

- **Reconstruction quality** is assessed through photometric comparisons such as PSNR and SSIM computed between rendered 3DGS views and the original camera frames, including held-out viewpoints not used during training. Geometric metrics are evaluated when ground-truth or reference geometry is available, measuring point-to-surface distances and identifying local geometric inconsistencies. Qualitative evaluations include detecting reconstruction artefacts, completeness issues, and assessing temporal stability when new chunks are integrated.
- **Performance and latency** measurements include training time per video chunk, GPU memory usage, computational load during densification and pruning, and the responsiveness of the reconstruction stage when processing long sequences or high-motion segments. Latency is broken down from the moment frames are captured onboard the UAV to the moment the 3DGS model is updated on the backend.
- **Robustness tests** examine behavior under rapid UAV maneuvers, motion blur, variable lighting, reduced frame rates, and degraded or intermittent sensor data. Preliminary results show that 3DGS can maintain a good balance between reconstruction detail, training time, and incremental update capability, outperforming classical mesh-based SfM/MVS pipelines in update frequency and outperforming NeRF-like methods in speed and latency. The explicit nature of 3D Gaussians makes it possible to update only affected regions when new chunks arrive, yielding a scalable and efficient reconstruction process aligned with TRIFFID's requirements. These early observations informed the more detailed method comparison and motivated the final choice of 3DGS as the core representation.

3.2.3.1 Evaluation metrics

Evaluation follows three complementary perspectives: (i) visual fidelity of rendered novel views, (ii) geometric accuracy and completeness of reconstructed structure, and (iii) operational performance (latency, throughput, and stability) under streaming constraints.

Visual fidelity metrics are computed on held-out viewpoints not used during optimisation. We report PSNR and the “Structural Similarity Index (SSIM)” [Wang04] for pixel/structure similarity, and we additionally report “LPIPS” [Zhang18] to approximate perceptual similarity using learned deep features. Metrics are computed both per chunk and cumulatively after incremental updates to quantify drift and progressive refinement over time.

Geometric metrics are computed when reference geometry exists (e.g., laser scans or high-quality reconstructions). We adopt accuracy and completeness reporting in the style of established MVS benchmarks such as “ETH3D” [Schops17]. When using Tanks and Temples conventions, we report a distance-threshold F-score that balances precision and recall of reconstructed surfaces relative to a reference scan (“Tanks and Temples” [Knapitsch17]).

Pose accuracy is evaluated using Absolute Trajectory Error (ATE) and Relative Pose Error (RPE), following standard RGB-D/VO benchmarking practice (“TUM RGB-D benchmark methodology” [Sturm12]). These are computed after temporal alignment and, when required, similarity alignment of estimated and ground-truth trajectories.

Semantic quality is evaluated using mIoU for semantic segmentation. When instance-aware outputs are assessed (e.g., tracking and reconstruction of moving objects), Panoptic Quality (PQ) can additionally be reported as a unified metric for “things” and “stuff” segmentation (“Panoptic Segmentation” [Kirillov19B]).

Operational metrics include:

- End-to-end latency (capture → backend ingest → pose estimation → 3DGS update available to client).
- Throughput (frames/s processed and updates/s delivered).
- Update stability, measured via (a) view-consistency of a fixed virtual camera across successive model updates using SSIM/LPIPS, and (b) semantic consistency (label agreement) across updates for static regions.

3.2.3.2 Results for the 3D reconstruction task

Experimental setup

The evaluation setup mirrors the operational TRIFFID architecture by replaying both public datasets and internally captured UAV sequences through the same ingest, synchronisation, and reconstruction stack used in deployment.

To capture realistic networking and buffering behaviour, prerecorded sequences are optionally re-streamed as RTMP using the “NGINX RTMP module” and decoded uniformly via “FFmpeg”. Time alignment between video and sensor streams follows a single time base; when hardware time synchronisation is available, “IEEE 1588 Precision Time Protocol (PTP)” is used to bound timestamp drift across components. Updates are distributed to clients over “WebSocket (RFC 6455)”, enabling measurement of network delivery latency and client update behaviour.

Hardware and software environment:

- Backend: AMD Ryzen 9 9900X3D, NVIDIA RTX 4070 12GB and 64GB RAM.
- Software: Original INDRIA 3DGS implementation in python [Kerbl23], FFMpeg, NGINX, Unity.
- Drone: DJI Mini 4K

Experimental protocol:

- Input partitioning: each sequence is divided into time-window “chunks” to evaluate incremental map updates versus batch reconstruction.

- Baselines: SfM/MVS baseline via a “COLMAP”-style pipeline [Schonberger16], and (where relevant) a fast NeRF baseline such as “Instant-NGP” [Muller22], compared against the primary “3DGS” method [Kerbl23].
- Evaluation split: for each chunk, a subset of frames is held out for quantitative rendering evaluation (PSNR/SSIM/LPIPS), with the remaining frames used for optimisation.
- Repetitions: key sequences are run multiple times to estimate variability due to sampling and GPU nondeterminism, reporting mean and dispersion.

Experimental results

This section reports (i) measured TRIFFID prototype performance (latency/throughput and rendering speed), and (ii) visual fidelity using PSNR, SSIM and LPIPS. For the NeRF-family comparison, we additionally cite published benchmarks that report training time and rendering FPS for 3DGS and representative baselines, demonstrating the runtime advantage of 3DGS for interactive applications [Kerbl23].

Table 14 Published benchmark comparison (source experiments; native test resolutions)

Dataset	Method	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	Train \downarrow	FPS \uparrow	Mem \downarrow
Mip-NeRF360	Instant-NGP (Base)	0.671	25.30	0.371	5m37s	11.7	13MB
Mip-NeRF360	Mip-NeRF360	0.792	27.69	0.237	48h	0.06	8.6MB
Mip-NeRF360	3DGS (Ours-7K)	0.770	25.60	0.279	6m25s	160	523MB
Mip-NeRF360	3DGS (Ours-30K)	0.815	27.21	0.214	41m33s	134	734MB
Tanks & Temples	Instant-NGP (Base)	0.723	21.72	0.330	5m26s	17.1	13MB
Tanks & Temples	Mip-NeRF360	0.759	22.22	0.257	48h	0.14	8.6MB
Tanks & Temples	3DGS (Ours-7K)	0.767	21.20	0.280	6m55s	197	270MB
Tanks & Temples	3DGS (Ours-30K)	0.841	23.14	0.183	26m54s	154	411MB
Deep Blending	Instant-NGP (Base)	0.797	23.62	0.423	6m31s	3.26	13MB
Deep Blending	Mip-NeRF360	0.901	29.40	0.245	48h	0.09	8.6MB
Deep Blending	3DGS (Ours-7K)	0.875	27.78	0.317	4m35s	172	386MB
Deep Blending	3DGS (Ours-30K)	0.903	29.41	0.243	36m2s	137	676MB

Table 15 Derived speedups from published benchmarks (computed from Table 14)

Dataset	3DGS (7K) FPS	Instant-NGP FPS	3DGS/Instant-NGP (×)	Mip-NeRF360 FPS	3DGS/Mip-NeRF360 (×)	Mip-NeRF360 train / 3DGS train (×)
Mip-NeRF360	160	11.7	13.7×	0.06	2667×	449×
Tanks & Temples	197	17.1	11.5×	0.14	1407×	416×
Deep Blending	172	3.26	52.8×	0.09	1911×	628×

These published results indicate that at comparable “fast NeRF” training times (~5-7 minutes), 3DGS reaches substantially higher rendering FPS (order-of-magnitude improvements) while maintaining competitive fidelity; compared to high-fidelity NeRF baselines, rendering speed differs by orders of magnitude (e.g., 1000×+) and training time by hundreds of times on these benchmarks [Kerbl23]. A known trade-off is the model’s memory footprint (hundreds of MB for 3DGS vs. tens of MB for some NeRF encodings), which is addressed in TRIFFID through model management (streaming/tiling/compression) and selecting iteration budgets aligned with operational requirements. [Kerbl23].

Figure 46 Dilapidated building presented with 3DGS

Figure 47 Complex stadium inside forest area presented with 3DGS

3.3 LiDAR-based data processing

In TRIFFID, the legged UGV is the only platform equipped with a 3D LiDAR sensor, and it plays a very specific role in complementing the global situational awareness built from aerial perception. Whereas the UAV provides large-scale visual coverage and is responsible for producing the main 3D semantic reconstruction from RGB imagery, the UGV contributes the close-range geometric accuracy needed for reliable operation on the ground. The two systems are meant to work together: the aerial stream offers breadth and semantic context, while the terrestrial LiDAR provides the dense, metrically precise geometry required for safe navigation and fine-grained scene understanding near obstacles, debris or structures. LiDAR is particularly important in the environments considered by TRIFFID, where visibility can be compromised by smoke, water drops, dust, collapsed material or low illumination. While the UAV's global map provides the overarching semantic picture of the disaster site, its accuracy inevitably degrades at ground level due to occlusions and viewpoint limitations. The UGV therefore enriches and corrects these regions by continuously gathering high-resolution point clouds as it moves. These measurements form the local spatial representation used for UGV navigation and also serve as geometric adjustments to the aerial map, improving alignment, consistency and local detail.

Within WP4, these LiDAR data streams will support the UGV's SLAM subsystem and feed into the broader multimodal mapping pipeline. The UGV's mapping component will not attempt to produce a standalone global map; instead, it focuses on producing accurate local 3D estimates that can be anchored to the UAV-derived 3D semantic map. This anchoring is essential, because it allows all ground observations (e.g., geometry, robot localization, and local traversability cues) to be integrated into the unified 3D semantic map that is used by the ground station and by higher-level planning modules. The adjustments made from LiDAR are therefore not meant to override the UAV map, but to refine it, ensuring coherence between global structure and the fine detail required for nearby navigation.

The LiDAR stream also enables the UGV's traversability reasoning. Close-range 3D geometry around the robot must be accurately and timely estimated, since the UGV must identify uneven terrain, unstable debris or narrow passages that would not be visible to the UAV. These traversability models are calculated from the robot-centric LiDAR scans and are used by the navigation stack to decide where the UGV can safely move. In many cases, UAV imagery cannot sufficiently capture the subtle topographic structures that influence foothold safety for a legged vehicle, making LiDAR indispensable in this context.

The LiDAR subsystem interacts with several other components across the project. Its outputs feed the UGV's SLAM and localization module, which in turn influence motion planning (WP3-T3.1) and real-time navigation (WP3-T3.2). The mapping information is essential not only to autonomy but also to the operator experience. The ground station receives an always-updated, 3D map that integrates aerial semantics with UGV-level specifics. This ensures that what the operator sees is not just a global reconstruction, but one that reflects the true navigable space at the resolution required for ground operations. Finally, the datasets generated from these scans form the core of TRIFFID's internal multimodal dataset (DS7). They enable training, benchmarking, and validation of SLAM, traversability, and fusion algorithms, ensuring that the system is robust across wildfire, flood, and earthquake conditions.

The remainder of this section elaborates on these elements in more detail. It begins with the curation of the available SOTA LiDAR and localization datasets. It then presents the LiDAR-based SLAM pipeline developed for the UGV. This is followed by the description of the traversability analysis used to assess ground safety and locomotion viability. Finally, the document discusses how LiDAR geometry can be merged with the UAV-derived 3D semantic map, forming the unified representation that supports planning, monitoring and operator interaction.

3.3.1 Relevant public LiDAR datasets

In this section, we review a set of publicly available datasets relevant to robotic mapping, perception, and SLAM using LiDAR. We evaluate each dataset in terms of sensing modalities, environment type, availability of transformation frames (TF), semantic labels, refresh rates, and suitability for different components of our SLAM system. Based on this analysis, we identify the best datasets that might be relevant to TRIFFID and justify the exclusion of others.

In particular, the datasets surveyed are: **Disaster City** [Pellenz10]; **KITTI** [Geiger13]; **TRADR** [Kruijff-Korbayová15]; **RUGD** [Wigness19]; **UMA SAR** [Morales21]; **Goose** [Mortimer24]; **WildScenes** [Vidanapathirana25]; **SegmentedForests** [Laino25]; **GrandTour** [Frey25]; **DigiForests** [Malladi25].

The **Disaster City** dataset [Pellenz10] contains LiDAR scans, RGB, IMU and GPS recordings acquired in a structured disaster-response training environment. Despite being semantically interesting, the dataset uses outdated sensor formats, lacks meaningful TF information and suffers from frequent GPS jumps. The low LiDAR refresh rate and missing transforms make it impractical for SLAM benchmarking without extensive preprocessing.

The **KITTI** dataset [Geiger13] remains one of the most widely used benchmarks in autonomous driving, including LiDAR, stereo, IMU/ Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) and accurate ground truth. However, its semantics are designed for traffic scenarios (e.g., with vehicles, pedestrians, or cyclists) which are not representative of disaster-response or off-road UGV missions. Moreover, the car-mounted sensor configuration differs substantially from that of ground robots. For these reasons, KITTI's semantic content is not aligned with the objectives of this work.

TRADR [Kruijff-Korbayová15] offers ROS-native multimodal data from real robot deployments in industrial plants, forests and disaster areas. While TF information is present, sensor availability varies significantly between data recordings: some include full 3D LiDAR, others only 2D laser scans. In addition, many sequences are short, reducing their value for continuous SLAM evaluation.

The **RUGD** dataset [Wigness19] focuses on unstructured natural terrain such as vegetation, rocks, water, mud, and trails, and includes high-resolution RGB images with pixel-level semantic labels.

Despite its strong semantic diversity, the dataset contains only camera-based semantics without LiDAR or depth channels, preventing 3D projection and limiting its applicability to semantic SLAM or multimodal fusion.

The **UMA SAR** dataset [Morales21] provides multimodal recordings from search-and-rescue outdoor training exercises, including LiDAR, RGB cameras, thermal imagery, IMU and GNSS, all stored as ROS (1) topics. It offers long-duration mission sequences and realistic robot deployment scenarios, but it lacks semantic labels and focuses exclusively on urban SAR scenes, which limits its use in our semantic-SLAM context.

Goose [Mortimer24] is a multimodal dataset targeting autonomous mobile robots (AMRs) operating in complex urban and semi-urban spaces. Depending on the subset, it includes LiDAR, RGB, thermal, radar, IMU, GNSS and various semantic annotations. Goose provides controlled conditions with sufficient semantic structure for segmentation-based SLAM, making it one of the reference datasets to be used in TRIFFID.

WildScenes [Vidanapathirana25] is oriented toward SLAM in unstructured natural environments, combining RGB, depth, GPS and IMU data captured from both UAVs and UGVs. Although it is valuable for localization benchmarking, it does not include dense semantic annotations and provides only a minimal TF structure, reducing its suitability for semantic SLAM experiments.

SegmentedForests [Laino25] contains terrestrial LiDAR scans with high-quality per-point vegetation labels. While it is semantically rich, the data consists of static scans rather than robot-mounted acquisitions, meaning that no motion, IMU or robot-centric TF information is available. This prevents its use for odometry, LiDAR-inertial benchmarking or any SLAM pipeline evaluation.

The **GrandTour** dataset [Frey25] offers high-quality multimodal data recorded using the ANYmal quadruped robot in challenging indoor and outdoor environments. It includes LiDAR, IMU, cameras, GNSS, joint states, base odometry and well-structured calibration and TF information. Because of its motion richness and clean sensor organization, GrandTour could be used in TRIFFID for LiDAR-inertial odometry testing.

DigiForests [Malladi25] is a large-scale forest mapping dataset combining airborne and terrestrial LiDAR. Although semantically rich and built with a ROS backend, it doesn't include semantics that are interesting for this project such as humans, houses, or objects. Nonetheless, it can still be used for SLAM and segmentation of some classes. However, the Goose dataset will have preference over this one.

Given these conclusions on the available datasets, and to facilitate their comparison, Table 16 summarizes their main properties, sensing modalities and suitability for our research goals.

Table 16 Summary of the available datasets containing LiDAR data and their usability

Dataset	Sensors Modalities	Environment Type	Annotation Labels	Notes
Disaster City [Pellenz10]	LiDAR, IMU, GPS	Disaster-response test site	None	Outdated format; missing TF; GPS drift; preprocessing required.
KITTI [Geiger13]	Stereo, LiDAR, GPS/IMU	Urban driving	Yes: 2D semantics	Semantics focused on driving; the

				platform differs from UGV/SAR.
TRADR [Kruijff-Korbayová15]	RGB, Thermal, LaserScan/Point Cloud, IMU, TF	Industrial plants, forests, disaster sites	None	ROS-native; LiDAR availability inconsistent across sequences.
RUGD [Wigness19]	RGB cameras	Natural unstructured outdoor	Yes: camera frame segmentation	No LiDAR semantics; no TF chains for multimodal SLAM.
UMA SAR [Morales21]	LiDAR, RGB, Thermal, IMU, GNSS	Outdoor SAR training areas	None	ROS-native, multimodal; no semantics.
Goose [Mortimer24]	LiDAR, RGB, Thermal, IMU, GNSS	Unstructured/off-road outdoor	Yes: point-cloud and image semantics	Consistent TFs, calibrated sensors; suitable for semantic SLAM.
WildScenes [Vidanapathirana25]	RGB, LiDAR, IMU, GPS	Natural unstructured outdoor	Yes: 2D + 3D semantics	Rotating LiDAR at 0.5Hz; limited TF structure.
SegmentedForests [Laino25]	Static terrestrial LiDAR scans	Forests / vegetation	Yes: per-point labels	High-quality labels; no motion or TF data.
GrandTour [Frey25]	LiDARs, RGB, IMUs, GNSS, joint states	Indoor + outdoor locomotion terrains	None	Synchronized ANYmal dataset; excellent for odometry.
DigiForests [Malladi25]	Lidar	Natural unstructured outdoor	Yes: per-point labels	ROS-based, limited TF structure

Based on the above analysis, the following datasets are the ones with the highest potential for their usage during TRIFFID's development:

- Segmentation-based SLAM: Goose dataset
- LiDAR-inertial odometry: GrandTour dataset
- System integration and real-world validation: UPC-UWB in-house dataset collected from our real robot platform, including LiDAR, IMU, RGB, GNSS, and ROS2 TF data.

These choices provide some balance between semantic richness, sensor quality, high-frequency data, and relevance to real-field operations. However, these datasets were gathered with different purposes or use cases in mind, so they still lack some quality, frequency or other data metrics. Further, some of them use old data formats, requiring conversions that might alter them (e.g., ROS changed from version 1 to version 2, and with that, some message formats also migrated, containing new information fields). For these reasons, even though they are still valuable for some developments and validations, we also focused on data gathering as explained in the following.

3.3.1.1 Contingency data acquisition platform for early LiDAR collection

To accelerate the early stages of LiDAR-SLAM development in TRIFFID, and considering that the purchase of the UGV took several months, UPC has designed and assembled a handheld sensing device that integrates the core hardware expected on the UGV, but in a compact and easily deployable form. This platform acts as a practical bridge between simulation, algorithm design, and the eventual integration on the legged robot, allowing researchers to gather representative real-world datasets and validate the SLAM pipeline long before the full robotic system is operational. The handheld unit combines a Velodyne Puck LiDAR, Intel RealSense D455i RGB-D camera, Bosch BNO055 IMU, Reach RTK GNSS, an Intel NUC computer, a portable battery, and a 4G/5G access point providing Wi-Fi connectivity. This configuration captures the essential multimodal sensor streams (e.g., 3D LiDAR scans, depth and visual data, inertial measurements, and global positioning) that will later be used on the UGV for LiDAR-inertial odometry, map alignment, and semantic fusion.

Using such a self-contained handheld platform is beneficial for several reasons. First, it enables rapid data collection across diverse environments (indoors, outdoors, structured and unstructured scenes) without requiring the full UGV and its support systems. This allows the team to build high-quality datasets to benchmark LiDAR-inertial algorithms, design calibration procedures, and validate time synchronization strategies under controlled conditions. Second, it provides a flexible testbed for experimenting with driver configurations, network architectures, and ROS2 integration without risking mission-critical hardware. Finally, because the device can be carried, oriented, tilted, or moved through tight spaces, it exposes SLAM algorithms to motion profiles and occlusion patterns that are difficult to replicate in simulation and that closely resemble the challenging conditions the UGV will encounter in collapsed or cluttered structures. The resulting datasets and prototype run inform the selection, tuning, and validation of the LiDAR-SLAM approach used in TRIFFID (especially FAST-LIMO as described hereafter) while minimizing development overhead. The handheld platform therefore, plays a key role as an intermediate step between algorithm research and full deployment on the TRIFFID legged UGV. Figure 48 shows the handheld multimodal sensor box developed by UPC for LiDAR-SLAM prototyping.

Figure 48 Handheld multimodal sensor box developed by UPC for LiDAR-SLAM prototyping

3.3.2 UGV LiDAR-based simultaneous localization and mapping

3.3.2.1 Review of traditional and semantic LiDAR-based state-of-the-art methods

Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) is the core algorithmic capability that allows a mobile robot to estimate its own pose while incrementally building a map of an unknown environment. In GPS-denied or degraded conditions, like those of TRIFFID's use cases, SLAM becomes the primary source of localization for the UGV, providing the pose estimate that all higher-level navigation, perception and safety modules depend on. Classical SLAM formulations model the problem as the joint estimation of robot states and environmental features, either in a filtering framework (e.g. EKF-SLAM) or as a sparse non-linear optimization problem over a factor graph [Cadena16].

For the TRIFFID legged UGV, SLAM is particularly critical. The robot must operate close to debris, rubble and partially collapsed structures, often in smoke, dust or low light, where GNSS is unreliable and cameras may be severely degraded. Under these conditions, LiDAR is the most reliable modality to maintain metric consistency. LiDAR-based SLAM uses dense 3D point clouds as its primary measurement, which makes the resulting motion estimation robust to illumination, texture and many adverse visual effects. This is essential for: (i) providing a locally consistent 3D map that supports safe traversability reasoning; (ii) anchoring UGV pose estimates into the global 3D semantic map derived from UAV imagery; and (iii) enabling repeatable, drift-controlled navigations across extended areas and long durations. The UGV in TRIFFID will therefore rely on a LiDAR-inertial SLAM pipeline to estimate its 6-DoF pose and to produce a locally dense representation of the terrain around it. This local

map will be aligned to the global UAV-based semantic map described in T4.1, combining aerial scale with ground-level precision.

Over the last decade, LiDAR SLAM has evolved from relatively simple scan-matching pipelines to sophisticated multi-sensor systems that fuse LiDAR with inertial and other modalities. Early and foundational work such as LOAM (Lidar Odometry and Mapping in Real-time) [Zhang14] demonstrated that it is possible to achieve low-drift 6-DoF odometry estimation and mapping using a spinning laser scanner, by decoupling a high-frequency odometry front-end from a lower-frequency mapping back-end. LOAM extracts edge and planar features from each scan, uses a fast scan-to-scan odometry module to track motion, and refines the trajectory at a lower rate by aligning to a global map. This method achieved SOTA accuracy on the KITTI odometry benchmark⁵ [Geiger12B] and has accumulated several thousand citations, becoming a canonical reference for LiDAR SLAM. Building on this, LeGO-LOAM (Lightweight and Ground-Optimized LOAM) [Shan18] specialized the LOAM architecture for ground vehicles. It segments the point cloud, explicitly models the ground, and uses this structure to simplify optimization and reduce computation. The method is designed to run in real time on embedded hardware, making it attractive for UGVs with limited compute. LeGO-LOAM has been widely adopted and extended in the robotics community and is one of the most cited LiDAR SLAM variants after LOAM itself.

In parallel, systems such as Google Cartographer [Hess16] demonstrated that it is possible to perform real-time loop closure and globally consistent mapping using 2D or 3D range sensors. Cartographer combines a local SLAM system that maintains submaps with a global optimization back-end that continuously solves for a consistent pose graph, integrating loop-closure constraints as they are detected. This architecture has been influential in subsequent submap-based SLAM designs and is widely deployed in commercial and research platforms.

More recently, LiDAR-inertial odometry and SLAM (LIO/LIS) systems have become dominant. They exploit high-rate IMU data to deskew LiDAR scans, improve motion prediction and increase robustness under fast motion and sparse structure. LIO-SAM [Shan20] is one of the most prominent representatives: it formulates LiDAR-inertial odometry as a factor-graph optimization, using IMU pre-integration. This yields highly accurate, globally consistent trajectories and has made LIO-SAM a standard baseline in many comparative studies. In LIO-SAM, each node in the graph corresponds to a robot state (pose, velocity, IMU biases), and factors encode constraints from IMU pre-integration, LiDAR scan-to-map alignment and loop closures. The IMU is used to deskew the point cloud and provide a high-rate motion prior; LiDAR constraints then refine this estimate. Loop closures are detected with scan-context descriptors and integrated online to reduce drift and enforce global consistency. To remain real-time, LIO-SAM marginalizes older states and performs optimization over a sliding window, while maintaining a separate global map representation. This enables high accuracy at moderate computational cost, but the factor-graph optimization remains relatively heavy, especially on constrained hardware. LIO-SAM's main strengths are its globally consistent trajectories and the maturity of its open-source implementation.

At the same time, a complementary line of work has focused on efficiency. FAST-LIO [Xu21] and FAST-LIO2 [Xu22] propose tightly-coupled LiDAR-inertial odometry based on an iterated error-state Kalman filter, rather than a full factor graph. FAST-LIO2 removes hand-crafted feature extraction by registering raw points directly against a map stored in an incremental k-d tree (ikd-Tree), allowing the

⁵ https://www.cvlibs.net/datasets/kitti/eval_odometry.php

system to exploit subtle geometric details while maintaining high update rates (up to ~ 100 Hz) even on embedded platforms. These frameworks have set a high bar for real-time performance and have become widely used in autonomous driving and robotics.

LiDAR-based SLAM has emerged as the prevailing standard due to its capacity for precise range measurements and robustness to illumination variations, thereby ensuring a high-fidelity three-dimensional representation of the captured environment. This renders it more appropriate for environmental representation than camera-based SLAM. Despite their capacity to generate precise geometric representations of the surrounding environment, point clouds are characterized by sparsity and a lack of texture in the captured data. Consequently, the integration of semantic information with LiDAR data enhances the comprehension of the diverse scenarios that may arise during autonomous exploration. The efficacy of SLAM is enhanced through the implementation of semantic loop closing, which involves the alignment of proximate semantics. Another advantage of incorporating semantic data into SLAM is its potential to enhance the comprehensibility of the underlying scenario for users with less familiarity with the interpretation of LiDAR point clouds.

Most of the current approaches for semantic LiDAR-SLAM use the different labels to perform a semantic assisted Iterative-Closest-Points (ICP) approach, meaning that the point clouds are downsampled based on the semantic label, as in the case of SA-LOAM [Li21B] or SAGE-ICP [Cui24]. This technique has been demonstrated to enhance the ICP performance: rather than employing the conventional nearest neighbour pairing method, semantic methods facilitate the direct association of two points with the same label. Alternatively, these methods can assign a weight coefficient based on the semantic label consistency of the associated point pair.

SuMa [Behley18], and its extension SuMa++ [Chen19B] utilize the stability of the semantic labels to filter out dynamic objects. As illustrated in Figure 49, a comparative analysis is presented between SuMa (a), SuMa++ (b), and a version filtering all detected objects that have associated classes indicating potential dynamics (e.g., cars marked with blue points). Here, this evaluation of stability (i.e., static vs dynamic labels) is crucial in order to avoid erroneous associations between observations and the map, thereby enhancing the accuracy of SLAM trajectories.

Figure 49 Effect of filtering dynamic objects. (a) Surfels generated by SuMa; (b) SuMa++ method; (c) remove all potentially moving objects

A more recent approach that also filters the dynamic labels is SD-SLAM [Li24C]. Rather than employing an ICP to estimate the pose, SD-SLAM initially derives a coarse pose estimate through the execution of landmark pairing between frames. Instead of employing log-odds as SuMa++, a Kalman filter is implemented, which differentiates between semi-static and dynamic landmarks. Subsequently, the static and semi-static models are employed for the purpose of precise pose estimation.

In the field of semantic SLAM, a particular branch of research focuses on semantic graph-enhanced SLAM. This approach involves constructing a factor graph comprising various landmarks and subsequently optimising it, a process which can be accomplished with GTSAM [Dellaert22]. SlideSLAM [Liu25B] is a multi-robot real-time SLAM that presents three different levels of abstraction. The lowest level is employed for autonomous navigation and geometric exploration. The middle level is not applicable in real time and is used for more detailed representations. The high level is used for semantic landmarks, enabling localisation and mapping, and is where the GTSAM is implemented. Another method that uses factor graphs is SG-SLAM [Neng25], which performs odometry estimation with a semantic downsampled ICP. The database is formed by descriptors and used in conjunction with the factor graph to perform loop closing, based on the semantic landmarks and the background points.

It is important to note that all previous methodologies are reliant upon the precision of the semantic labels utilized. Hence, in the following we shift our focus to the various existing methods of semantic segmentation that can extend a SLAM architecture. One of the most common semantic segmentation methods is RangeNet++ [Milioto19]; it is used by SuMa++ or SD-SLAM. Firstly, RangeNet++ converts the point cloud to a range image, obtaining a transformation between spherical coordinates to image coordinates. With the range image it is possible to use a CNN to train and segment each LiDAR point. The main downside of this method is that the coordinate transformation yields to overlapping and some of the points in the point cloud are not represented in the range image. Cylinder3D [Zhu21C] proposed a different approach to avoid this exact issue and retain the geometric information which RangeNet++ fails to do. It uses a cylinder coordinate system to replace the Cartesian grid partition. It utilizes the increasing grid to cover the further-away region, thus it more evenly distributes the points across different regions and matches the distribution of outdoor points. Figure 50 shows an example with the results of the Cylinder3D technique applied to the Waymo dataset [Sun20].

Figure 50 Example of Cylinder3D segmentation on a frame of the Waymo dataset

Lately, there has been an increased trend of equipping commercial vehicles and robots with both cameras and LiDARs. The present configuration facilitates the enhancement of semantic segmentation through the integration of data from two complementary sensors. SAM4D [Xu25] is a multi-modal and temporal FM designed for promptable segmentation across camera and LiDAR streams. The system is

capable of generating camera-LiDAR aligned pseudo-labels with promptable multi-modal segmentation, meaning it is able to receive point prompts either on the camera or the LiDAR and transform them into the other. This solution is effective for the segmentation of concrete labels. However, for the purpose of achieving complete scene segmentation, as is required for SLAM, an image segmentation model is necessary in order to generate the labels that will be transferred from the camera to the point cloud, thus facilitating a comprehensive understanding of the surroundings. The following Figure 51 illustrates the utilisation of the SAM2 [Ravi24] as an image segmentation model, which generates prompts in the image to convert them to a point cloud using the SAM4D.

Figure 51 Example of SAM2 segmentation (left) and the pseudo-labels generated by the SAM4D on the point cloud (right)

It is not efficient for a computer mounted in a robot to have one model to segment images and then another to convert labels to point clouds. However, it might be useful for converting image labels provided by an external agent to the robot point cloud. 2DPASS [Yan22] is a method and a general training scheme that has been developed for the purpose of enhancing representation learning on point clouds. In the training process, the system utilizes images and LiDAR separately, extracting features from both sources. Subsequently, a multi-scale fusion-to-single knowledge distillation (MSFSKD) is conducted to enhance the 3D network using multi-modal features. This process involves the full utilisation of texture and colour-aware 2D priors, in addition to retaining the original 3D-specific knowledge. During the process of inference, the 2D branch is disregarded, thus enabling a more rapid computation in comparison to alternative fusion-based approaches. Figure 52 shows an example of the 2DPASS segmentation outcome on the KITTI dataset [Geiger12].

Figure 52 Example of 2DPASS segmentation in the KITTI dataset

3.3.2.2 Implemented solution

FAST-LIMO⁶ is an open-source LiDAR-inertial SLAM system implemented by the UPC (formula student team) that builds directly on ideas from FAST-LIO2 and UPC's LIMO-Velo [Segarra22], but is explicitly engineered for high-velocity platforms and modern LiDARs. It implements a tightly-coupled iterated Kalman filter (following the formulation of incremental Kalman Filters on manifolds [He22]) and uses a fast incremental map structure derived from ikd-Tree to store and query 3D points.

Architecturally, FAST-LIMO is organized into two main threads. The prediction thread continuously propagates the state with high-rate IMU data, while the update thread consumes LiDAR packets or full scans to deskew the point cloud, perform scan-to-map alignment and update the filter state by minimizing point-to-plane residuals. This design allows it to support both traditional “full-scan” LiDAR drivers and modified drivers that stream scan packets as they are produced, increasing temporal resolution and robustness under fast motion. From an algorithmic standpoint, FAST-LIMO maintains an internal state comprising pose, velocity and IMU biases. IMU measurements, arriving at high rate, are integrated in an error-state formulation that propagates the state forward. When LiDAR data arrive, individual points are deskewed using the predicted motion and registered against the current map via point-to-plane optimization. The resulting residuals update the filter, correcting both pose and biases. This tightly-coupled scheme is important for the UGV because it:

- Reduces motion-induced distortion in scans during fast rotations or legged gaits,
- Maintains stable accuracy even when local structure is sparse or partially occluded.
- Keeps latency low, a prerequisite for safe control on rough terrain.

FAST-LIMO has been developed by the UPC team during several previous projects before TRIFFID (e.g., the BotNet⁷ project, 23S06128-00, founded by “Ajuntament de Barcelona” and “Fundació La Caixa”) and was not explicitly tailored to platforms like the TRIFFID's UGV. During such developments we validated our approach using the famous KITTI dataset [Geiger12]. Results of these validations are shown in Figure 53, with the Absolute Positional Error (APE) of FAST-LIMO using the Kitty dataset 0034 2011/09/30, where we obtained a maximum of 1.9m, a mean of 1.6m and a standard deviation of 0.496m of APE error. Further comparisons included the evaluation of the APE error on other datasets of KITTI, such as the raw unsynced 0027 2011/09/30, where we obtained a maximum of 0.993m, a mean of 0.3025m and a standard deviation of 0.22m of APE error for a path length of 690.7m, as shown in Figure 54.

⁶ https://github.com/fetty31/fast_LIMO

⁷ <https://www.iri.upc.edu/project/show/317>

Figure 53 APE of FAST-LIMO using the 0034 Kitty dataset⁸

Figure 54 APE of FAST-LIMO using the raw unsynced 0027 Kitty dataset⁹

FAST-LIMO has also been tested on high-speed platforms such as the UPCs Formula Student autonomous race cars¹⁰, where it has demonstrated reliable operation at high longitudinal and angular velocities, making it very interesting in platforms such as the TRIFFID’s UGV that can experience high dynamics while walking. Hence, FAST-LIMO is particularly attractive for TRIFFID because it offers a high-rate, low-latency odometry suitable for dynamic UGV maneuvers; a C++/ROS2 implementation aligned with the rest of the autonomy stack; support for different LiDAR brands and scanning patterns; and a design that can be extended with loop closure and map-based localization when needed.

⁸ KITTI 0034 2011/09/30

⁹ KITTI 0034 2011/09/30

¹⁰ <https://telecos.upc.edu/ca/futurs-estudiants/informacio-per-futurs-estudiants/projectes-estrategics/driverless-upc>

In the initial phase of TRIFFID, FAST-LIMO will be adopted as the core LiDAR-inertial odometry module for the legged UGV. Its role is to provide a continuous 6-DoF pose estimate of the robot base and a locally consistent 3D map of the surrounding environment. These outputs will feed:

- The UGV navigation stack (local planners and traversability analysis) in WP3-T3.2.
- The safety and monitoring layer, which relies on consistent pose estimates to detect anomalies in WP3-T3.3.
- The mapping fusion pipeline that aligns UGV LiDAR geometry with the UAV-derived 3D semantic map (WP4).

Implementation-wise, FAST-LIMO relies on robust open-source components (e.g. IKFoM and ikd-Tree-inspired data structures) and exposes ROS-compatible topics for poses and point clouds. This fits naturally with the existing ROS2-based architecture of the UGV, and allows the module to be containerized, monitored and updated within the same CI/CD infrastructure as the rest of the TRIFFID software. Finally, the experience already accumulated by the UPC team in applying FAST-LIMO to high-dynamic platforms (e.g. autonomous race cars) is directly transferable to the legged UGV. It reduces integration risk and accelerates the process of tuning the system to TRIFFID-specific LiDARs and motion profiles. In this sense, on 20th and 21st of October of 2025, UPC's team members visited the UWB premises for an integration exercise. Among others, one of the tests carried out was the installation and test of FAST-LIMO running onboard the TRIFFID's UGV, which was very successful. Figure 55 shows an example of the map obtained by FAST-LIMO running onboard the TRIFFID's UGV in one of the tests in UWB premises.

Figure 55 Example of FAST-LIMO implementation running onboard the TRIFFID UGV in the UWB campus

Even though LiDAR-based SLAM is a requirement for the navigation of the TRIFFID's UGV, it is important to recognize that mapping alone might not be sufficient in some of the higher-level functions required in TRIFFID. Beyond estimating poses and producing a consistent 3D structure, the UGV could also understand what the environment contains: passable vs. non-passable regions, types of obstacles, human-relevant elements, and structural categories that influence risk. Semantic SLAM addresses this gap by enriching the geometric map with class-level information derived from visual, thermal or learned perception models. While classical LiDAR-based SLAM relies exclusively on geometry, recent research has explored how semantics can guide data association, improve robustness in low-structure

scenes, and produce maps that are more useful for navigation and decision-making. For TRIFFID, semantic integration will consist of several thrusts: First, by anchoring LiDAR geometry to the UAV's 3D semantic reconstruction. Then, we will investigate if semantics can be directly leveraged in the local UGV SLAM system. In this sense, the following introduces the main concepts of semantic SLAM we are currently exploring and outlines how semantic cues can be incorporated into LiDAR-based pipelines as a first step toward unified geometric-semantic mapping on the ground.

3.3.2.3 Towards semantic simultaneous localization and mapping

Given this SOTA status, and the fact that we have a the FAST-LIMO LiDAR-based SLAM as the baseline for the mapping and localization of the UGV in the first stages of TRIFFID, we are currently exploring to incorporate semantic information into our SLAM. Our initial approach is based on extending SG-SLAM [Neng25], to produce our first lightweight and robust semantic graph SLAM. In order to function in real time, SG-SLAM relies on labels provided by off-the-shelf segmentation. This enables the SLAM system to maintain its functionality and incorporate different segmentation frontends. However, in the original publication, these labels were provided by the ground truth of the KITTI dataset. Therefore, 2DPASS [Yan22] has been selected as the segmentation technique, primarily due to its capacity to perform inference directly over the point clouds obtained from the LiDAR sensor. This facilitates a more rapid inference process in comparison to alternative methodologies. As is the case with the majority of LiDAR segmentation methods, 2DPASS has been trained with the KITTI dataset, a fact that is particularly useful given that it is also the main benchmark for LiDAR SLAM. Consequently, we have been able to verify the effectiveness of SG-SLAM in structured environments. Furthermore, the capacity to train 2DPASS in a range of scenarios will facilitate the testing of the capabilities of SG-SLAM in unstructured environments. Furthermore, the SG-SLAM algorithm exclusively employs foreground instances, such as poles, trunks and static vehicles, which are inherently distinguishable from background points, including buildings and fences. These latter instances are typically extensive and perspective-dependent, rendering them unstable for representation as instance nodes. This approach has been shown to be effective in outdoor structured environments, as evidenced by the KITTI dataset, which depicts a car driving through streets. Consequently, the identification of various trunks and poles is rendered straightforward. In the Figure 56 below the instances used for the nodes of the semantic graph can be seen, blue being static vehicles, brown trunks and white poles. In the context of unstructured environments, such as forests or indoor settings, the identification of these notable features may be a significant challenge and will present future research opportunities within the TRIFFID framework and use cases.

Figure 56 Result of the SG-SLAM over KITTI sequence 00, with 2DPASS segmentation. In this case, we marked the trajectory in red, the odometry estimation in green, and the nodes used for the semantic graph. Also, static vehicles are shown in blue, trunks in brown and poles as white

3.3.3 UGV traversability analysis

3.3.3.1 Review of state-of-the-art methods

Traversability analysis aims to determine which regions of the environment a ground robot can safely cross, taking into account not only geometric properties but also semantic and contextual cues that impact autonomous locomotion. For complex outdoor and disaster-response scenarios, this capability is essential because terrain may include compact soil, vegetation, debris fields, rubble, steep surfaces, soft ground, and visually ambiguous regions. LiDAR is an attractive sensing modality due to its robustness to illumination conditions, weather, and environmental variability; however, its sparsity and lack of intrinsic semantics require dedicated processing to infer terrain characteristics and traversability in real time.

Historically, geometric terrain modeling began with elevation-map-based methods designed for outdoor UGV navigation, providing structured representations for ground and obstacle discrimination [Pfaff13]. Hybrid elevation mapping later introduced multi-layer surface models capable of better handling overhangs and irregular outdoor scenes [Douillard10]. Additional segmentation strategies emerged to address the limitations of elevation maps. Fast geometric segmentation methods demonstrated the benefits of exploiting LiDAR scan geometry for near-real-time ground extraction [Himmelsbach10], while graphical models based on loopy belief propagation showed robustness to noise and sparsity in 3D point clouds [Zhang15]. Coarse-to-fine Markov Random Field approaches provided improved segmentation in large or cluttered outdoor environments [Huang22]. Further work explored lightweight online segmentation that remained efficient even in sparse LiDAR data [Bogoslavskyi17], while graph-structured segmentation methods, such as TRAVEL, leveraged spatial relationships between points to separate ground and non-ground regions reliably across varying environmental conditions [Oh22].

Parallel to geometric segmentation, progress in semantic LiDAR understanding has been driven by large annotated datasets such as 2DPASS [Yan22], SemanticKITTI [Behley19], and nuScenes [Caesar20].

These datasets enabled deep neural segmentation architectures capable of distinguishing detailed classes in urban and semi-structured environments. However, their deployment on embedded robotic platforms remains challenging due to high computation demands and vulnerability to adversarial effects, particularly in safety-critical field operations [Bar20]. This reveals a practical gap: deep semantic models achieve excellent accuracy but are often unsuitable for real-time, onboard UGV operation.

Aside from the terrain segmentation, autonomous ground robots also require a reliable and computationally efficient representation of their surrounding environment to perform safe navigation. In TRIFFID, the legged UGV relies on LiDAR-based SLAM to produce accurate 3D point clouds of the environment, but using these raw points for real-time navigation or obstacle avoidance is often too costly. A structured environment model must be derived from the SLAM output, enabling rapid collision checks, local planning, and safe motion execution. Occupancy Grid Maps (OGMs) serve precisely this role.

OGMs were introduced as a probabilistic spatial representation in mobile robotics to encode the likelihood of each cell in a discretized 2D map being either free or occupied [Elfes90]. This representation continues to underpin modern navigation systems, including those in ROS2 (Nav2¹¹) and the ones used in TRIFFID (WP3-T3.2, described in the deliverable D3.1). The main advantages of OGMs are their simplicity, deterministic update rules, and compatibility with real-time planning algorithms such as the Dynamic Window Approach [Fox95], grid-based path search, and costmap-based reactive behaviors. For obstacle avoidance, OGMs provide a conservative yet robust abstraction: free cells are assumed safe to traverse, whereas any cell with occupancy above a threshold is treated as an obstacle, ensuring high reliability in cluttered or semi-structured environments.

However, LiDAR-based SLAM naturally produces 3D point clouds, not 2D grids. Projecting raw point clouds directly into an OGM is undesirable because the robot would lose information about vertical structures, overhangs, vegetation density, and multi-level clutter. Instead, an intermediate 3D representation is typically constructed. OctoMap [Hornung13] is a commonly used probabilistic 3D mapping framework that organizes space into an octree, efficiently storing free, occupied, and unknown regions with a Bayesian update mechanism. Because OctoMap maintains a hierarchical structure, it can represent large outdoor environments while remaining memory-efficient, an advantage for long-duration TRIFFID missions. An example of the OctoMap representation is shown in Figure 57.

¹¹ <https://docs.nav2.org/>

Figure 57 Example of an Octree showing free (white) and occupied (black) cells, with the volumetric model (top-left) and its tree representation (top-right). The bottom row illustrates OctoMap's ability to represent the environment at multiple resolutions

3.3.3.2 Ground segmentation and occupancy representation

To address the gap between the accuracy of the deep semantic models and their unfeasibility to run onboard in embedded computing means, within TRIFFID, we adopt a hybrid approach combining reliable geometric ground segmentation with lightweight semantic inference. Patchwork++, based on the Patchwork concentric-zone region-wise ground segmentation method [Lim21], offers a ready-to-use deterministic geometric segmentation module. Its iterative plane estimation and region-likelihood modeling provide robust performance across diverse environments, including slopes, vegetated scenes, and non-uniform terrain. It forms an efficient first stage that isolates ground points and removes above-ground obstacles.

However, geometric ground segmentation alone cannot determine whether a geometrically flat surface is safe for traversal. Vegetation layers, soft or unstable terrain, wet ground, or rubble may appear planar in LiDAR geometry while remaining hazardous. To overcome this limitation, we will investigate the integration of a single-scan LiDAR semantic classifier from our previous work [Pino24]. This method extracts geometric and radiometric descriptors (such as local smoothness, slope, intensity distribution, incidence patterns, and prediction-error metrics) directly from raw LiDAR scans, using a shallow neural model capable of real-time inference on CPU-only platforms. It classifies surface materials into categories such as asphalt, compact soil, loose soil, or vegetation, enabling discrimination of visually similar but physically distinct terrain types. In combination, Patchwork++ provides robust and efficient geometric ground segmentation, while the LiDAR semantic classifier refines these results by identifying surface types that are not traversable despite passing geometric checks. This mirrors the strategy validated in our previous work, where vegetation and unstable soil were reliably distinguished from traversable regions using only single-scan LiDAR features. The integrated pipeline, shown in Figure 58, will produce accurate, computationally efficient traversability estimations tailored to TRIFFID's UGV requirements. Finally, regions identified as non-traversable will be incorporated into occupancy-grid-based obstacle avoidance to ensure safe navigation in complex environments.

Figure 58 Two-stage segmentation scheme. First, the ground is segmented using LiDAR scans and then a shallow neural network is used to classify traversable and non-traversable ground using semantic information

Once we have the ground correctly segmented, in TRIFFID we leverage OctoMap as a bridge between the segmented dense point cloud and the navigation: the segmented SLAM point cloud (or pose-registered point clouds accumulated over time extracting the traversable areas) is inserted into the octree, and only the cells intersecting the ground-relevant height band are later projected into a 2D OGM. This ensures that obstacles such as rubble, concrete blocks, vegetation clusters, or collapsed structures are correctly preserved as occupied cells in the resulting 2D map. Conversely, overhanging structures and high-level clutter do not pollute the ground plane, preventing false obstacles that would unnecessarily restrict navigation.

The final OGM, often maintained as a costmap layer (WP3 - T3.2) enables the UGV to perform real-time obstacle avoidance by continuously updating free and occupied regions, inflating them for safety, and enabling planners to compute safe trajectories in dynamic or partially-known environments. This layered architecture (SLAM - OctoMap - OGM) ensures both geometric fidelity and computational tractability, supporting fast reaction times while preserving consistency between 3D perception and 2D navigation.

Even though standard OctoMap-based algorithms often produce a ground projection of the 3D, these do not satisfy the navigation requirements of the TRIFFID UGV. If raw point cloud data contains obstacles at any height, including ceiling detections, these are projected directly onto the ground plane, erroneously marking free space as occupied. Such behavior causes issues near doorframes, overhanging structures, or sensor noise. Additionally, OctoMap does not automatically remove spurious detections, causing dynamic obstacles to smear across the costmap as persistent noise. To address these limitations, UPC developed a custom perception algorithm. Our method continuously queries an octree representation of the surrounding environment. When evaluating whether a cell should be marked as free or occupied, the robot’s current height is considered, and only voxels within a configurable vertical window around that height are treated as relevant for navigation. In effect, the algorithm checks for obstacles within the robot’s local traversable band rather than across the entire scene. A schematic 2D representation of this concept is shown in Figure 59.

Figure 59 Depiction of different scenarios (left), of their traversability according to MapConverter (middle) and their projection to an occupancy map (right)

This approach directly mitigates the issues associated with standard OctoMap ground projection. Obstacles detected on ceilings or elevated surfaces are ignored unless they intersect the robot’s navigable height range. Dynamic obstacles are naturally handled because the octree is continuously updated, providing consistent clearing of outdated sensor information. Furthermore, the method enables genuinely three-dimensional navigation reasoning: a quadrupedal robot ascending or descending slopes, uneven terrain, or multi-level structures can interpret obstacles relative to its current height rather than assuming a globally flat world. However, the method does not come without limitations. Because obstacle evaluation is restricted to a vertical band around the robot, the system may incorrectly classify sloped terrain as non-traversable. In situations where the ground height varies significantly along the robot’s path, regions of valid terrain may fall outside the fixed vertical window, leading to conservative or overly restrictive costmap generation. In summary, the algorithm provides a cleaner, safer, and more semantically meaningful 2D costmap for navigation in scenarios where traditional projection methods fail, particularly for robots operating in non-flat environments or environments with substantial vertical structural complexity. Nonetheless, its dependence on a height-centered vertical window introduces challenges on steep or rapidly changing slopes, where future extensions may require adaptive height reasoning or local terrain estimation.

Once the OGM has been obtained, the navigation stack must transform this representation into actionable constraints for real-time motion planning. The TRIFFID navigation stack, presented in the deliverable D3.1 and part of the task developments of WP3-T3.2, accomplishes this through a layered costmap architecture, where the OGM acts as the foundational occupancy layer and is further processed to ensure safe local navigation. A key step in this process is costmap inflation, which expands the influence of each obstacle by assigning increasing cost values to nearby cells. Inflation ensures that

even if the robot's localization contains minor drift, or if the LiDAR under-samples thin structures, the planner maintains a safe clearance by treating regions around obstacles as progressively risky. This approach reduces the likelihood of scraping against obstacles, entering narrow gaps, or colliding with protruding structures that are only partially captured in the point cloud. On top of the inflated costmap, the robot's local planner computes feasible motion commands that obey both kinematic and dynamic constraints.

Dynamic environments introduce additional complexity. People, vehicles, debris, and moving objects commonly appear in TRIFFID-related missions. Static costmaps are insufficient in such settings because obstacles must be updated at high frequency. Therefore, further investigation will be required to extend the current usage of OGMs to incorporate dynamic obstacle filtering. For the TRIFFID UGV, dynamic filtering might become relevant in cluttered outdoor environments where branches, vegetation, dust, and human responders may produce intermittent or partial LiDAR returns.

3.3.4 Mapping fusion with 3D semantic map

3.3.4.1 Review of state-of-the-art methods

Multi-robot mapping originates in the desire to accelerate SLAM by deploying multiple agents to collect complementary perspectives. Classical multi-robot map fusion required aligning point clouds, typically via ICP or its variants such as Generalized ICP (G-ICP) [Segal09]. A well accepted approach based on ICP for a lightweight SLAM computation is KISS-ICP [Vizzo23], which emphasizes efficiency. More robust formulations, such as KISS-Matcher [Lim25] include TEASER++ [Yang20] for point cloud registration and certifiable outlier rejection. However, all these approaches primarily operate on point sets, thus using and resulting in a geometric-only 3D representation.

This lack of photometric detail creates the need to improve the expressiveness of 3D point clouds. Traditional enhancements include textured meshes and dense stereo or RGB-D reconstructions [Newcombe11], [Dai17B]. Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs) [Mildenhall21] introduced differentiable volumetric scene representations that allow novel-view synthesis, at the cost of long training times and high memory footprints [Gao22]. To mitigate these limitations, several variants have been proposed, such as Sparse Voxel Rasterization (SVR) [Sun25], which leverages voxel grids and efficient rasterization for real-time, high-fidelity radiance field rendering. Recently, 3DGS [Kerbl23, Meuleman25] has emerged as a real-time alternative, approximating radiance fields with anisotropic Gaussians. 3DGS achieves photorealistic rendering with orders of magnitude faster compared to NeRF, making it attractive for multi-robot pipelines [Zhu24A]. Data alignment in radiance-based representations, such as 3DGS, is often achieved indirectly by matching features in the image space (e.g., NetVLAD, or learned global descriptors [Arandjelovic16, Hausler21]) rather than directly optimizing in the 3D representation.

Current Multi-Robot SLAM (MR-SLAM) methods underutilize the rich rendering attributes embedded in 3DGS. Recent systems like HAMMER [Yu25] and MAGiC-SLAM [Yugay25] provide collaborative or multi-agent mapping with 3DGS, supporting asynchronous streams, semantic embeddings, sub-map merging and loop closure. However, these methods generally use image tracking for pose alignment, rather than a registration algorithm that directly matches Gaussian primitives across maps with probabilistic geometric and photometric terms. Matching two Gaussian splat maps derived from distinct sensor and estimation pipelines (e.g., LiDAR-based SLAM vs monocular SfM) remains particularly challenging when coverage is partial or when viewpoints differ significantly. Hence, in this work, we propose extending conventional point-to-point ICP to a Gaussian-aware registration algorithm that

incorporates photometric terms (i.e., color and opacity) into a unified cost function. This photogeometric formulation aims to enable robust alignment across modalities and densities, leveraging the probabilistic structure of 3DGS representations.

The initial version of TRIFFID’s architecture for multi-robot map fusion is shown in Figure 60. On the one side, we consider a semantic 3DGS built from the UAV imagery, as described in the sections above. One such solution is georeferenced monocular 3DGS, where GNSS priors are injected into the image-based optimization [Lhuillier11]. This yields metrically consistent maps but remains sensitive to GNSS degradation in urban, forested, or indoor environments. In our aerial platform (blue pipeline in Figure 58), this approach provided a reliable global frame. As an alternative, one can rely on SLAM-inferred trajectories, which directly enforce metric consistency at the cost of extra computation. For our ground platform (red pipeline in the same Figure), we can adopt the FAST-LIMO approach, described above, to generate metrically scaled poses and construct a 3DGS. Platform characteristics shape the resulting 3DGS: Aerial vehicles capture large-scale, multi-altitude scenes but at reduced ground fidelity, while ground vehicles provide high-resolution detail with limited viewpoint diversity. Notice, for instance, these differences between the 3DGS generated by the aerial and ground vehicles in Figure 60. In our dataset, shared start and end points ensured sufficient overlap for cross-platform alignment, though specialized preprocessing may be required in less favorable conditions.

Figure 60 Initial aerial-ground multi-robot mapping pipeline, using different 3DGS generation methods and our novel 3DGS matching algorithm to estimate the ground–aerial relative transformation

3.3.4.2 3DGS map filtering and preprocessing

Raw 3DGS maps often contain many Gaussians that do not correspond to real physical surfaces, which could be initialization artifacts or splats generated with low confidence. To ensure robust and efficient registration after the initial 3DGS we developed a two-stage filtering pipeline: opacity-based culling followed by statistical outlier removal.

Opacity based filtering discards splats with opacity below a threshold, since these low-opacity Gaussians contribute little to the rendered scene. While opacity filtering removes visually uninformative splats, it does not address spatial anomalies, such as isolated or spurious Gaussians that may remain due to noise or imperfect initialization. Statistical outlier removal is then applied to further clean the filtered set. We adopt the standard approach from [Yoon24], where a point is considered an outlier if its Euclidean mean distance to its k -nearest neighbors exceeds a threshold defined by the global statistics.

The impact of this two-stage filtering is shown in Figure 61, where noise and irrelevant splats are effectively removed, resulting in a much cleaner 3DGS map. This reduction in dataset size makes registration and optimization faster. Even though one could filter a 3DGS by just considering the centroids of the Gaussian splats and using traditional point cloud processing, filtering by opacity considerably improves the correspondence quality and matching reliability of downstream alignment steps.

Figure 61 Impact of two-stage filtering on 3DGS maps

To address the scaling ambiguity issue on SfM-generated 3DGS, various anchoring strategies have been employed:

- **Object Anchoring:** Detecting in the images a scene object of known dimensions, which could be deliberately added with minimal scene contamination next to the base station, thus observed during deployment of the robot. In our experiments, we introduced a fiducial marker (i.e., an AprilTag [Wang16]) of known dimensions. Enabling pose estimation using a Perspective-n-Point (PnP) algorithm, hence allowing a direct scale estimation. The procedure is described in more detail hereafter, and shown as the bottom orange pipeline of Figure 60 as an option in case of a poor or lacking GNSS signal during initialization.
- **GNSS Anchoring:** Quality (outdoors) GNSS provides globally-consistent and geo-referenced metric observations. By embedding GNSS coordinates as statistical priors into SfM or SLAM optimization, scale drift can be mitigated and local reconstructions can be anchored to a global frame.
- **Final Scale Refinement:** Regardless of the two previous anchoring methods (Fiducial or GNSS), residual misalignment remains due to noise and drift. To refine the normalization, we rely on RANSAC's similarity estimation, which robustly rejects outlier correspondences and produces a consistent scale and alignment across robots. This two-stage approach (i.e., global anchoring followed by robust scale refinement) ensures that heterogeneous 3DGS maps can be integrated into a coherent multi-robot representation.

In our initial tests, we employ AprilTags as fiducials for the object anchoring. The procedure, shown in Figure 62, is as follows:

- Detect the AprilTag corners in an image. With the tag pose estimated in COLMAP, apply PnP optimization to recover its orientation.
- Cast rays from the camera center through each detected corner and discretize candidate points in the sparse 3DGS point cloud that lie close to these rays.
- Select the corner candidates that best represent the tag by minimizing the cost function:

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=0}^3 (d_{plane}^i + d_{ray}^i + a \cdot d_{camera}^i),$$

Where d_{plane}^i is the distance from candidate i to the estimated tag plane; d_{ray}^i is the distance to its corresponding ray; and d_{camera}^i is the distance to the observing camera.

- From the four selected centroids, we retain the two with the lowest cost.
- Compute the distance between these two centroids and scale the entire 3DGS such that this distance matches the known tag size.

Using this procedure brings the original monocular 3DGS to a rough metric scale that is precise enough for a posterior matching.

Figure 62 3DGS rough scaling using AprilTag marker

3.3.4.3 Implemented solution

Traditional ICP algorithms operate purely on geometric correspondence, limiting their effectiveness when registering 3DGS maps that contain rich photometric information. Our approach extends the classical point-to-point ICP framework by incorporating color and opacity into both correspondence finding and rigid transform estimation through multimodal feature vectors that combine normalized spatial coordinates with scaled photometric attributes. This exploits the fact that splats with similar appearance properties are more likely to correspond to the same physical surfaces.

The proposed multimodal 3DGS-ICP pipeline, detailed in Figure 63, follows four main steps: (i) preprocessing and filtering (detailed in Section III.B); (ii) RANSAC-based initialization using FPFH descriptors extracted from 3DGS centroid positions for scale and coarse alignment; (iii) multimodal feature construction; and (iv) iterative refinement with weighted correspondence matching. We focus on presenting our novel contributions in steps (iii) and (iv) hereafter.

- Multimodal Feature Construction For each Gaussian splat, we construct a unified feature vector that encodes both geometric and photometric information:

$$f_i = [p_{norm}, \gamma \cdot c_i, \delta \cdot o_i],$$

where p_{norm} and c_i are the normalized 3D position and RGB color (mapped to $[0, 1]^3$), respectively. o_i is the opacity value, and γ and δ are scaling factors that control the relative influence of color and opacity features compared to the spatial data, e.g., small γ and δ values provide subtle photometric guidance without overwhelming spatial proximity, while larger values increase appearance matching influence. The feature vector dimensionality adapts based on which

modalities are enabled: 3D (position only), 4D (position + opacity), 6D (position + color), or 7D (position + color + opacity).

- **Weighted Correspondence and Transform Estimation** During each 3DGS-ICP iteration, correspondences are established in the multimodal feature space searching the nearest neighbours, stored as a k-d tree for efficiency. However, rather than treating all correspondences equally, we compute confidence weights based on photometric similarity:

$$w_{color} = \exp(-\alpha \cdot d_{color}^2),$$

$$w_{opacity} = \exp(-\beta \cdot d_{opacity}^2),$$

$$w_i = w_{color} \cdot w_{opacity},$$

Where $d_{color} = \|c_s - c_t\|_2 / \sqrt{3}$ is the normalized color distance, $d_{opacity} = |o_s - o_t|$ is the opacity difference, and α, β are exponential decay parameters. These weights are then incorporated into a weighted least squares formulation for rigid transform estimation, such as:

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i (\mathbf{p}_i - \bar{\mathbf{p}}_s)(\mathbf{q}_i - \bar{\mathbf{q}}_s)^T,$$

Where $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_s$ and $\bar{\mathbf{q}}_t$ are the weighted centroids of source and target point sets, respectively. The algorithm terminates when the change in alignment error between consecutive iterations falls below a tolerance threshold τ_{tol} or when the maximum number of iterations $imax$ is reached.

Note that if we try to match two 3DGS built using different sets of sensors from different platforms, the centroids of matching Gaussian splats may result in no overlap, but still with a small Euclidean error because they belong to the same physical surface. In such situations, one can easily choose a strategy to decide which splats to keep. This fact appears in Figure 65, where the comparison of using different vector dimensionality based on different modalities (position, opacity or color) required normalization by their respective minimum Root Mean Square Errors for the sake of readability.


```

Algorithm 1 Multimodal 3DGS-ICP


---


Require:
  1. Source splats  $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{c}_s, o_s\}$ ,
  2. Target splats  $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathbf{p}_t, \mathbf{c}_t, o_t\}$ ,
  3. Parameters:  $\gamma, \delta, \alpha, \beta, \tau_{tot}, i_{max}$ 
  // Preprocessing
   $\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T} \leftarrow \text{filter\_by\_opacity}(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T})$ 
   $\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T} \leftarrow \text{filter\_statistical\_outliers}(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T})$ 
  // Initialization
   $T_{init} \leftarrow \text{FPFH\_RANSAC}(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{T})$  ▷ With scale estimation
   $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \mathcal{S} \times T_{init}$ 
  // Feature construction
   $\mathbf{p}_{min}, \mathbf{p}_{max} \leftarrow \text{compute\_bounds}(\mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{T})$ 
   $\mathbf{F}_s \leftarrow \text{build\_features}(\mathcal{S}, \gamma, \delta, \mathbf{p}_{min}, \mathbf{p}_{max})$ 
   $\mathbf{F}_t \leftarrow \text{build\_features}(\mathcal{T}, \gamma, \delta, \mathbf{p}_{min}, \mathbf{p}_{max})$ 
   $\text{kdtree}_t \leftarrow \text{build\_kdtree}(\mathbf{F}_t)$ 
  // Iterative refinement
   $T_{total} \leftarrow I_4, \text{error}_{prev} \leftarrow \infty$ 
  for  $i = 1$  to  $i_{max}$  do
    indices, distances  $\leftarrow \text{kdtree}_t.\text{query}(\mathbf{F}_s)$ 
     $\mathcal{M} \leftarrow \mathcal{T}[\text{indices}]$  ▷ Matched target splats
     $\mathbf{w} \leftarrow \text{compute\_weights}(\mathcal{S}.\mathbf{c}, \mathcal{M}.\mathbf{c}, \mathcal{S}.o, \mathcal{M}.o, \alpha, \beta)$ 
     $R, \mathbf{t} \leftarrow \text{weighted\_rigid\_transform}(\mathcal{S}.\mathbf{p}, \mathcal{M}.\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{w})$ 
     $\mathcal{S}.\mathbf{p} \leftarrow R.\mathcal{S}.\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{t}$ 
     $T_{total} \leftarrow \begin{bmatrix} R & \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{0}^T & 1 \end{bmatrix} T_{total}$ 
    error  $\leftarrow \text{RMSE}(\mathcal{S}.\mathbf{p}, \mathcal{M}.\mathbf{p})$ 
    if  $|\text{error}_{prev} - \text{error}| < \tau_{tot}$  then
      break
    end if
     $\text{error}_{prev} \leftarrow \text{error}$ 
     $\mathbf{F}_s \leftarrow \text{build\_features}(\mathcal{S}, \gamma, \delta, \mathbf{p}_{min}, \mathbf{p}_{max})$  ▷ Update source features
  end for
  return  $T_{total}, \text{error}$ 


---



```

Figure 63 Pseudocode for Multimodal 3DGS-ICP

3.3.4.4 Experimental evaluation

Analysis of 3DGS geometric features for matching

Initially, we explored if two 3DGS could be matched using geometric features extracted from individual splats. We investigated three eigenvalue-based shape descriptors: anisotropy, linearity, and planarity, derived from each splat’s covariance matrix to capture geometric variation, like linear structures and planar surfaces. A systematic parameter sweep tested all feature combinations across 50 registration trials per configuration, showing success rates of 34-70%, with no clear winner. Figure 64 presents the distribution of these features on a real dataset. These histograms reveal that most splats have high anisotropy, high linearity and low planarity (anisotropy: 87% are over 0.95, linearity: 46% are over 0.95, planarity: 52% are below 0.05). This narrow distribution fundamentally undermines discriminative capacity: when most splats are almost always elongated and anisotropic, matching of individual splats exploiting their geometric characteristics becomes ineffective.

Figure 64 Distribution of geometric features of 3DGS splats from a real-world dataset, resulting in narrow range concentrations, which limits discriminative capacity for registration

Additionally, we explored surface normals extracted directly from splat orientations, but these also proved unreliable, often failing to align with expected surface orientations (e.g., wall splats yielding random normal directions).

These results are of importance because if the splat geometric representation is not accurately codifying the physical geometry of the scene, we will not be able to compare two splats belonging to 3DGS generated using different sensors. These findings motivated our shift toward exploiting the photometric properties (color and opacity) for multi-robot map alignment, and suggests that 3DGS splat representations are optimized for differentiable rendering than geometric accuracy, excelling at photorealistic rendering while their primitives lack geometric faithfulness.

Analysis of 3DGS photometric features for matching

The assessment of our 3DGS-ICP includes a convergence rate analysis, where combinations of our feature vectors are compared. To evaluate the robustness to outliers, we also show a comparison in the presence of (controlled) noise. All experiments were conducted using CPU-based processing with Intel Core i7-7700K 4.20GHz and Python implementations. The experimental setup employed calibrated sensors with both intrinsic and extrinsic parameters determined through standard calibration procedures. Intrinsic camera parameters were obtained using chessboard-based calibration, while extrinsic transformations between sensors were established through simultaneous data capture and correspondence-based estimation. This calibration ensures accurate spatial alignment between multi-modal sensor data throughout the evaluation process. We evaluated the convergence behavior of our multi-modal 3DGS-ICP variants on a filtered real-world 3DGS map. The dataset consists of approximately 150,000 splats, remaining after voxel downsampling and statistical outlier removal. For each configuration, no additional noise was applied, and the reported results reported in represent averages over 10 independent runs.

Figure 65 shows the convergence curves for vector representations using different features to highlight the importance of each. Note that, for the sake of clarity, each configuration has been shifted by its final stable Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) so that all trajectories end at zero, enabling a clear visual comparison of their relative convergence rates. However, as reported in Table 17, the true final RMSE values are nonzero. This occurs because incorporating additional features such as color and opacity increases the Euclidean distances between matched feature vectors, even when geometric alignment error is negligible. Notably, the Color+Opacity configuration required only 8 iterations and 1.29 seconds to converge, compared to 44 iterations and 4.18 seconds for geometry alone. While the convergence time is of no importance (as it would depend on the particular computation power) and all configurations achieved successful alignment, the inclusion of photometric cues (color and opacity) consistently accelerated convergence.

Table 17 Performance metrics averaged over 10 runs for 3DGS-ICP feature vector configurations

Configuration	Final RMSE	Iterations	Time (s)
No Color, No Opacity	0.004	44	4.18
Opacity Only	0.036	17	1.92
Color Only	0.116	11	1.57
Color + Opacity	0.181	8	1.29

Figure 65 3DGS-ICP convergence curves for different feature vector configurations. Note how matching vectors without color or opacity features correspond to using a traditional ICP

To evaluate the robustness of the proposed multimodal 3DGS-ICP algorithm, we conducted systematic noise injection experiments on a real-world 3DGS map containing approximately 10,000 splats, after filtering and voxel downsampling. Gaussian noise with identical standard deviation was applied independently to each feature with the following ranges: Cartesian coordinates ($[-3.0, 3.0]$), colors ($[0.0, 1.0]$), and opacity ($[0.9021, 1.0]$). The noisy 3DGS was transformed using the known ground truth transformation, with registration success defined by translation error $\leq 0.15\text{m}$ and rotation error ≤ 3.0 degrees. We selected these values based on expert judgment and to highlight cases where the resulting transformation deviated notably. Success rates were computed over 25 trials for each feature combination. Results in Figure 66 demonstrate that feature richness directly correlates with noise robustness. Clearly, adding color and opacity to the feature vectors achieves superior performance, maintaining a really high success rate through all the evaluated noises. This robustness stems from direct exploitation of 3D Gaussian properties rather than reliance on correspondence-based matching that may degrade under noise. For instance, this is the case of TEASER++ [Yang20], which requires to setting in advance the level of noise present in the data or, otherwise, significantly degrades its registration performance.

Figure 66 Performance evaluation of 3DGS-ICP under additive Gaussian noise for all vector features

Conclusions of the 3DGS-ICP algorithm

Our analysis demonstrates that Gaussian Splats cannot be exploited in terms of their geometry as they do not represent physical features, with splats exhibiting consistently elongated and anisotropic properties that undermine geometric feature matching of individual splats. This finding motivated our

pipeline’s focus on photometric properties: we developed strategies for the generation of scale-normalized and filtered 3DGS across heterogeneous sensing robots, and introduced an ICP variant that exploits 3DGS color and opacity properties to improve registration performance. Through experimentation we validated the robustness of our algorithm, showing faster convergence and improved noise tolerance than traditional point-to-point ICP.

As an example, a resulting aerial-ground alignment process is presented in Figure 67 where, for the sake of clarity, we show all 3DGS maps in the form of point clouds of splat centroids. The fused map demonstrates visually consistent registration and strong spatial correspondence across the two modalities, highlighting the ability of our method to reliably integrate heterogeneous sensor data into a unified 3D reconstruction, even in scenarios with significant viewpoint and coverage differences. **For these experiments, we leveraged the hand-held LiDAR device described above, mimicking a ground robot.**

Our findings open several promising directions for future research. A natural next step is the development of semantic-aware splat fusion, where object- or region-level information could be embedded into the Gaussian representation to support higher-level tasks such as scene understanding and semantic SLAM. Finally, large-scale deployments in complex and dynamic environments remain an open challenge: extending the proposed framework to handle dynamic obstacles, and long-term consistency across fleets of robots will be critical for real-world applications.

Figure 67 Aerial and ground multi-robot 3DGS mapping using our 3DGS-ICP method with a real-world dataset. Each point cloud represents the respective 3DGS splat centroids

3.4 Non-visual cues integration

In addition to LiDAR and vision-based perception, the TRIFFID UGV leverages non-visual sensor cues to enrich its environmental understanding and to extend the 3D semantic map with contextual layers not captured by geometry alone. The legged robot is equipped with an Arduino Nicla Sense ME, a compact multi-modal sensing module that provides continuous measurements of environmental properties such as temperature, humidity, air pressure, and air-quality indicators (VOC, gas concentration). These data sources are particularly relevant in search-and-rescue and degraded-environment scenarios, where non-visual cues help characterize local conditions that are not directly observable in point-cloud geometry.

The Nicla readings are integrated into the UGV’s perception pipeline by representing each measurement as a point in a dedicated point cloud, spatially anchored using the robot’s current pose provided by the SLAM system. This ensures that all non-visual sensor cues are automatically georeferenced and can be

fused into the global semantic 3DGS (Gaussian Splatting) map maintained at the ground station. Each measurement point carries its corresponding sensor metadata (e.g., temperature, humidity level, air-quality index), allowing the ground station to augment the 3D representation with environmental attributes and to visualize spatiotemporal patterns across the operational area.

In parallel, the UGV performs continuous monitoring of wireless communication quality. Metrics such as signal strength, packet success ratio, and link stability are periodically recorded and also mapped into the 3D reference frame as geolocated points. This enables the creation of a communications-health layer within the same 3D semantic map, allowing operators to visualize areas of weak connectivity, communication dropouts, or high latency. These cues are essential for mission supervision, replanning, and operator safety, as poor communication zones can hinder teleoperation, remote intervention, or high-bandwidth data transfer.

All sensor readings (e.g., the Nicla environmental cues, communications-health measurements, or their associated metadata) are transmitted using ROS2 as the system's middleware. Dedicated ROS2 topics allow the UGV to publish these data streams to the ground station, where they are stored, visualized, and integrated into the 3DGS semantic map. ROS2's built-in QoS (Quality-of-Service) settings ensure the appropriate levels of reliability depending on the message type: non-critical high-frequency cues may use best-effort delivery, while communication-health events or alerts use reliable channels to guarantee notification.

Together, these non-visual cues provide a complementary layer of situational awareness beyond geometric perception. By embedding environmental sensor data and communication quality into the global 3D representation, the TRIFFID system offers operators a more complete understanding of environmental conditions, infrastructure limitations, and operational risks, ultimately supporting safer mission execution and more informed decision-making.

3.5 Environmental sound analysis and event detection

Acoustic sensing constitutes a critical sensing modality in disaster response challenging operational environments. Unlike optical or thermal signals, sound waves exhibit strong diffraction properties, enabling them to propagate efficiently through dense debris, around substantial obstacles, and across complex, non-line-of-sight structural layouts. This characteristic makes acoustic sensing uniquely suited for detecting events and human presence in collapsed or visually obstructed environments, where autonomous navigation and situational assessment depend on multi-modal robustness.

Acoustic intelligence for emergency response represents a paradigm shift from basic sound capture to sophisticated pattern analysis and event classification, providing actionable insights. At its core, this field utilizes Acoustic Event Detection (AED) and localization to classify specific sound patterns indicative of critical situations. These include impulsive events such as explosions, glass breaks, structural failures, and mechanical impacts, which are frequently precursors to secondary collapses or evolving hazards. Their early identification supports real-time risk assessment and directly informs path planning, safety management, and mission adaptation for FRs. Furthermore, acoustic sensors can capture subtle but meaningful cues, such as distant screams, tapping, whistling, or low-Signal-to-Noise Ratio (low-SNR) distress signals, that may not be observable through camera-based perception. This capability offers a vital, non-visual mechanism for victim localization and triage under degraded and low-visibility conditions.

Sound Event Detection (SED) is a machine learning (ML) task focused on identifying the presence of specific sound events within an audio stream and determining their precise temporal boundaries (onset and offset times).

In the context of TRIFFID, SED supports multiple functionalities. First, detected acoustic events enrich the semantic 3D area map by providing temporally anchored environmental indicators that can signal hazardous conditions or human presence. Second, SED serves as an auxiliary channel for navigation and safety management. For example, identifying distant impacts or collapsing debris can guide UGV behavior. Overall, SED provides input to downstream multimodal fusion, complementing visual and non-visual sensor data and informing mission planning and robot behavior adaptation under WP3.

The current status of Sound Event Detection developments in the context of the TRIFFID project is documented in section 4.5.3 “Triffid Sound/Speech Analysis Engine”.

3.5.1 Relevant public audio datasets

Open datasets for environmental and urban sound analysis vary widely in scale, annotation quality, and intended use. In general, these datasets differ along several axes:

- clip-level vs. event-level annotation (weak vs. strong labels),
- monophonic vs. polyphonic acoustic scenes,
- curated vs. web-crawled source material,
- domain specificity vs. general-purpose taxonomies

Small, balanced datasets are typically used for benchmarking classification models, whereas large-scale or strongly annotated datasets support training of more robust and temporally precise systems for sound event detection and scene analysis.

Table 18 Comparison of audio datasets

No	Dataset	Year	Source	Use Case	No. Classes	No. Samples	Annotation Type
1	UrbanSound8K [Salomon14]	2014	Freesound	Urban noise monitoring	10	1,302	Timestamps + Saliency
2	ESC-50 [Piczak15]	2015	Freesound	General	50	2,000	Clip-level
3	AudioSet [Gemmeke17]	2017	YouTube	Large-scale recognition	632	1.7M+	Clip-level
4	AudioSet-Strong [Hershey21]	2021	YouTube	Temporal precision/SED	632	~85,000	Timestamps

UrbanSound8K [Salomon14] was developed to address the lack of detailed taxonomies for urban soundscapes. Its creation was guided by three strict requirements: the taxonomy had to factor in previous research, it needed to be granular enough to distinguish low-level sources (e.g., differentiating "jackhammer" from general "construction"), and it prioritized sounds relevant to urban noise monitoring.

Based on this, the authors defined four top-level groups, namely human, nature, mechanical, and music, and selected 10 specific low-level classes for the dataset: air conditioner, car horn, children playing,

dog bark, drilling, engine idling, gunshot, jackhammer, siren, and street music. This selection was limited to 10 classes to ensure manageable manual annotation efforts while providing a strong starting point for urban research.

The data was sourced from Freesound. The curation process involved a rigorous manual inspection where 60 hours of candidate audio were filtered down to 1,302 field recordings (27 hours) containing verified events. Using Audacity, annotators labeled the start and end times of every occurrence, adding salience descriptions (foreground vs. background). The resulting corpus contains 18.5 hours of labeled occurrences, capturing the complex temporal structure of urban environments.

ESC-50 [Piczak15] dataset was introduced to provide a standard benchmark for general environmental sound classification. It comprises 2,000 labeled recordings strictly balanced across 50 classes, with 40 clips per class. These classes are organized into five loosely defined categories: animal sounds, natural soundscapes/water, non-speech human sounds, interior/domestic sounds, and exterior/urban noises. The dataset offers exposure to a wide spectrum of acoustic events, ranging from common sources like dog barking to distinct events like glass breaking and nuanced classes such as distinguishing between helicopter and airplane noise. A known limitation is the restricted number of clips per class, a trade-off made to maintain strict class balance despite the high cost of manual annotation and the scarcity of exotic sound events.

AudioSet [Gemmeke17] was created to provide a dataset and ontology of audio events at an "ImageNet-like" scale. The goal was to move beyond flat lists of labels by structuring events into a hierarchical abstraction layer, allowing classifiers to handle ambiguity by backing off to general parent categories (e.g., recognizing "dog" when "bark" is ambiguous).

The resulting ontology contains 632 categories arranged in a hierarchy up to 6 levels. The dataset consists of over 1.7 million 10-second YouTube segments. To make labeling this volume feasible, the authors employed a heuristic candidate generation process, where videos were pre-selected based on metadata, anchor text, and user engagement signals (e.g., view counts >1,000), and then ranked by matching keywords against the ontology. These candidates were sent to human raters who performed a 3-way majority vote ("present," "not present," "unsure") for specific labels. This methodology allowed for the creation of a massive, general-purpose resource covering the distinctions made by a typical listener.

However, the original AudioSet relied on "weak" labels (tags applied to 10-second clips without specific timestamps) which limits the ability to train detection models or handle "missing positives" where unannotated events occur in the background. To address this, AudioSet-Strong [Hershey21] was introduced to reveal the importance of temporal precision. The authors collected precise timestamps (approx. 0.1-second resolution) for a subset of the data, including all 18,000 evaluation clips and a training subset of 67,000 clips. The subset selection aimed for 250 examples per class, though frequent label co-occurrence meant common classes like Speech and Music appear more frequently. This "strong" subset resolves the ambiguity of weak labels by confirming both the presence and the exact temporal extent of sound events.

Figure 68 Comparison of an audio clip's spectrogram (top), original AudioSet 10-s labels (blue = present, yellow = confirmed absent), temporally strong labels from AudioSet-Strong, and projected 0.96-s frame-level labels with complementary negatives used for evaluation

3.5.2 Review of state-of-the-art methods

Early deep-learning-based SED systems were dominated by CNNs. These models utilize 2D convolutions to extract local time-frequency features from log-Mel spectrograms [Chen17]. To better model the temporal evolution of sounds (e.g., the fading tail of an alarm), the field eventually shifted toward CRNNs [Adavanne17]. These models typically use a CNN for feature extraction followed by recurrent layers (e.g., bidirectional Gated Recurrent Units or Long Short-Term Memorys (LSTMs)) to aggregate long-range context. While effective, the recurrent component introduces training bottlenecks due to its sequential nature.

The current SOTA accuracy is dominated by attention-based models like AST. AST employs a ViT backbone to process the 2D spectrogram. The input spectrogram is discretized into a sequence of overlapping patches, which converts the continuous spectro-temporal signal into a sequence of embeddings. Because the standard self-attention mechanism is permutation-invariant (treating input as a set rather than a sequence), learnable positional embeddings are added to the patch sequence to retain the temporal and frequency structure of the signal (Figure 69). Additionally, AST authors proposed an approach for transferring knowledge from the ViT pretrained on ImageNet [Deng09] to AST (cross-domain transfer learning), which significantly improved SED performance.

Figure 69 The AST architecture

A major bottleneck in SED is the scarcity of strongly labeled data. To mitigate dependency on labeled data, recent work has introduced the SSAST [Gong22]. Unlike previous SED frameworks that focus primarily on temporal predictive coding, SSAST employs a masked spectrogram patch modeling objective. In this framework, a significant portion of the spectrogram patches are randomly masked, and the model is trained with a joint objective: a) Generative Reconstruction: Minimizing the MSE between the predicted and original values of the masked patches and b) Discriminative Classification: Using Information Noise-Contrastive Estimation (InfoNCE) loss to identify the correct patch content from negative samples. This approach is conceptually parallel to the Masked Language Modeling (MLM) used in LLMs such as BERT. Just as BERT [Devlin19] randomly masks linguistic tokens and learns to predict the original word based on bidirectional context, SSAST masks rectangular patches of the audio spectrogram and learns to reconstruct them. By forcing the model to reconstruct and classify masked regions based on context, SSAST learns rich, transferrable representations of both frequency and temporal structures without human annotation. This approach has been shown to outperform supervised pretraining baselines on benchmarks.

SSAST introduces also Cluster Factor C , which dictates to control how masked patches cluster. Instead of masking patches individually and uniformly, the masking strategy groups patches into clusters of size C . Larger Cluster Factor leads to contiguous blocks of the spectrogram being masked, which removes significant local signals, forcing the model to rely on global spectrogram structures and long-range dependencies to infer the missing content. On the contrary, smaller Cluster Factor masks scattered, isolated patches, which encourages the model to learn local structures, such as textures and immediate spectro-temporal transitions. By randomizing the cluster factor during training, SSAST robustly captures both the fine-grained spectral details and the high-level event semantics required for complex SED tasks (Figure 70).

Figure 70 Illustration of the patch-level masking with different cluster factor C but same total masking area

Beyond structural modeling, recent advancements leverage natural language to provide semantic supervision. CLAP [Elizalde23] addresses the limitation of fixed-label taxonomies by learning a joint embedding space for audio and text. CLAP's architecture consists of dual encoders: a CNN-based audio encoder and a text encoder. The model is trained using a symmetric contrastive loss on large-scale pairs of audio and natural language descriptions, maximizing the cosine similarity between matched audio-text pairs while minimizing it for unmatched ones. This paradigm enables zero-shot SED, where the model can detect or classify sound events based on arbitrary textual prompts (e.g., "the sound of glass breaking") without needing explicit training examples for those specific classes (Figure 71). This aligns the acoustic representation with natural language semantics rather than rigid class indices.

Most recently, the field is moving toward unified Audio-LLMs capable of universal audio understanding. Qwen-Audio [Chu23] represents a paradigm shift where SED is treated as a generation task within a multitask framework. The model's architecture fundamentally bridges the gap between acoustic perception and textual reasoning by connecting a robust audio directly to an LLM, specifically Qwen-7B. Also, while traditional models are often constrained to specific tasks or audio types, Qwen-Audio addresses this limitation by scaling up audio-language pre-training to cover over 30 tasks and diverse audio types, including human speech, natural sounds, and music.

However, such scaling introduces "one-to-many interference", which refers to a conflict that arises during multi-task co-training when different datasets provide inconsistent or varying textual labels for similar types of audio inputs. In a unified training setup, the model might encounter similar audio signals that are associated with completely different target outputs depending on the dataset's specific objective. To address this, Qwen-Audio introduces a novel hierarchical tagging framework. Instead of standard static prompts, the model conditions the decoder on a structured sequence of special tokens that explicitly define the task hierarchy. This sequence begins with a Transcription Tag (`<start_of_analysis>`) to signal the input modality, followed by an Audio Language Tag to define the source language, and a Task Tag (e.g., `<caption>`, `<detect>`) to specify the generation objective. This structure allows the model to share knowledge across similar tasks (like transcription and captioning) while preventing interference between distinct objectives.

Crucially for SED, Qwen-Audio incorporates a specialized training objective termed Speech Recognition with Word-level Timestamps (SRWT). Unlike standard transcription which outputs a continuous stream of text, SRWT forces the model to predict precise onset and offset timestamps

interleaved directly with the text tokens. By learning to align specific acoustic segments with semantic labels at a fine-grained level, the model implicitly acquires strong grounding capabilities. This allows it to perform grounding-based audio question answering, such as identifying the exact time intervals of specific sound events (e.g., "the sound of glass breaking starts at 2.5s and ends at 3.1s"), achieving SOTA performance on grounding and detection benchmarks without the need for task-specific classification heads or fine-tuning.

Figure 71 CLAP audio-text contrastive learning (left) and zero-shot classification (right)

3.6 Synthetic soundscape generation

Open-source datasets commonly used in environmental sound analysis (e.g., for sound event detection, acoustic scene classification, or anomalous sound detection) and those used in HRI research (section 4.5.1.3) do not adequately represent the acoustic and semantic characteristics of post-disaster emergency response scenarios.

More specifically, existing environmental audio datasets fail to capture sound events characteristic of damaged or unstable infrastructure, heavy rescue machinery, alarms, and human distress, as well as the realistic overlap of hazard cues with background noise typical of disaster environments. Likewise, HRI datasets (Keyword Spotting or SPLU/ Natural Language Understanding (NLU)) lack semantic intents, operational terminology, or communication patterns used by FRs.

To address these limitations, we have developed a parametric synthetic data generation pipeline that employs both stochastic and deterministic sequencing to construct strongly labeled, polyphonic soundscapes that aim to capture the acoustic complexity of disaster sites.

3.6.1 Acoustic event library creation

We established a library of foreground and background sound events through a hybrid curation strategy that prioritizes signal purity and semantic relevance.

To extract high-quality samples, we leveraged the strongly annotated subset of AudioSet, which provides precise temporal boundaries for sound events. We implemented a custom retrieval algorithm to assess the "spectral purity" of potential clips. For a target event class of interest, the system analyses the strong labels to calculate the IoU with concurrent events. Candidates were selected based on a) Isolation: Events exhibiting minimal overlap with unrelated classes and b) semantic compatibility: Events overlapping only with contextually consistent classes (e.g., an Explosion event overlapping with Fire is retained, whereas one overlapping with Domestic Music is discarded).

For hazard-specific categories absent from public datasets, such as specific material impacts, structural groans, or mechanical failures, we utilized modern generative audio models. Using the ElevenLabs¹² audio generation Application Programming Interface (API), we generated samples of rare events using textual prompts.

Speech data generation for human-robot interaction

To construct a speech corpus aligned with verbal HRI requirements, we utilized ElevenLabs neural voice synthesis to generate a diverse set of utterances across varying prosodies, which is divided into two operational categories:

- Human-to-Robot (H2R) Command Speech: Short, imperative operational commands used by FRs to control UGVs (e.g., "Stop," "Forward," "Measure vitals," "Activate siren") and
- Robot-to-Human (R2H) Assessment Prompts: Structured dialogue prompts intended for victim assessment, including health queries, safety instructions, and consent requests. This content supports semantic labeling for downstream intent classification.

3.6.2 Parametric soundscape synthesis pipeline

To assemble these isolated assets into realistic acoustic scenes, we developed a custom Python framework built upon the Scaper soundscape synthesis library. This framework introduces advanced logic for controlling event relationships.

- Stochastic co-occurrence generation: This mode simulates complex acoustic contexts by sampling events based on probabilistic dependencies defined in a JSON configuration schema. Unlike random sampling, this approach models the causal or environmental relationships between sound sources. Rules are defined by conditional probabilities, relative timing windows, and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) deltas.
- Choreography-based generation: For scenarios requiring rigorous validation of temporal reasoning, the pipeline supports a deterministic "choreography" mode. This allows for the explicit specification of onset times, durations, and foreground/background layering, facilitating the creation of "gold-standard" test sets where specific edge cases (e.g., speech partially masked by a specific hazard alarm) can be systematically evaluated.

3.6.3 Experimental evaluation

3.6.3.1 Evaluation metrics

For evaluating SED we selected Top-5 Accuracy, which is an evaluation metric for multi-class classification that measures the proportion of samples for which the true label appears among the model's five highest-scoring predicted classes. The intuition behind this decision is that during Sound Event Detection inference, we consider present the 5 most probable predicted classes (that surpass a pre-defined threshold).

Similarly, for Command Detection evaluation we selected Average Word Accuracy, which measures the mean proportion of correctly recognized words across commands, averaged over all samples.

3.6.3.2 Results for the sound event detection task

¹² <https://elevenlabs.io/>

Experimental setup

In close collaboration with FR stakeholders of TRIFFID consortium, a closed vocabulary of operational commands was defined and structured into functional categories covering navigation, victim interaction, health assessment, sensor activation, documentation, consent handling, reporting, warnings, and monitoring (Table 19). In total, 33 distinct commands were specified, representing short, imperative utterances characteristic of time-critical HRI in emergency response scenarios.

Table 19 Operational spoken command set used for synthetic speech generation

SN	Command
NAVIGATIONAL	
A1	Stop
A2	Forward/Backward
A3	Left/Right
A4	Hold position
A5	Follow me
A6	Go to zone A
A7	Go to point B
A8	Emergency
A9	I need help
A10	Evacuate
A11	Lost connection
A12	Mission finish
VICTIM INTERACTION	
A13	Start victim check
A14	Check victim
HEALTH ASSESSMENT	
A15	Start healthcheck
A16	Healthcheck on
VITAL SIGNS/SENSOR TASKS	
A17	Measure vitals
A18	Vital scan
A19	Measure heart rate
A20	Measure breathing
A21	Thermal scan
DOCUMENTATION	
A22	Take photo
A23	Take thermal
A24	Record video/audio
CONSENT	
A25	Ask touch permission
REPORTING & LOCATION	
A26	Mark location
A27	Send report
A28	Update status
WARNINGS & SIGNALS	
A30	Activate siren
A31	Alert operator
MONITORING	
A32	Repeat status
A33	Monitoring on/off

To generate speech material aligned with these requirements, all commands were synthesized employing two distinct English-speaking first-responder personas: one male and one female (FR-MALE-EN, FR-FEMALE-EN). Both voices were configured using prompts that explicitly target operational realism, emphasizing loud, breathy, and clipped delivery intended to remain comprehensible under high ambient noise and stress.

For each command-voice combination, ten distinct soundscapes were generated, resulting in a total of 640 labeled samples (32 commands \times 2 voices \times 10 soundscapes). Foreground sound events were sampled from curated AudioSet classes, informed by the hierarchical taxonomy proposed by Pham et al. for post-disaster acoustic scenes. For background sound events, we used three sound events, namely wind, outdoor-crowd and white-noise.

In this initial dataset version and the corresponding preliminary benchmarking of the Sound/Speech Engine (section 4.5.3), synthetically generated non-speech sound effects were deliberately excluded. Although extensive experimentation was conducted with modern generative audio models to produce rare, domain-specific hazard sounds (e.g., structural creaks, material-specific impacts, mechanical failures), the generated outputs did not meet the realism requirements necessary for reliable model evaluation. Two prompting strategies were explored. The first employed scene-based, descriptive prompts that embed sound events within a broader post-earthquake context, implicitly combining multiple sound sources and background conditions (e.g. “An outdoor urban area after an earthquake, with damaged structures producing intermittent debris sounds”). The second strategy adopted a causality-driven, event-centric formulation, where prompts explicitly describe a single physical sound source and action, optionally qualified by coarse intensity and environment (indoor/outdoor), while omitting inferred acoustic attributes (e.g. “Moderate sound of metal rubble shifting, outdoors”).

Experimental results

The results, summarized in Table 20 and

Table 21, provide a baseline evaluation of command detection and sound event detection performance.

Table 20 Top-5 accuracy for SED on the preliminary version of synthetic soundscapes dataset

Category	Top-5 accuracy
Crying/sobbing	82.47%
Driving	84.12%
Engine	78.86%
Glass	60.39%
Heavy equipment	82.91%
Tools	71.58%
Metal	93.73%
Plastic	84.19%
Siren	96.07%
Safety alarm	85.28%

Table 21 Average word accuracy per command category for command detection task on the preliminary version of synthetic soundscapes dataset

Category	Average word accuracy
Navigation	80.60%
Victim interaction	89.80%
Health assessment	67.70%
Vital signs/Sensor tasks	73.70%
Documentation	75.10%
Consent	78.40%
Reporting & location	67.80%
Warnings & signals monitoring	93.20%

The preliminary results presented here serve as a baseline and should not be considered conclusive indicators of system performance. At this stage of development, the evaluation is constrained by the preliminary nature of the synthetic dataset, which was designed to validate the data generation methodology rather than to support fine-grained performance analysis. In addition, given the fully synthetic nature of the dataset, the built-in digital signal processing (DSP) capabilities of the deployed sound sensor (section 4.5.3.1), especially audio denoising and speech enhancement, could not be utilized.

Building on these preliminary outcomes, several next steps are planned. Further experimentation with generative audio models will be conducted. Few-shot metric learning approaches, such as Prototypical Networks [Snell17], will be employed to enable robust discrimination of rare, domain-specific sound events with very limited labeled data, particularly for classes absent from large-scale open datasets such as AudioSet. Pre-processing techniques will be implemented, specifically Audio Source Separation, to create a higher-quality pool of foreground and background sound events. The quality of these synthetic outputs will be validated using realism metrics (e.g. Fréchet Audio Distance [Kilgour18]). The spoken command corpus will be localized into the native languages of all TRIFFID end users to support multilingual HRI evaluation. The dataset will be systematically extended into distinct, use-case-specific releases, covering all TRIFFID use-cases: earthquake, flood, and fire, each with tailored sound event distributions reflecting the operational characteristics of the corresponding disaster context.

Finally, the performance of the TRIFFID Sound/Speech Engine and its individual components will be systematically assessed via exhaustive benchmarking and ablation studies.

4 Human robot interaction and behavior analysis

4.1 Relevant public datasets

There are no datasets for gesture-based HRI in post-disaster scenarios. However, there are a few for guiding drones or other robots via hand signals, which could be considered relevant to the TRIFFID use cases. In particular, MD-UHGRD [Xu24] and LRHG [Zhou21A] were proposed for drone navigation, with a recognition range up to 10m and 7m, respectively. URGR [Bamani24] contains gestures captured at a distance of up to 25m for guiding UGVs. AUTH [Patrona21], UAV [Perera18] and NATOPS [Song11] comprise dynamic coarse-grained gestures for aircraft handling (including UAVs). Manipulating construction machinery through gestures has also been investigated [Wang 21]. Only LRHG and NATOPS are publicly available. These datasets are shown in Table 22.

Table 22 Academic datasets for gesture-based AMRs control

Name	Year	Kind	Modality	Source	Gestures	Samples	Signers	Environment
MD-UHGRD	2024	Static	RGB	UAV	19	20,000	5	-
URGR	2024	Static	RGB	UGV	5	347,483	16	Indoor & outdoor
LRHG	2021	Static	RGB	UAV	10	4,320	8	Indoor
AUTH UAV GESTURE	2021	Dynamic	Video RGB	UAV	6	4,930	58	Indoor & outdoor
[CONSTRUCTION]	2021	Dynamic	Video RGBD	Machinery	11	364	-	Indoor & outdoor
UAV GESTURE	2019	Dynamic	Video RGB	UAV	13	119	8	Outdoor
NATOPS	2011	Dynamic	Video RGBD	UAV	24	9,600	20	Indoor

For static HGR, the lightweight version of HAGRID [Kapitanov24], a large-scale dataset for gesture-based HCI, and the LRHG [Zhou21A], a smaller dataset for controlling UAVs via hand gesture detection, were adopted. The HAGRID dataset includes roughly 550K RGB gesture samples in total that correspond to 18 classes and performed by 37,583 distinct subjects in a distance up to 4 meters. These characteristics make HAGRID a dataset with high diversity, thus the methods trained on it gain the necessary generalization ability that guarantees sufficient accuracy in real-world scenarios. Furthermore, this dataset could be adopted for transfer learning. Its lightweight version contains images of lower resolution, which does not affect the experimental results, as the models perform resize before processing an image. The LRHG dataset is a small dataset compared with HAGRID, designed for gesture-based UAV guidance and containing only 4320 images for 10 classes in total, performed by 8 participants in indoor environments. The dataset has been captured indoors and the perception angle is not the one that corresponds to a camera mounted on an UAV, thus it can not be considered a sufficient solution for this application scenario. Unfortunately, there are not any other public datasets available for static gesture-based AMRs control, and even though we contacted authors of [Bamani24], we failed

to gain access to their dataset (for UGV guidance). Thus, LRHG was the only available dataset for this purpose. The LRHG was originally proposed for hand gesture detection (that is, a bounding box of the hand is also provided accompanying the gesture class), but we adopted for hand gesture classification (recognition), regarding that the position of the hand is not a very important information for this task. The characteristics of other datasets for static HGR that are publicly available are shown in Table 23. Considering their small size, we have not conducted any experiments with them, as the amount of data is insufficient to train an accurate deep learning method.

Table 23 Publicly available datasets for static HGR

Dataset	No. Classes	No. Samples	No. Subjects	Annotation type	Modality	Range	Domain
OUHANDS	10	3,000	23	Masks, BBs, Keypoints	RGB-D	Short	HCI
HGR1	27	899	12	Masks	RGB	Short	General
NUSI	10	240	-	-	RGB	Short	General
NUSII	10	2,000	40	-	RGB	Short	General
LRHG	10	4,320	8	BBs	RGB	Long	HRI
HaGRID	18	554,800	37,583	BBs	RGB	Short	HCI

The only publicly available dataset for dynamic HGR near to the TRIFFID needs is the NATOPS [Song11]. However, as mentioned earlier, it doesn't provide temporal boundaries of the gestures, as a result it cannot be used for video classification. Thus, experiments on public benchmarks, either proposed for HCI or general-purpose, were conducted. Sign language datasets weren't selected, being strongly irrelevant to the TRIFFID purposes. In particular, IPN-Hand [Benitez-Garcia21], proposed for appearance-based dynamic isolated & continuous gesture recognition, and SHREC2017 [De Smedt17], a general-purpose pose-based dataset, were examined in order to cover a large part of the spectrum of (Isolated Dynamic Hand Gesture Recognition) IDHGR. The Jester [Materzynska19], a large-scale dataset usually leveraged for pretraining, was not selected, because we couldn't find the entire dataset (only a subset was available on the internet). The isolated version of the IPN-Hand was proposed for gesture-based HCI in short distance and consists of 4218 instances of 13 classes, performed by 50 subjects. It provides RGB and OF frames as well as segmentation masks. SHREC17 provides pose and depth modalities, containing 2800 samples performed by 28 subjects. The number of classes is 18 or 28, depending on the evaluation protocol.

4.2 Hand gesture dataset creation

As the aforementioned datasets for gesture-based HRI are not publicly available or are inadequate as they don't contain the commands needed by the FRs (based on the requirements elicitation), we have proceeded with the definition of a new list of gestures (mapped to corresponding UGV commands) and the collection of a relevant dataset.

4.2.1 Semantic corpus definition

The human gestures list and the corresponding commands were iteratively redefined based on the end users' feedback. This list consists of either custom hand signals or adopted existing ones, mainly used by task forces and firefighters. Primarily, gestures used by Chemical, Radiological, Biological, Nuclear

(CRBN) personnel of the HFC¹³ and army visual signals¹⁴ were considered. Dynamic gestures included in these resources were rejected or modified to static ones, aiming to maintain the model’s computational cost relatively small. Gestures irrelevant to the TRIFFID purposes were also discarded or transformed accordingly. For example, the CRBN “Danger - Evacuate” and the military “Come to me” were replaced by the proposed “Evacuate the area” and “Come to me” static gestures, shown below, which are more discriminable. The final corpus can be found in Table 24.

Table 24 Final corpus including navigational, general-purpose, and tool-and equipment-related commands

SN	Command	Description	Image
NAVIGATIONAL			
G1	Come to me	Indicating the head with both hands. The robot approaches the FR who performs the gesture (i.e., the signer).	
G2	Ok to go	Thumbs up with both hands at the height of the head. The robot continues its normal path.	
G3	Freeze/Stop	Fist at head level, performed with either the left or right hand. The robot stops moving.	
G4	Move away from here	"Spreading" the hands. The robot moves away from its current position (e.g., it was obstructing the passage of vehicles).	
GENERAL PURPOSE			

¹³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cIgg_hdKSS4

¹⁴ https://rdl.train.army.mil/catalog-ws/view/100.ATSC/0EE94275-C9B1-4C75-B9F3-CBB07D4251A4-1490024166167/tc3_21x60.pdf

G5	Emergency situation	Crossing hands at head or chest level. Performed to indicate that an emergency situation has occurred (e.g., a FR has been trapped in debris).	
G6	I need help	Hands raised. The FR calls for support (e.g., he/she cannot extinguish the fire alone, so additional FR will come to help).	
G7	Evacuate the area	Hands stretched at head level with thumbs down. The robot leaves the area due to immediate danger (e.g., a tank full of flammable liquid is about to explode).	
G8	I lost connection	Covering the ears with both hands, indicating that the FR is facing communication issues (e.g., wireless communication is not working).	
G9	Operation finished	Hands raised with palms crossed above the head. The operation has finished, so the robot returns to the ground station.	
TOOLS & EQUIPMENT			
G10	Fetch a shovel	Pretending to dig the ground. The robot fetches a shovel.	
G11	Fetch an axe	Pretending to cut something. The robot fetches an axe.	

G12	Fetch a gas mask	Mimicking gas mask filters with the hands. The robot fetches a gas mask.	
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4.2.2 Data collection procedure

The samples were captured in 3 different scenes, two indoors and one outdoors. The participants were asked to perform each of the aforementioned 12 gestures once at 6 or 7 different distances (approximately from 1 to 7 meters), following LRHG [Zhou21A], in order to make the model able to recognize commands at various distances. RGB and Depth frames were gathered by two Intel RealSense cameras, at a resolution of 640x480 for both modalities, and saved in PNG format. These two cameras were positioned at two different heights, with an arbitrary perception angle, aiming to enhance robustness in viewpoint variability. Partially occluded samples were also considered, regarding related edge cases of the in-the-wild deployment. Indicative samples are shown in Figure 72.

Figure 72 A sample consists of two RGB frames from different viewpoints with aligned depth maps, where each gesture is repeated at 6-7 distances per signer

The data curation was facilitated by a script written in Python, which was showing sequentially the gesture that the subject should perform and automatically capture the frames after a timelapse. CSV files were used to keep track of the process, saving the status of each sample (whether it has been captured or not) and necessary information (e.g. distance from the camera, paths to RGBD frames).

4.2.3 Dataset statistics

Six subjects in total took place in the dataset curation, after signing a related data privacy protection document. Out of them, only one (the subject “s3”) is a woman. We are looking forward to overcoming this gender imbalance by increasing the number of female participants in a future version of the dataset.

Subjects 4 and 5 have performed 240 gestures, resulting in 480 RGB-D pairs (as they were captured by two cameras). The rest of the volunteers have performed 252 gestures each, that is, 504 RGB-D pairs. 968 pairs were captured in scene 3 and 1006 in scene 1 and 2. The dataset contains overall 2976 instances as RGB-D frames.

The distribution of RGB-D pairs per subject and environment is shown in Figure 73. Scene 1 is outdoors, while scene 2 and 3 are indoors.

Figure 73 Distribution of RGB-D pairs across subjects (left) and scenes (right). Scene 1 (outdoor) and Scene 2 (indoor) include slightly more samples than Scene 3 (indoor)

4.3 Human-robot-interaction through hand gestures

The HGR system aims to provide FRs crew a form of HRI, enabling them to control AMRs in a more intuitive manner. The existing approaches mainly rely on cumbersome devices, such as remote controllers, which may not be optimal for their needs, interrupting FRs during their operations to use such devices. Thus, gesture recognition becomes a noteworthy solution, limiting such issues and allowing FRs to guide and manipulate systems without distracting them. Furthermore, commanding robots through verbal commands may not be feasible in noisy environments or over extended distances, making the gesture-based interaction more reliable.

The existing gesture recognition methods can be divided into two main categories: sensor-based and vision-based. Multimodal methods that combine both of them have also been considered. Although the measurements extracted by sensors (wearable or not) tend to be more accurate, sensor-based HGR is in practice infeasible because of its impracticability and the high equipment cost. In contrast, Visual (or Vision-based) HGR (VHGR) utilizes mainly modalities acquired by camera sensors, such as visual spectrum images and depth maps, as well as derived modalities, like OF and pose heatmaps, making it suitable for low-cost solutions and real-world applications. Focusing on enhancing FR's efficiency, VHGR seems a more appropriate approach.

VHGR relies heavily on CV techniques. For simple use cases, traditional CV feature extraction approaches (such as HOG) are often sufficient to develop accurate and lightweight systems. Nevertheless, these features are not meaningful enough to facilitate recognition during in-the-wild applications. The Deep Learning (DL), constituting an advanced representation learning scheme, limits remarkably the aforementioned issue, outperforming traditional methods and achieving high performance on even challenging tasks. Regarding the superiority of DL methods and the requirements of the TRIFFID project, in this study we exclusively focus on DL techniques, considering approaches based on traditional CV as outdated and insufficient for our purposes.

Researchers have proposed VHGR methods for an enormous variety of applications. Overall, four application domains can be considered: Sign Language Understanding (SLU), HRI, Human-Machine

Interaction (HMI) and Human Computer Interaction (HCI). VHGR for SLU aims to identify sign language gestures, bridging the gap between hearing impaired people and the rest of the community. As mentioned earlier, VHGR has been deployed to make HRI more intuitive for humans, even if they have not been trained on the use of robots. Using VHGR to control robotic arms in robotic assisted surgery and industrial scenarios, navigate AMRs such as UAVs and UGVs and communicate with social robots are few examples of gesture-based HRI. In the same sense, manipulation of computer apps (HCI), autonomous cars and construction machinery (HMI) can also be achieved through gesture recognition. In the context of the TRIFFID project, gesture-based HRI seems to be more suitable for the navigation of the UGV.

In the rest of the current section, a literature review of the VHGR is provided, focusing on recent advancements on the field. Regarding the strong relationship between static VHGR and image classification, general-purpose visual backbones are also briefly discussed. Then, datasets relevant to gesture-based AMRs control are enumerated and a micro-dataset, especially collected for the needs of the TRIFFID project, is analyzed. Finally, experimental results on academia datasets and the micro-dataset are presented.

4.3.1 Review of state-of-the-art methods

In this subsection we discuss the current SOTA on VHGR and we highlight the approaches that fit the most to our needs. Various VHGR methods have been developed to accomplish three main tasks: static HGR (SHGR), IDHGR, and continuous dynamic HGR (CDHGR). Methods for SHGR rely only on spatial data, mainly RGB images, in order to recognize gestures that are not evolved in terms of time. In contrast, IDHGR considers spatiotemporal data, capturing both spatial and temporal relationships. These systems are able to recognize single gestures within data sequences, while CDHGR systems are able to handle occurrence of multiple gestures within them. Regarding the complexity of each task, the corresponding methods are accordingly complicated and require analogous amounts of computational power and resources. Thus, SHGR seems to fit more the TRIFFID purposes, as a result the following sections focus on that. Despite this, many concepts are common for all the tasks, so we provide an overview of the entire VHGR field in the next paragraphs.

A more in-depth overview of visual HGR based on deep learning and a presentation of current SOTA in the field can be found in our survey [Foteinos25], conducted during our study for the purposes of the TRIFFID project.

Static HGR

Methods for visual SHGR rely only on spatial data, such as (single) RGB images and depth maps. These methods consist of either a single model (i.e., end-to-end approaches) or a pipeline (i.e., the input data are fed into multiple models, undergoing various processing stages). End-to-end architectures learn implicitly to remove gesture-irrelevant factors through training on large-scale datasets, while pipelines explicitly eliminate redundant information, using specialized (often off-the-shelf) models, such as segmentation models to limit the interference of clutter background and human detectors to perform spatial normalization.

For SLU, authors in [Sharma21] developed a shallow 2DCNN, named Gesture-CNN, to recognize Indian Sign Language (ISL) gestures. The ViT has also been adopted for ISL recognition by authors in [Kothadiya23], proposing the SIGNFORMER. The STN-ND-Net, proposed by authors in [Ghorai23], combines the Spatial Transformer Network (STN) to limit the effect of spatial transformations with a

2DCNN backbone with cascaded deconvolutional and convolutional layers in an autoencoder structure. Authors in [Shin24] proposed dual-stream backbone, incorporating both RGB and pose modalities via intermediate fusion.

For HRI, authors in [Bamani24] developed a three-stage approach, using YOLOv3 for human cropping, the proposed HQ-Net for super-resolution and a custom classifier. The structure of the network is oriented to handle long-range recognition scenarios for gesture-based UGV guidance. Human cropping is performed to normalize the spatial dimensions and super-resolution is utilized to increase image quality, enabling accurate recognition up to 20 meters and introducing the task of ultra-range gesture recognition (URGR). This scheme sufficiently fits the requirements of the TRIFFID project. Unfortunately, although we contacted authors to share their data and code with us, this was not achieved. Authors in [Sahoo23] used a hand segmentation model followed by a classifier named DRCAM, a 2DCNN with stacked Residual Channel Attention Modules (RCAMs) and dense interconnections.

For HCI, authors in [Alam22] created a pipeline for egocentric HGR, consisting of YOLOv2 for hand detection and VGG16 for feature extraction and classification. Authors in [Dang23] examined various combinations of segmentation (such as DeepLab and U-Net) and classification models (like MobileNet). The FGDSNet proposed by authors in [Zhou24] utilizes a dual-stream segmentation model followed by a dual-stream 2DCNN for feature extraction and a MLP for mid-level fusion classification. Finally, authors in [Jafari23] introduced the 2DPSTPP-Net, consisting of four stacked convolutional blocks with a custom pooling method.

General purpose methods for vision-based SHGR have also been proposed. Authors in [Tan21] developed a modification of DenseNet, named EDenseNet, by inserting additional convolutional layers between dense blocks. The SpAtNet, introduced by authors in [Bhaumik24], is a lightweight 2DCNN with three streams: two MAFF modules for coarse-grained features and one Interleaved Module for high-level representations; their fused features are fed to an MLP for classification. Authors in [Zhang23D] developed the LHGR-Net, a lightweight network with spatial pyramid pooling and attention, configured for execution on ARM devices.

The architectures of each current SOTA visual SHGR method and their accuracies on public datasets are shown in the Table 25. Since most methods are evaluated on different or custom datasets, a straightforward performance comparison is not feasible.

Table 25 SOTA performance on SHGR benchmarks, segmentation-based pipelines are depicted with *

Method	Modality	Architecture	Dataset	Accuracy
Gesture-CNN [Sharma21]	RGB	2DCNN consisting of four convolutional layers	Jochen Triesch II	100.0%
DRCAM [Sahoo23]*	Depth	Attention-based 2CNN with residual connections	ASL-FS	93.44%
2DPSTPP-Net [Jafari23]	RGB	Convolutional blocks followed by the proposed pooling method, intermediate features are concatenated to obtain the final representation	NUS-I	100.0%
			NUS-II	99.61%
FGDSNet [Zhou24] *	RGB	Dual stream 2DCNN approach and a custom dual-stream segmentation module to obtain the mask	HGR1	94.80%
			OUHANDS	97.80%
			NUS-II	99.80%
	RGB		ASL-FS	99.99%

EDenseNet [Tan21]		Modified DenseNet with extra convolution layers	NUS-II	99.30%
SpAtNet [Bhaumik24]	RGB	Three-stream 2DCNN, where each stream aims to obtain either high-level or coarse-grained features	HGR1	93.33%
			ASL-FS	99.67%
			NUS-II	96.53%
LHGR-Net [Zhang23D]	RGB	BaseNet + MSS (adopting the atrous spatial pyramid pooling) + LAS (based on CBAM)	HGR1	93.15%
			OUHANDS	98.75%

Most of the aforementioned method publications do not provide code or the necessary details that would allow us to implement them. Thus, we proceed with a brief analysis of the current SoTA for image classification, aiming to identify newer and more accurate methods, which we may adopt for HGR. Older but widely used Deep Learning (DL) methods were also considered. In the following subsections, we briefly describe the main architectural approaches.

CNNs were the first type of DL image classifiers proposed by the researchers, based on learnable convolution filters. ResNet [Kaiming16] increased the performance of image classification by introducing residual connections between blocks, facilitating gradient flow. Even though it is old, it is still used as backbone by many HGR methods ([Kapitanov24, Cui19]). ResNeXt [Saining17] modifies ResNet by replacing the initial blocks with multi-branch modules, proposing the “cardinality” (e.g. number of branches) hyperparameter to better tune the architecture. To reduce computational complexity, MobileNet [Howard17] and GhostNet [Han20A] replaced the vanilla convolution operation with separable depthwise convolution and the Ghost module that applies convolution to only half of the input and cheaper linear operations to the other half, respectively. EfficientNet [Mingxing19] proposed the “compound coefficient”, which simultaneously controls width, depth and resolution hyperparameters to facilitate scaling. TinyNet [Han20B] proposed a mathematical formula to shrink the EfficientNet and obtain an even more lightweight model. ConvNeXt [Zhuang22] gradually incorporates vision transformers' architecture into 2DCNNs, claiming that the effectiveness of vision transformers is due to their architectures and not to attention mechanisms. ConvNeXt-V2 [Woo23] extends ConvNeXt by pretraining in as part of a MAE using sparse convolutions and proposing the global response normalization layer to promote feature diversity. InternImage [Wang23E] incorporates deformable convolution and the transformer architecture to scale up CNNs, resulting in a vision FM. Motivated by the fact that small models fail to leverage transfer learning prior, ParameterNet [Han24] used dynamic convolution to increase capacity without a significant impact on the Giga Floating Point Operations (GFLOPs).

Transformers were originally proposed for Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks. However, they were adopted for CV by ViT [Dosovitskiy21], a fully attention-based approach, which treats images as patches sequence and combines linear embeddings with position encodings. DeiT [Touvron21] enhances ViT using various knowledge distillation techniques through the addition of a distillation token. TNT [Han21] further divides patches into smaller ones and applies additional attention mechanisms (termed inner transformer blocks) to enhance scale invariance. Swin-T [Liu21A] introduced a hierarchical transformer-based approach with reduced computational cost; self-attention is applied to non-overlapped windows and shifted windows facilitate cross-window feature extraction. BiFormer [Zhu23] introduced the Bi-Level Routing Attention module, which discards irrelevant patches during the computation of attention and selects the top-k semantically related (using a dynamic adjacency matrix).

Hybrid models that utilize convolutional operations alongside attention have also been proposed. MaxViT [Tu22] decoupled self-attention into block and grid attention (multi-axis attention) to capture local and global context, respectively, without increasing complexity. EfficientFormerV2 [Li23B] made the architecture simpler by replacing the token mixer with a Feed-forward Neural Network and Depth-Wise Convolution (DWC) facilitating the architectural search process. Motivated by the low expressiveness of linear attention (e.g. a method that reduces computational cost using an approximation of the similarity function and the matrix multiplication associativity), FLatten Transformer [Han23A] introduced a new mapping function and increased feature diversity by an extra DWC module. EfficientViT [Liu23A] introduced the group attention module which processes various splits of the input features to reduce redundancy. FFNs and DWC layers are also utilized to decrease the computational cost and enhance token interaction.

Despite the effectiveness of the methods listed above, vision (or spatial) MLPs have also achieved remarkable performance, relying only on fully connected layers. The input image is partitioned into smaller patches, just like in transformers, while many spatial MLPs share architecture similar to them. In particular, MLP-Mixer [Tolstikhin21], which is the first model of this kind, introduced an architecture that separates the per-location and cross-location feature extraction, performed using only MLPs. ResMLP [Touvron22] consists of alternatively stacked MLPs that extract cross-path and cross-channel features. These modules also incorporate residual connections. AS-MLP [Lian21] emphasized on local feature extraction, introducing horizontal and vertical shifts. Hire-MLP [Guo22] substituted the token mixer of the MLP-Mixer with the proposed Hierarchical Rearrangement Module, which aims to enhance both local and global feature extraction and enable processing of input of variable dimensions. Cycle-MLP [Chen21B] introduced the cycle fully connected layer, in order to reduce the computational complexity, maintaining a large receptive field. Wave-MLP [Tang22] dynamically aggregated tokens instead of using fixed weights, aiming to leverage the different semantics of each, by representing them as waves and fusing them depending on the phase and amplitude. SNN-MLP [Li22B] introduced Leaky Integrate and Fire (LIF) spiking neurons. Vertical and horizontal LIF are applied in parallel within LIF modules.

Recently SSMs used for NLP tasks, mainly Mamba variants, were adapted as vision backbones, in order to overcome challenges related to transformers (e.g. computational cost). Similar to spatial MLPs, transformers' general architectures are usually considered. In more detail, VMamba [Liu24B] introduced the 2D-Selective-Scan (SS2D) module, which traverses patches in four different ways. Mamba-Adaptor [Xie25] enhanced Mamba via an extra summation term to overcome the forgetting limitation and a convolutional operator to capture spatial context. Targeting to reduce computational complexity, GroupMamba [Shaker25] grouped the input channels and applied the proposed Visual Single Selective Scanning (VSSS) to each separately. A channel modulator operator is also utilized for cross-channel learning as well as knowledge distillation. DefMamba [Liu25C] introduced a multi-scale scheme consisting of deformable blocks with dynamic scanning paths.

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) proposed for visual tasks also treat images as a set of patches similar to transformers and SSMs. However, these patches are viewed as nodes of a graph, enabling these models to capture more complex and fine-grained dependencies. The first such model was the ViG [Han22], which connects patches with edges based on the K-NN algorithm. The over-smoothing phenomenon was mitigated by inserting linear layers and activation functions. ViHGNN [Han23B] enhanced ViG by using hypergraphs (i.e. edges connecting more than two image patches) to capture more complex inter-patch relations. The hybrid GNN/CNN GreedyViG [Munir24] introduced the

Dynamic Axial Graph Construction (DAGC) method instead of the K-NN in order to reduce the number of edges and therefore the computational complexity.

Isolated dynamic hand gesture recognition

In contrast with SHGR methods that neglect temporal information, IDHGR methods utilize both spatial and temporal data in order to recognize individual gesture instances. When gestures are part of a sign language, the task is also mentioned as Isolated Sign Language Recognition (ISLR). Regarding the nature of sign languages, ISLR methods often leverage both manual (e.g., hand movements) and non-manual (e.g., facial expressions, upper body motion) features.

Pose-based IDHGR approaches rely only on skeleton data, such as keypoint heatmaps, skeleton joints coordinates and bone motion vectors. Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs), originally developed for Human Action Recognition (HAR) are usually adopted, due to their ability to capture the structure of the human hand. In more detail, authors in [Cui25] proposed DSTSA-GCN, which deploys three stacked stages each, consisting of group channel-wise and temporal-wise GCN, followed by multiscale TCN. Authors in [Zhao23B] developed STST, a two-stage transformer-based approach that performs global and local spatiotemporal feature extraction. Authors in [Narayan23] introduced SBI-DHGR, which consists of three 1DCNN streams for spatial feature extraction. These embeddings are concatenated and subsequently fed into a BiLSTM for temporal aggregation and MLP for classification. Authors in [Li24D] proposed a two-stream network consisting of an attention-based dual-branch module and a MAE. The TD-GCN [Liu23B] is a variant of the ST-GCN with channel-dependent and temporal-dependent adjacency matrices. Inspired by the BERT pretraining paradigm, authors in [Hu21B] introduced a masked pose reconstruction framework, named SignBERT, to insert hand topology prior using a MANO-based decoder. The architecture consists of a GCN for spatial feature extraction followed by a transformer encoder that performs temporal modeling. Variations of this approach are the SignBERT+ [Hu21C], BEST [Zhao23C] and MASA [Zhao23D]. Considering the insufficiency of stand-alone pose-based methods, mainly caused by pose estimation failures, these are often combined with parallel RGB-based branches via late fusion. Authors in DSTA-SLR [Hu24A] utilized dynamic adjacency matrices and multi-stream fusion to improve recognition accuracy.

Multimodal networks leverage multiple modalities (e.g., OF, RGB frames, depth maps) simultaneously, significantly improving the accuracy. Authors in [Li25C] introduced a unified multi-task multimodal framework, named Uni-Sign, which consists of three pose and one visual encoder. The extracted features are fused using attention and fed into an LLM to obtain the prediction, performing ISLR, CSLR, and Sign Language Translation (SLT) simultaneously. The SAM-SLR proposed by authors in [Jiang21A] combines six streams and late fusion. The SAM-SLR v2 [Jiang21B] extends SAM-SLR by adding a learnable late fusion strategy and a 3D skeleton graph stream. Authors in [Hampiholi23] introduced CTFB to perform multi-level fusion for dual-stream 3DCNN architectures. The RAAR3DNet [Zhou21B] is a modification of the I3D that uses NAS to define the optimal network structure and attention mechanisms to focus on the most informative regions. NAS was also combined with 3D Central Difference Convolution (3DCDC) by authors in [Yu21]. The De+Recouple, developed by authors in [Zhou22], is a dual-stream RGBD-based architecture with an AE for multi-level fusion and mechanisms to reduce redundancy. Self-distillation for inter-frame learning and extra supervision to enhance the AE are also deployed. A dual-stream Res3D-18 followed by late fusion was proposed by authors in [Li23C], who utilized a memory network to enhance the discriminative capability of the extracted features and an information-theoretic loss function.

The data scarcity remains a notable challenge for IDHGR. Researchers aim to address this by using few-shot and zero-shot approaches, mainly adopting BERT and textual descriptions that accompany the gesture samples. In particular, authors in [Bilge22] combined BERT-encoded textual descriptions and hand-crafted features for zero-shot ISLR. Authors in [Bikle24] proposed a few-shot learning framework with a three-stream architecture that utilizes both RGB (using 3DCNNs) and pose modalities, which are fused via an attention mechanism. Authors in [Rastgoo23] utilized a vision transformer and a LSTM for temporal modeling. Authors in [Rastgoo24] incorporated skeleton-derived geometric features with a RGB-based stream consisting of a C3D for short-term spatiotemporal modeling followed by an LSTM to capture long-term context and an AE to obtain the final representation in the shared embedding space.

Aiming to minimize the computational cost, many works have used key-frame extraction techniques. In particular, authors in [Bharti23] proposed a trainable key frame selection method based on error correction. VGG16 features are used to identify key frames, which are then preprocessed and fed into a custom 3D CNN for classification. In the method introduced by authors in [Liu24C], a 2D-CNN and attention mechanism filter out less informative frames. The remaining keyframes are processed by two branches: the Hand stream, which crops and analyzes hand regions with attention blocks, and the Full stream, which processes the entire frame. The fused features are used for final classification. Authors in [Gan23] proposed DRL-DDNet that adopts reinforcement learning to obtain the most important frames, which are subsequently fed into the DDNet to perform the recognition. Authors in [Beer24] utilized a lightweight 2DCNN to extract per-frame features that are processed to obtain the key frames. These are passed through an object detector that crops the human region and the SlowFast to perform the classification. The pipeline was adopted for long-range gesture-based UGV guidance.

The current SOTA for IDHGR is briefly analyzed in Table 26. Authors leverage self-supervised pretraining to inject a hand topology prior, NAS to determine the optimal structure of networks, multimodality fusion to incorporate information from various data forms, key frame selection to reduce redundancy and the computational cost, as well as multi-tasking learning.

Table 26 Architectures and per-instance accuracy of SOTA IDHGR methods

Method	Modality	Architecture & training setting	Dataset	Accuracy (PI)
DSTSA-GCN [Cui25]	Pose	Three stacked stages, each one consisting of group channel-wise and temporal-wise GCN, followed by multiscale TCN	SHREC-14	97.74%
			SHREC-28	95.37%
			DHG-14	95.04%
			DHG-28	93.57%
STST [Zhao23B]	Pose	Two-stage transformer-based approach	SHREC-14	97.62%
			SHREC-28	95.83%
			DHG-14	94.82%
			DHG-28	93.18%
SBI-DHGR [Narayan23]	Pose	Multi-stream 1DCNN + BiLSTM	SHREC-14	97.00%
			SHREC-28	92.36%
			DHG-14	94.64%
			DHG-28	91.79%
[Li24D]	Pose		SHREC-14	96.90%

		Two-stream approach consisting of an attention-based dual branch module and MAE	SHREC-28	94.17%
			DHG-14	94.21%
			DHG-28	92.11%
TD-GCN [Liu23B]	Pose	ST-GCN variant with channel-dependent and temporal-dependent adjacency matrices	SHREC-14	97.02%
			SHREC-28	95.36%
			DHG-14	93.90%
			DHG-14	91.40%
DRL-DDNet [Gan23]	Pose	DD-Net for classification and FS-Net for keyframe extraction	SHREC-14	96.50%
			SHREC-28	93.80%
SignBERT [Hu21B]	RGB, Pose	Spatial GCN, temporal and chirality embedding + Transformer & RGB-based stream + late fusion, pretrained with masked pose reconstruction	MSASL1000	71.24%
			WLASL2000	54.69%
			CSL500	97.60%
SignBERT+ [Hu21C]	RGB, Pose	Extension of SignBERT with Spatial-Temporal Position Encoding and enhanced late fusion technique	MSASL1000	73.71%
			WLASL2000	55.59%
			CSL500	97.80%
BEST [Zhao23C]	RGB, Pose	d-VAE + GCN + Transformer & RGB-based encoder + late fusion and SSL pretraining (masked tokens reconstruction)	MSASL1000	71.21%
			WLASL2000	54.59%
			CSL500	97.70%
MASA [Zhao23D]	RGB, Pose	Spatial GCN + Transformer & RGB-based stream, pretrained with masked input reconstruction and contrastive learning	WLASL2000	55.77%
Uni-Sign [Li25C]	RGB, Pose	A pretrained LLM processes features extracted by pose, visual, and temporal encoders. Three-stage training, multi-task learning with additional training data	MSASL1000	78.16%
			WLASL2000	63.52%
SAM-SLR-v2 [Jiang21B]	RGBD, Pose, HHA, OF, DF	Extension of SAM-SLR with 3D graph stream and learnable weights for late fusion	WLASL2000	59.39%
			CSL500	99.00%
CTFB [Hampiholi23]	RGBD	Dual-stream I3D with multi-level fusion	Chalearn IsoGD	69.02%
RAAR3DNet [Zhou21B]	RGBD	Dual stream I3D with adoptable	Chalearn IsoGD	66.62%

		cells, spatial and temporal attention, trained with multi-task loss and NAS		
SlowFast+NAS+CDC [Yu21]	RGBD, OF	Multi-stream and multi-rate 3DCNN with 3D-CDC, multi-level fusion and NAS	Challearn IsoGD	66.23%
De+Recouple [Zhou22]	RGBD	Dual-stream spatial + temporal with AE for multi-level fusion and mechanisms to reduce redundancy. Self-distillation for inter-frame learning, extra supervision to enhance the AE.	Challearn IsoGD	66.79%

Continuous dynamic hand gesture recognition

CDHGR networks aim to identify multiple gestures within an untrimmed data sequence and generate the corresponding gesture sequence. The exact temporal boundaries of the gestures are not provided, thus CDHGR is considered to be a weakly-supervised task. However, recent studies [Wei23] have highlighted that CDHGR methods learn to spot them implicitly. The Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) loss is usually utilized to facilitate training, but its limitations have driven researchers to define other loss functions [Zhang23E]. Although some authors have incorporated CDHGR to other application domains such as autonomous driving, the most advanced methods have been developed to perform Continuous Sign Language Recognition (CSLR). In that context, “gestures” are also mentioned as “glosses” (i.e., atomic lexical units of sign languages, analogous to words in spoken languages).

RGB-based methods follow a three-stage architecture: a spatial perception model (like 2DCNN or vision transformer) that extracts frame-wise features, a short-term temporal module (mainly TCN or 1DCNN) to extract local gloss-wise features, and a long-term temporal module (a BiLSTM) which acts as a global context aggregator and obtains the final representation. This scheme was originally introduced by the authors in [Cui19]. The decoupled spatial+temporal has dominated against 3DCNNs due to the latter’s inability to define clear temporal boundaries [Adadoglou21]. Regarding the optimization difficulties of the aforementioned scheme, authors in [Min21] proposed VAC-CSLR. The framework (Figure 74) utilizes auxiliary losses to provide extra supervision, via visual enhancement and alignment losses, which aim to facilitate the efficient training of the lower components of the architecture. Authors in [Hu22] introduced Temporal Lift Pooling (TLP) in order to overcome the limitations of handcrafted pooling layers within the 1DCNN. Authors in [Hu23] proposed CorrNet, which contains extra modules after the 2DCNN stage to capture inter-frame trajectories and focus on the most informative regions. The CorrNet+ [Hu24B] replaces the correlation operator of the CorrNet with a more efficient variant and inserts an attention layer. The CLIP spatial feature extractor has been adopted for CSLR by authors in [Alyami25], who applied LoRA and MLP adapters to fine-tune the frozen visual encoder. Auxiliary classifiers were also utilized to provide early extra supervision. Authors in [Gan24] proposed a different approach, named SignGraph, which deploys GCNs to process image patches that are treated as nodes in a dynamic learnable graph. A multiscale variant was also developed in the same work.

Figure 74 Visual Alignment and Visual Enhancement losses guide feature extractor training via knowledge distillation and early supervision

Unimodal pose-based CSLR approaches have also been proposed. Authors in [Guan25] proposed MSKA-SLR which processes each region independently via attention-enhanced temporal convolutions across four branches. The resulting features are fused to decode gloss sequences using a CTC loss, complemented by frame-level self-distillation. Authors in [Jiao23] developed CoSign that employs group-specific GCNs for each subset and introduces regularization to preserve inter-stream consistency. Their dual-stream variant integrates joint positions and motion features using multi-level fusion to capture both static and dynamic cues. Autonomous driving is considered by authors in [Fu23] and [Wang22B], who aim to recognize police traffic gestures. The FA-STGCN [Fu23] normalizes skeleton inputs and applies alternating spatial and temporal GCNs. Spatial modules learn latent joint relationships, while temporal processing is split into global and local paths, extracting coarse-grained and fine-grained motion patterns, respectively. Authors in [Wang22] developed a two-stage pose-based. The first stage extracts geometric features and encodes them via LSTM layers. The second stage uses a dual-stream setup, where one branch processes geometric descriptors and the other uses a ConvLSTM to handle co-occurrence matrices. Features are fused with directional orientation indicators for final classification.

Multimodal methods for CSLR incorporate multiple modalities, such as RGB, depth and pose heatmaps, to increase the recognition accuracy. Authors in [Chen22B] proposed TwoStream-SLR, a dual-stream approach consisting of S3D blocks that process pose heatmaps and RGB frames in parallel with bidirectional lateral connections to perform multi-level fusion. The overall framework is illustrated in the figure below. Auxiliary classifiers are utilized to provide extra supervision through extra CTC loss and self-distillation. Uni-Sign [Li25C] and SignBERT+ [Hu21B] can also be used for CSLR.

Optimization difficulties due to the CTC spike phenomenon [Min21] and the large complexity of the architectures, as well as data scarcity, put barriers on the performance of CDHGR methods. Thus, regarding both the available computational resources in the context of the TRIFFID project and the enormous amount of data needed, CDHGR does not seem a reasonable choice for efficient gesture-based HRI. In Table 27, the current CSLR SOTA methods are quantitatively and qualitatively compared.

Figure 75 The TwoStream-SLR architecture

Table 27 SOTA methods for CSLR. WER stands for word error rate

Method	Modality	Architecture	Training Setting	Dataset	WER
CoSign-2s [Jiao23]	Pose	Dual stream approach based on ST-GCN, considering both joints and motions. Each stream consists of group-specific branches	Extra supervision via auxiliary classifier and complementary regularization to enhance the robustness to noise.	CSL-Daily	27.20%
				Phoenix	20.10%
				Phoenix-T	20.10%
TwoStream-SLR [Chen22B]	RGB, Pose	Dual stream (containing S3D blocks) with bidirectional lateral connections.	Extra supervision is achieved by auxiliary CTC losses and self-distillation applied to additional prediction heads.	CSL-Daily	25.30%
				Phoenix	18.80%
				Phoenix-T	19.30%
Uni-Sign [Li25C]	RGB, Pose	A pretrained LLM process features extracted by pose, visual and temporal encoders.	Three-stage training, multi-task learning with additional training data	CSL-Daily	26.00%
C ² ST [Zhang23E]	RGB	SwinT+1DCNN+BiLSTM	CGD loss, distillation to maintain the consistency between video and local-level features and linguistic prior	CSL-Daily	25.80%
				Phoenix	17.70%
				Phoenix-T	18.90%
CorrNet [Hu23]	RGB	2DCNN equipped with the proposed	VAC-CSLR [Min21]	CSL-Daily	30.10%

		identification and correlation modules, followed by 1DCNN+BiLSTM.		Phoenix	19.40%
				Phoenix-T	20.50%
CorrNet+ [Hu24B]	RGB	Modification of the CorrNet [19], obtained by adding temporal attention after the correlation and identification modules.	VAC-CSLR and TLP [Hu22]	CSL-Daily	28.20%
				Phoenix	18.20%
				Phoenix-T	19.10%
SLA-Adaptor/LoRA [Alyami25]	RGB	CLIP visual encoder with adopter/LoRA, followed by TCN and BiLSTM	VAC-CSLR [hu22] and early supervision, by adding an extra classifier after the visual encoder	CSL-Daily	25.80%
				Phoenix	18.8%/19.3%
				Phoenix-T	19.5%/19.4%
MultiSignGraph [Gan24]	RGB	A multiscale spatial-temporal GNN that considers image patches as the nodes.	VAC-CSLR [Min21]	CSL-Daily	26.40%
				Phoenix	19.10%
				Phoenix-T	19.10%

4.3.2 Implemented solutions

Static hand gesture recognition

For static HGR, following the HAGRID [Kapitanov24] baseline, ResNet variants of different scales (ResNet-18, ResNet-50 and ResNeX-50) were considered. Experiments with the lightweight EfficientNet-B0 [Mingxing19] were also conducted, regarding its suitability for resource-constrained deployment (requiring only 0.39 GFLOPs). Gesture-CNN [Sharma21], proposed for gesture-based HCI, was also selected in order to evaluate a model especially designed for HGR. Transformers, such as [Dosovitskiy21], weren't considered due to their large size (in terms of parameters). Segmentation + Classification pipelines inspired by [Dang23] were implemented in order to mitigate the data scarcity problem; the segmentation module performs background removal, reducing the interference of gesture-irrelevant factors. However, authors in [Dang23] fine-tuned DeepLabV3 in OUHANDS [Matilainen16] for hand palm segmentation. In the conducted experiments, the "human" class by the pretrained DeepLabV3 was utilized, without fine-tuning the model, regarding that 1) the OUHANDS is very small and the hand palm masks are not of sufficient quality and 2) for the LHGR dataset, subjects perform gestures in various distances, reaching up to 7 meters, while in the OUHANDS the recognition range is very short.

ResNet

ResNet [Kaiming16] is a 2DCNN method widely adopted as a backbone for downstream tasks. Most of the existing works on CSLR (the 2DCNN+1DCNN+BiLSTM pipelines) still use the ResNet to obtain per-frame representations, due to its ability to efficiently propagate the gradients, through residual connections, facilitating the optimization process. In more detail, the authors of ResNet proposed five different settings, corresponding to various scales (with 18, 34, 50, 101, and 152 layers). All of these architectures share the same building block, which is the core of the publication; the residual (aka

shortcut) connections, which aim to mitigate optimization difficulties and in particular, the fact that deep architectures tend to be more difficult to train. As shown in Figure 76, the residual blocks incorporate an identical mapping, which is added to the output. Thus, the resulting module can be formulated as $y = F(x, \{W_i\}) + x$ where W is the weights of the in between layers. If the dimensions do not match, linear projection is applied and the formula becomes $y = F(x, \{W_i\}) + W_{sx}$.

Figure 76 The residual block architecture

The ResNet model is discussed in Section 2.4.2. We would also like to mention here that most of the existing works on CSLR (the 2DCNN+1DCNN+BiLSTM pipelines) still use the ResNet to obtain per-frame representations, while many papers for static HGR (including HaGRID [HAGRID]) propose the ResNet as a baseline model.

ResNeXt

ResNeXt [Saining17] is an extension of the ResNet, which aims to increase the capacity of the former with a negligible computational overhead. The core idea lies in modifying the residual block, by transforming it into a multi-branch module. The number of these branches, called “cardinality”, is revealed as a new hyperparameter together with width (e.g. number of channels) and depth (e.g. number of layers). The outputs of each stream are aggregated via addition. Figure 77 illustrates the initial ResNet building block and the augmented version, introduced by the authors of the ResNeXt. Three implementations of ResNeXt are provided by PyTorch¹⁵: ResNeXt-50 32x4 (e.g. 50 layers with cardinality equal to 32 and width equal to 4), ResNeXt-101 32x8 and ResNetXt-101 64x4.

Figure 77 The ResNeXt architecture

Gesture-CNN

The Gesture-CNN [Sharma21] was proposed for static Sign Language Recognition (SLR), but in this study it was adopted for gesture-based HRI. Its architecture is relatively simple, consisting of only three convolutional layers, as shown in Figure 78. The softmax classifier was replaced by a FC layer, with a number of output features according to the considered dataset (in the case of LRHG, ten). Despite its

¹⁵ <https://pytorch.org/>

small depth, it comprises a large number of parameters (approximately 67M). However, these do not increase the model's capacity and expressiveness, as was obtained by our experiments.

Figure 78 The Gesture-CNN architecture

EfficientNet-B0

Authors in [Mingxing19] targeted to efficiently scale DL-based image classifiers, balancing computational complexity and accuracy. In particular, they made two observations that drove them to introduce the compound scaling scheme Figure 79: 1) tuning width, depth and resolution of the model independently increase the accuracy, but the gain saturates and 2) in order to develop both a fast and accurate method, these values should be changed simultaneously. The compound scaling framework relies on the compound coefficient, which is employed to modify the architecture following the equations $d = \alpha^\phi$, $w = \phi^\beta$, $r = \gamma^\phi$ where d, w, r corresponds to depth, width and resolution, respectively. The α, β, γ constants are determined through grid search, which control how the available computational resources (modelled by ϕ) are distributed within the network. This approach was applied to existing architectures (e.g. ResNet [He16]) and to a custom, termed EfficientNet, which was obtained through multi-objective NAS, optimizing accuracy and FLOPs simultaneously.

Figure 79 EfficientNet introduces compound scaling, jointly optimizing width, depth, and resolution

Dynamic hand gesture recognition

Aiming to investigate methods of various kinds, the pose-based TD-GCN [Liu23B] and the IPN-Hand [Benitez-Garcia21] baseline models were used. TD-GCN was selected due to its superior performance in the SHREC17 [De Smedt17]. IPN-Hand baseline includes the ResNeXt-101, both for unimodal evaluation (relying only on RGB frames) and multimodal setting (using RGB and OF that are early fused).

TD-GCN

The Temporal-Decoupling Graph Convolution (TD-GC), illustrated in Figure 80, proposed by authors in [Liu23B], aims to enhance the graph convolution for gesture recognition, by introducing per-frame adjacency matrices, instead of using shared across the entire sequence. In particular, TD-GC can be formulated as $X' = F(M(D, X), M(H, X))$ where tensor X' represents the output features corresponding to each node and X is obtained after applying 1×1 temporal convolution to the input X features. D, H comprise channel-dependent and temporal-dependent adjacency matrices, respectively, which are calculated based on a fixed adjacency matrix - reflecting the physical joints connections - and a correlation matrix. The M operation, which combines matrix multiplication and concatenation, multiplies each adjacency matrix with the corresponding features and fuses the results through concatenation. F aggregates the two outputs after multiplying them with learnable weights. The basic block of the architecture (named TD-GCN) consists of three parallel TD-GC layers, corresponding to three different fixed topologies. Their outputs are concatenated and subsequently fed into a multi-branch temporal convolution module. The overall architecture comprises ten stacked such layers followed by linearity to perform classification.

Figure 80 TD-GC applies temporal and channel decoupling to enhance expressiveness, then fuses graph-convolved features using Temporal-Channel Fusion

ResNeXt (3DCNN)

Authors in IPN-Hand [Benitez-Garcia21] introduced the 3D ResNeXt-101 [Hara18] as a baseline model for their dataset. The 3D ResNeXt-101 extends the initial ResNeXt-101 for video classification and HAR, replacing the 2D convolutional kernels with 3D filters. The cardinality was set to 32. The building block of the architecture is shown in Figure 81. The overall model firstly applies downsampling with a

large receptive field (kernel size of $7 \times 7 \times 7$) and then feeds the output feature maps in 4 stacked layers, each one consisting of the previously mentioned building blocks (66 in total). As in the original ResNeXt, the dimensions of the feature maps are divided by two from layer to layer and the number of channels is doubled. For multimodal gesture recognition, authors in [Benitez-Garcia21] deployed early fusion, via stacking the RGB frames with OF, segmented RGB frames or depth maps before feeding them into the model.

Figure 81 The basic block of the 3D ResNeXt

4.3.3 Experimental evaluation

Static hand gesture recognition

The results are shown in Table 28. The weights corresponding to the maximum validation accuracy were picked to obtain the test accuracy. The epochs were set to 100 and 200 for HaGRID and LRHG, respectively. The batch size, the optimizer and other hyperparameters were selected either based on the given by the papers training details or either through empirical analysis.

EfficientNet-B0 achieves superior performance in HaGRID, despite its small size; however, it is often surpassed by the rest of the models in LRHG. Considering the small size of the LRHG and its large capacity, it was not evaluated on it. On the contrary, Gesture-CNN, although it is the largest model in terms of (trainable) parameters, doesn't overfit in the LRHG, reflecting its poor capacity. It was not evaluated on HaGRID, due to its high computational cost and poor architecture.

As was mentioned in the review of SOTA methods for SHGR, the background removal does not always increase the accuracy and often end-to-end approaches surpass Segmentation + Classification pipelines, probably because the segmentation module inserts extra failures. This is also verified by our experimental results.

Table 28 Experimental results on public datasets

Model	Type	GFLOPs	Parameters	HaGRID (F1)	LRHG (Acc)
ResNet-18	2DCNN	1.81	11,689,512	96.60%	97.60%
ResNet-50	2DCNN	4.09	25,557,032	97.09%	97.14%
ResNeXt-50	2DCNN	4.23	25,028,904	97.36%	-
EfficientNet-B0	2DCNN	0.39	5,288,548	97.57%	96.91%
Gesture-CNN	2DCNN	-	67,000,000	-	97.02%
Frozen DeepLabV3 (ResNet-101 backbone) + ResNet-18	Human Segmentation + 2DCNN	1.81+258.74	11,689,512 (trainable) + 60,996,202 (frozen)	-	97.25%
Frozen DeepLabV3 (ResNet-101 backbone) + ResNet-50	Human Segmentation + 2DCNN	4.09+258.74	25,557,032 (trainable) + 60,996,202 (frozen)	-	93.82%
Frozen DeepLabV3 (ResNet-101 backbone) + EfficientNet-B0	Human Segmentation + 2DCNN	0.39+258.74	5,288,548 (trainable) + 60,996,202 (frozen)	-	94.97%

Dynamic hand gesture recognition

The numerical results are shown in Table 29. The training hyperparameters, as well as the implementations provided by the two papers, were used. Incorporating multiple modalities, even with early fusion (which is considered to be suboptimal), improves classification accuracy for appearance-based gesture recognition. Pose-based methods have access to less redundant information (e.g. the presence of gesture-irrelevant factors is more intense in RGB and derived modalities), assuming that the pose estimation doesn't fail.

Table 29 Comparison of gesture-recognition methods

Method	Modality	Type	Accuracy	Dataset
ResNeXt-101	RGB	3DCNN	84.503%	IPN-Hand
ResNeXt-101	RGB, OF	3DCNN	86.326%	IPN-Hand
TD-GCN (14label joint.pt)	Skeleton	ST-GCN variant	96.31%	SHREC14
TD-GCN (28label joint.pt)	Skeleton	ST-GCN variant	93.69%	SHREC28

4.3.4 Static hand gesture recognition experiments on the created gesture dataset

In this section, experimental results on the collected dataset are discussed. Regarding the previous experiments, the ResNet-18 was selected, due to its small size and superior performance on LRHG, which has ~1K samples more than ours. ResNet-50 and other larger architectures are considered to be very large for such a small dataset and computationally costly for on-board deployment, but they will be investigated in the future. AdamW was selected as the optimizer to prevent overfitting, StepLR (provided by PyTorch) with $\gamma=0.9$ and step size 1 as the learning rate scheduler, with initial learning rate equal to $1e-2$ and weight decay $1e-4$. Considering the suitability of HaGRID for transfer learning (due to its size and diversity), pretrained weights on HaGRID were used in some experiments for weight initialization. F1-Score was used as the classification metric.

Images are randomly distributed into train, validation and test splits, with 2376, 288 and 312 samples respectively, while keeping the number of samples per class the same for all the classes within a split to avoid class-imbalance.

Experimental results are shown in Table 30 and in the confusion matrix in Figure 82. Introducing augmentation hasn't improved the performance; on the contrary, it has downgraded it. Utilizing pretrained weights for parameter initialization is essential due to the small size of the dataset.

Table 30 Experimental setup and results in the custom dataset

Method	Pretrained	Augmentations	F1 Train	F1 Val	F1 Test
ResNet-18	Yes (HAGRID)	No	99.83%	96.18%	93.91%

Figure 82 Confusion matrix in the test set. The model tends to misclassify visually similar signs (such as “ok to go” and “come to me”)

4.4 Semantic abstraction for situation awareness

The TRIFFID system aims to enrich the services of the Base of Operation (BoO) typically set by FRs in proximity to the disaster site. The overall system consists of a ground station, a tele-operated UAV, and an autonomous UGV. The UGV accompanies the field crew within the disaster scene. The ground station provides the local Disaster Scene Commander (DCS) with a unified and updated view of the disaster scene, based on data collected during operations. DCS directly supervises BoO, and each field crew member is equipped with a smartphone to receive BoO notifications and coordination information through a dedicated app. The ground station is initialized with EO data that are analyzed to construct a semantically annotated map of the area of interest. The UAV is deployed to acquire additional data about specific areas or individual entities. The ground station operation makes strategic decisions by coordinating and setting mission-level tasks that are dispatched to selected resources (UGV or field crew members). The ground station centralized the AI services necessary to monitor and coordinate the execution of a mission. Such services enable DCS to maintain an informed and synchronized view of the mission, making timely and accurate decisions. In this technological landscape, AI components

would help and possibly improve the decisions of base commands by processing the data flow from the environment. TRIFFID investigates the use of knowledge-based representation and reasoning to interpret environmental data and reason about mission-level tasks that can be performed according to the types of detected situations and the capabilities of the resources on the field [Umbrico20]. Timeline-based planning [Cialdea16] then operationalizes operations by automating task decomposition and coordinating the UGV and field crew members.

Figure 83 Data abstraction process for situation awareness

A key aspect of TRIFFID is the capability to integrate the large amount of sensory data and images produced through satellite observations (EO), UGV, and UAV perception. Data processing enriched with semantic technologies for contextual abstraction would realize Situation awareness processes to frame mission information according to users' roles, proactively detect and notify users about relevant situations or decision needs, and generally improve communication among users and teams. Figure 83 depicts the conceptual process as introduced in [Kokar09]. It clearly shows the abstraction procedure consisting of finding relationships between objects detected from the environment and then reasoning about possible courses of action by identifying suitable tasks. This abstraction process is crucial to not overload DCS with information that could limit its evaluation of operational needs. Semantics would thus frame information and help DCS maintain the focus on specific emerging needs, taking advantage of the enhanced perception functionalities of the technology. Furthermore, mission-level tasks composing operational procedures (e.g, exploration, inspection, rescue, monitoring) would be contextualized according to the current context of a mission and the set of (prioritized) situations that have been detected. The outcome of the reasoning would provide the DCS with a list of prioritized situations and recommended tasks to be performed in the current context of the mission.

In combination with situation awareness, task planning keeps track of the execution of a mission and coordinates the implementation of mission-level tasks. It receives mission-level task requests from DCS and assigns operations to UGV and field crew members, according to their current state within the mission. Robot navigation for indoor and outdoor autonomy is guaranteed through SOTA control [Santamaria-Navarro25]. The designed semantics enriches robot autonomy and context awareness by providing task and motion planning with context parameters suitable to tailor performance, navigation modalities, and data acquisition sampling and/or quality according to the mission needs [Singamaneni24]. Similarly, the mission task planner would contribute to the distributed situation awareness by dispatching notifications about the state of task execution and robot state to the different human actors involved in the disaster management.

4.4.1 Review of state-of-the-art methods

Robotics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) are two research areas that historically addressed the challenge (among others) of building embedded intelligent systems capable of acting in a real-world environment [Rajan17]. Recent advancements in Robotics and AI are pushing the design and deployment of autonomous robots in increasingly complex/unstructured environments. On the one hand, technological advancements concerning the increased reliability and efficiency of sensing devices, manipulation and navigation skills of robots, as well as solving and predictive capabilities of AI technologies, open new opportunities for the effective deployment of Robotics and AI solutions. On the other hand, the increased complexity of application scenarios raises new technical/methodological challenges. A tight integration of Robotics and AI is crucial to enhance the autonomy and control capabilities of robots and allow them to safely and reliably act in the real-world [Ingrand17, Ghallab14]. In particular, robots acting in the real world should take into account several non-functional qualities that are crucial to realize behaviors that are safe and acceptable with respect to humans [Dautenhahn06, Rossi17], [Bruno19]. Robot controllers should therefore evolve towards an advanced “Perception, Reason, Act” paradigm implementing the cognitive capabilities needed to synthesize and execute flexible behaviors that are valid from both a technical and social point of view. To implement the envisaged cognitive control paradigm, we found particularly promising the integration of ontology-based reasoning with AI-based planning and robot control. The integration of semantic technologies with robot controllers has been widely studied in the literature [Manzoor21].

Ontologies have been recognized as true enablers of adaptable and flexible systems compared to classic approaches [Turaga08, Chandrasegaran13]. Robot-integrated ontology-based reasoning has, in particular, shown effective results in the enhancement of robot flexibility and awareness [Lemaignan17, Borgo19, Bessler18]. This section discusses some relevant works in the literature concerning the integration of ontology-based knowledge reasoning, planning, and robotics. It shows the enhanced flexibility and awareness of robots acting in different domains, thanks to the integration of the mentioned technologies.

KnowRob [Beetz18, Tenorth17] is a well-known framework supporting advanced Perception, Reasoning, and Control. The framework provides robots with a logical representation of a number of entities ranging from robotic parts and objects (with their composition and functionalities) to tasks, actions, and behaviors. This framework in particular focuses on manipulation tasks and allows robots to perceive objects of the environment, reason about their functionalities (e.g., formal description of affordances of objects [Bessler20]), and decide how to use them within planning actions [Bessler18], [Diab20]. Although general, KnowRob is mainly suitable for dealing with scenarios where a single robot manipulates objects and interacts with an environment. The dyadic nature of HRC scenarios requires reasoning on simultaneous executions of actions and the synergetic combination of robotic and human actors. An ontological model characterizing object manipulation tasks of robots has also considered within the PMK framework [Diab19]. Similar to KnowRob [Beetz18], PMK supports a standardized representation of the environment, defining a common language to exchange information between a human and a robot. It characterizes causal information and constraints about manipulation tasks well and defines knowledge that is useful at both the task and motion planning levels. The work [Suh07] exploits a robot knowledge framework (OMRKF) consisting of a series of ontology layers, including a robot-centered and human-centered ontology. The system in particular relies on an object layer, a context layer, and an activity layer to abstract gathered sensor data. However, this framework lacks a foundational background, which limits the reliability of inferred knowledge. Furthermore, it

does not distinguish between activity and functionality, resulting in a rigid characterization of robot capabilities and behaviors. For example, avoiding obstacles is not a behavior but a function that can be implemented in different ways, e.g., moving away or turning around. An interesting framework concerning the ontological description and integration of robotic skills is SkiROS [Rovida17]. Less general than KnowRob, this framework is designed on ROS to propose an ontological model of robot skills. On top of this knowledge, action-based planning supports a dynamic combination of skills to realize complex behaviors. Similar to KnowRob [Tenorth17], SkiROS focuses on the description/control of a single robot acting in the environment. The Open Robots Ontology (ORO) framework [Lemaignan10] develops a knowledge reasoning framework endowing robots with common sense reasoning capabilities to autonomously operate in semantically-rich human environments. With respect to KnowRob, the ORO framework addresses the control problem from a cognitive perspective and realizes a general cognitive architecture deployed on different robotic platforms and assessed on different cognitive scenarios [Lemaignan10]. This architecture has been specifically developed to support advanced cognitive skills (e.g., theory of mind capabilities) and thus support increasingly flexible and adaptive HRI [Lemaignan17].

Concerning HRI, knowledge representation, and reasoning have been used to realize socially compliant behaviors. Non-functional requirements like those regarding social norms are crucial to realize acceptable behaviors [Rossi17]. For example, the work [Awaad15] uses knowledge reasoning to represent social norms and allow a social robot to implement socially acceptable behaviors for social tasks. More specifically, the work proposes a formal description of the functional affordances of objects to reason about their possible use and thus infer those that are suitable to accomplish the requested social task (i.e., serving coffee to guests using the right object). The work [Bruno19] proposes the use of knowledge reasoning to adapt HRI to the cultural knowledge of different contexts and people. This is another example of how ontology-based reasoning can enhance context awareness of robots. In this case, reasoning capabilities evaluate non-functional qualities of HRIs and synthesize socially compliant behaviors. The work [Chang20], similar to other mentioned works, e.g., KnowRob [Tenorth17], proposes an ontological model characterizing users, the interacting environment, capabilities (not necessarily correlated to the robot only), and tasks. On top of this model, the work instantiates a cognitive architecture realizing a perceive, reason, act control loop. The resulting cognitive agent incrementally decides which social task to perform according to the perceived state of the interaction context. An added value of [Chang20] is the explicit representation of interacting users through user profiles that support personalized services.

Ontology-based reasoning has also been used in medical scenarios. The work [Prestes13] proposes the use of ontology in orthopedic surgery. The ontological model OROSU integrates and shows domain knowledge to different types of users uniformly, e.g., surgeons, nurses, or technicians, during surgery. It relies on KnowRob [Tenorth17] to describe surgical procedures concerning hip surgery. Finally, ontology-based reasoning has also been used to formally represent normative standards and evaluate compliance with them. An example is the work [Ribino21] where normative standards for indoor environmental qualities have been encoded into an ontological model. A social robot has been endowed with cognitive capabilities to ground detected quality conditions of an environment and automatically evaluate the compliance of a perceived environment with the normative standards.

4.4.2 Implemented solutions

TRIFFID extends an ontology specifically designed for situation awareness [Kokar09] with a semantic model of robot tasks [Schlenoff05] to detect critical situations and contextually reason about possible

tasks to be executed. On the one hand, we use the ontology to semantically enrich perception data and dynamically build the knowledge graph characterizing the current state of the mission and the whole monitored environment. On the other hand, the ontology enables logic-based reasoning suitable to infer situations, events (e.g., smoke, human body found, building infrastructure conditions), characterize mission contexts (e.g., preparation, monitoring, intervention), and prioritize suitable mission tasks. The next sections describe: the main concepts introduced into the designed ontological model; the data processing pipeline designed to ground perception labels to the ontological model; a prototype implementing the logic-based reasoning detecting relevant situations and prioritizing mission tasks.

4.4.2.1 Ontology representation of capabilities, events and tasks

Considering efforts on the ontological formalization of robot domains and situation awareness, a model capable of capturing the abstraction process and contextually characterizing information at different levels of abstraction is missing. One of the objective of TRIFFID is thus design a formal model suitable to: (i) semantically capture states, risks and human-related features of objects detected in the environment; (ii) capture capabilities and mission-level skills and responsibilities of heterogeneous resources ranging from human operators to autonomous artificial agents; (iii) characterize patterns of information to abstract critical/relevant situations and contextually prioritize opportunities of tasks. In this regard, the designed ontological model relies on a context-based approach supporting a flexible interpretation of environmental data and a contextual abstraction of situations and tasks to be performed. The model relies on a solid theoretical background provided by SOTA foundational ontologies. Foundational ontologies aim at describing reality from a high-level perspective in order to define concepts that are general enough to be valid across many domains. Their use is generally recommended and represents a good design choice to base new (more specific) ontological models on well-structured semantics. These ontological models constitute a stable theoretical background of more specific ontologies and thus foster a clear structuring and disambiguation of domain concepts [Jansen11], [Mascardi07]. Several foundational ontologies have been introduced in the literature, e.g., BFO [Otte22], DOLCE [Borgo22], or SUMO [Nikes01]. Among these, the TRIFFID ontology relies on DOLCE [Borgo22] in order to support a flexible interpretation of temporally evolving entities and, also, to rely on a recognized standard representation framework (ISO 213838-3). DOLCE, therefore, represents a flexible model, well-suited to support the interpretation of domain entities whose state depends on the context and may change/evolve. On top of the foundational layer, TRIFFID defines three main representational contexts that encapsulate, respectively: (i) the environment perspective; (ii) the situation perspective; (iii) the task perspective. Each context characterizes a coherent set of knowledge. The distinction among these three contexts also characterizes the data processing and abstraction pipeline necessary to realize proactive and contextual notifications and inference of task opportunities. The interoperability among the three contexts is thus crucial to effectively support the abstraction process and bridge the representational gap between physical entities of the environment and task requirements to coherently and timely respond to threats and risky situations.

First, the ontology defines the environmental context to characterize the relevant entities that are part of the modeled production environment. This layer is particularly critical since it defines the ground language and thus the low-level entity that the TRIFFID system is concretely able to recognize and reason about. Therefore, entities that could not be expressed within the environmental context would not *exist* inside the knowledge framework and would not be taken into consideration by the reasoning and abstraction processes. Figure 84 below shows an excerpt of the concepts that have been defined, and thus that can be recognized by the perception processes developed within TRIFFID. These concepts

are introduced as specialization DOLCE:PhysicalObject. As such, following the general structuring of DOLCE, they are tangible entities associated with DOLCE:Quality that are expressed within some DOLCE:Region of space. Namely, environmental objects would be characterized by general qualities like Longitude and Latitude, determining their spatial identification and localization within the monitored geographic area. More specific concepts can be further classified according to specific qualities that characterize them. For example, structural objects would be static and have some level of stability and safety concerning the risk of collapse. Other objects, like fire and smoke, could be dynamic and thus characterized by a changing behavior of their qualities (e.g., the area affected by a fire could grow) and represent a threat to the safety of humans. Other objects, like a human body or a school, could be static or dynamic entities that directly correlate with human beings and thus could be characterized by a higher priority or relevance in the monitoring process.

Figure 84 Classes of physical entities that could be part of a rescue scenario

The list of classes of the environment context would anchor the perceived entities to the ontology and the resulting knowledge graph. Depending on the accuracy of the perception module and the ambiguity of the used class labels, the ontological concepts defined are not strictly disjoint and would present intersections of individuals. For example, depending on the accuracy of the perception and the conditions under which perception occurred, an object could be generally classified as a building or more specifically as a school. The knowledge graph could therefore contain individuals that are instances of both classes, and this should not generate an inconsistency within the reasoning and abstraction process. Rather, the more precise the classification of the entity, the more detailed and informed the abstraction process. Each ontology class of the environment context is associated with textual descriptions through metadata properties. A rich description of such classes is crucial to correctly support the anchoring of the labeled classes, as it will be described in the next sections.

Figure 85 Types of rescue tasks according to [Schlenoff05]

To characterize the types of tasks that a generic agent can perform within a rescue mission, we considered the high-level taxonomy proposed by [Schlenoff05]. Figure 85 illustrates an excerpt of the ontology, highlighting the integrated taxonomy of rescue tasks. The taxonomical concepts are introduced as a specialization of RescueMethod that in turn specializes DOLCE:Method. As such, the concept characterizes general descriptions of procedures that would thus be implemented by means of properly instantiated and planned actions (types of DOLCE:Event). This is to clarify that this part of the context characterizes the procedural knowledge of the mission. It is necessary to contextually associate detected objects of the environment, their states, and relations with the tasks that could be performed. In other words, this concept formally characterizes the requirements and preconditions that would enable the execution of some mission tasks. Multiple instances of mission tasks would then be implemented and executed by grounding the procedural description to environmental objects (e.g., specific types of objects to be monitored or inspected). In this regard, it is also crucial to formally characterize the operational requirements of such methods in terms of the necessary agents' capabilities. Following previous works [Umbrico24], the ontology introduces the concept of Capability as an operational DOLCE:Quality of an agent. In this way, agents can be classified in terms of their functional qualities (i.e., capabilities) and detect the subset of RescueMethod each agent can actually perform. This knowledge is then used within the abstraction process to detect the agents that can concretely support a mission and the subset of suitable tasks. Figure 4 Figure 85 shows an excerpt of the ontology concerning the relations between types of agents and tasks.

Figure 86 Classification of agents and their associations with mission tasks

4.4.2.2 Ontology anchoring of perception labels

The ontology model serves as the formal language and the semantics guiding the data processing and abstraction process. Figure 87 shows a schematic flow from raw data about objects, tagged with labels, to the definition of a checklist ranking mission-level tasks that can be performed in the current context. The steps involved in the process can be summarized as follows:

- **Perception layer:** Detect and tag objects in the environment.
- **WordNet semantic mapping:** Normalize labels and extract hypernyms and relations.
- **Ontology layer (Apache Jena):** Map labels to ontology individuals and classes.
- **Semantic gloss similarity (Word2Vec / embeddings):** Infer ontology classes from gloss definitions if label mapping is ambiguous.
- **Reasoning layer:** Run an Web Ontology Language (OWL) reasoner to infer hierarchy, relations, and situations.

- (Optional) **BabelNet/ConceptNet enrichment**: Check common sense relation to further classify or infer relevant knowledge (e.g., the fact that the fire is dangerous)
- **Logic-based reasoning**: Ontology-based logic reasoning to abstract situations and infer suitable tasks that can be performed

Figure 87 Schematic flow of the abstraction process of labeled environment objects

Within the depicted process, the mapping of labeled objects to ontological concepts (anchoring) is particularly crucial to instantiate and maintain the knowledge graph semantically describing the mission context. This step specifically associates detected objects with knowledge individuals, classified according to the performed tagging. A correct retrieval of ontological concepts and association with perception labels is paramount to enable reasoning over environmental objects. To automate the anchoring, TRIFFID leverages existing and reliable semantic services supporting common sense reasoning and semantics. Specifically, the mapping between the ontological classes and perception labels relies on the WordNet lexical database¹⁶. Given a perception label, WordNet is queried to retrieve glossary definitions containing synonyms and a natural language description of the concept. Such synonyms and the textual description are then used to identify the best matching ontological class. The textual description from WordNet and the descriptions of the ontological classes (metaproperties) are mapped to embeddings through Word2Vec to compute cosine similarity and identify the ontological class description that is semantically closer to the label. Once the class has been identified, the Apache Jena library¹⁷ is then used to manipulate the knowledge graph and create the individuals and the associated information in compliance with the underlying semantic formalism (e.g., instances of qualities such as Geographic Information System (GIS) data of objects in terms of latitude and longitude). Furthermore, once a semantic label has been detected, additional services could be integrated to further acquire useful information about an entity. Services like ConceptNet¹⁸ could be used to integrate common sense knowledge and retrieve relations that could be useful within the reasoning. For example, the concept Fire is commonly recognized as “dangerous to humans”¹⁹, and suitable properties could be automatically retrieved and used within the inference.

4.4.2.3 Logic-based reasoning for contextual support to decisions

The process depicted in the previous section generates and maintains a semantically rich knowledge graph that characterizes mission contexts by inferring the types of entities and relations to humans. A logic reasoner further refines the knowledge by inferring risk-related situations and opportunities of

¹⁶ <https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>

¹⁷ <https://jena.apache.org>

¹⁸ <https://conceptnet.io>

¹⁹ <https://conceptnet.io/c/en/fire>

tasks. Figure 88 shows the internal elements of the contextual reasoner, with the logic reasoner process processing knowledge to rank situations and produce prioritized lists of tasks.

Figure 88 Structure of the contextual reasoner of TRIFFID

This section briefly describes the main elements of a Prolog²⁰ prototype developed to test and assess the feasibility of the envisaged reasoning. Figure 89 shows part of the Prolog program asserting facts concerning the detected objects of the environment. Rows 5-6 assert the data about the environmental entities detected with IDs, Latitude, and Longitude coordinates. Properties about these objects (identified by their symbols - IDs) are asserted according to the inferred ontological classes (e.g., building(), fire(), human()). These properties provide object symbols with semantics and are then considered within the reasoning mechanism.

```

1 % -----
2 % Dataset: Simple representation of objects received from Semantic Map
3 % entity(ID, Lat, Lon).
4 % -----
5 entity(school, 45.4642, 9.1900). % building detected
6 entity(body, 45.4650, 9.1915). % Person detected
7 entity(fire, 45.4700, 9.2000). % Fire detected
8 entity(smoke, 45.4600, 9.1950). % Smoke detected
9
10 % Semantic classification of entities
11
12 threshold(school, 0.3).
13 threshold(fire, 2.0).
14 threshold(smoke, 0.1).
15
16 building(school).
17 human(body).
18 fire(fire).
19 smoke(smoke).
20
21 % Classify building status according to perception
22 unsafe(school).
23

```

Figure 89 Logic Program, part 1/5

As Figure 90 shows, the logic program could also include common-sense knowledge concerning the types of objects. Logic rules would, for example, infer properties further classifying objects as related

²⁰ <https://www.swi-prolog.org>

to humans and as dangerous to humans, with a certain level of risk. Interestingly, as shown in rows 62-63, the computation of risk could be parametrized according to the types of entities involved. In the shown example, fire would be attributed with a risk level higher than the one attributed to unsafe buildings. Although this is an example, risk assignment would be easily modified according to the preferences of domain experts.

```
58 % Classify entities related to humans
59 related_to_human(Entity) :- entity(Entity, _, _), building(Entity).
60 related_to_human(Entity) :- entity(Entity, _, _), human(Entity).
61
62 % Classify of dangerous entities and risk level
63 dangerous(Entity, R) :- entity(Entity, _, _), fire(Entity), !, R is 10.0.
64 dangerous(Entity, R) :- entity(Entity, _, _), building(Entity), unsafe(Entity), R is 5.0.
```

Figure 90 Logic Program, part 2/5

In addition to object knowledge, Figure 91 shows that the logic program would include facts about known agents (rows 26-28), mission-level tasks (rows 31-38), and agents' capabilities in terms of tasks they can perform. Specifically, the logic program would contain the outcomes of the knowledge reasoning processing agents' capabilities with the ontological descriptions of known tasks.

```
25 % Data about acting robots that could be deployed to perform tasks
26 agent(uav).      % UAV
27 agent(ugv).      % UGV
28 agent(operator). % Operator(s)
29
30 % Constants representing types of tasks from taxonomy
31 task(reconnaissance, 1.0).
32 task(search, 2.0).
33 task(assessment, 3.0).
34 task(stabilization, 3.0).
35 task(medical, 5.0).
36 task(rescue, 9.0).
37 task(monitors, 6.0).
38 task(materials, 3.0).
39
40
41 % specify tasks the UAV can do
42 canDo(uav, reconnaissance).
43 canDo(uav, monitors).
44 canDo(uav, materials).
45
46 % specify tasks the UGV can do
47 canDo(ugv, search).
48 canDo(ugv, assessment).
49 canDo(ugv, monitors).
50 canDo(ugv, materials).
51
52 % specify tasks the Operator(s) can do
53 canDo(operator, medical).
54 canDo(operator, stabilization).
55 canDo(operator, rescue).
56
```

Figure 91 Logic Program, part 3/5


```

66 % -----
67 % Haversine formula for geodesic distance
68 % -----
69 deg2rad(Deg, Rad) :-
70     Rad is Deg * pi / 180.
71
72 haversine_distance((Lat1,Lon1), (Lat2,Lon2), D) :-
73     deg2rad(Lat1, RLat1),
74     deg2rad(Lon1, RLon1),
75     deg2rad(Lat2, RLat2),
76     deg2rad(Lon2, RLon2),
77     DeltaLat is RLat2 - RLat1,
78     DeltaLon is RLon2 - RLon1,
79     A is sin(DeltaLat/2)**2 +
80         cos(RLat1) * cos(RLat2) * sin(DeltaLon/2)**2,
81     C is 2 * atan2(sqrt(A), sqrt(1-A)),
82     EarthRadiusKm is 6371,
83     D is EarthRadiusKm * C.
84
85 % -----
86 % Predicate true if two entities are near of D kilometers, within a threshold,
87 % -----
88 near(Entity1, Entity2, D) :-
89     entity(Entity1, Lat1, Lon1),
90     entity(Entity2, Lat2, Lon2),
91     Entity1 \= Entity2,
92     haversine_distance((Lat1,Lon1), (Lat2,Lon2), D),
93     threshold(Entity2, Thresh), % threshold depends on entity2 type
94     D < Thresh.

```

Figure 92 Logic Program, part 4/5

Figure 92 shows further reasoning on the data associated with the detected entities. In the example, the logic program could process GIS data and compute the distance between distinct pairs of entities, see the procedure `near(Entity1, Entity2, D)` rows 88-94. This information is especially useful to parametrize the level of risk and priorities of tasks. Figure 93 shows an example of a rule that can be defined to infer the level of risk represented by a human-related entity (E1) near a dangerous entity (E2). Specifically, the rules weight the computed risk according to the distance between the two entities E1 and E2. Consider, for example, the case in which E1 is a human body and E2 is some fire detected. Intuitively, the risk of a human close to the fire would be proportional to the distance between them. Similarly, row 104 shows a rule inferring opportunities for task execution by taking into account the tasks each agent can perform and the inferred threat situations. The priority of each opportunity would be proportional to the risk of the addressed threat situation. The rule shown is an initial example, which could be further refined by modeling the types of threats “targeted” by each task to better evaluate the different situations.

```

96 % -----
97 % Semantic rule: classify a threat when something related to humans is close to something dangerous
98 % -----
99 threatenedBy(E1, E2, R) :- related_to_human(E1), dangerous(E2, Rd), near(E1, E2, D), R is Rd * D.
100 %threatenedBy(E1, E2, R) :- dangerous(E2, R), near(E1, E2).
101
102
103 % infer task opportunity with priority directly proportional to risk
104 opportunity(T, A, E, P) :- task(T, Pt), canDo(A, T), threatenedBy(E, _, R), P is R * Pt.
105 %opportunity(T, A, E) :- dangerous(E), building(E), agent(A), canDo(A, T).
106

```

Figure 93 Logic Program, part 5/5

4.5 Speech analysis and verbal human robot interaction

The domain of Urban Search and Rescue (USAR) robotics is historically characterized by the deployment of teleoperated mechanical platforms designed to penetrate environments that are too hazardous for human entry. They focused primarily on mobility and visual inspection, treating robots

as a passive tool for situational awareness. However, as robotic platforms achieve greater autonomy and physical capability, interaction emerges as the principal factor influencing mission success.

High-risk operational environments frequently impose severe constraints on perception and mobility, where visual channels become unreliable and physical interaction with interfaces is limited. Human operators are often engaged in demanding tasks and may be restricted by equipment or environmental conditions, reducing the feasibility of manual or visual control mechanisms. In this context, voice becomes the most efficient, high-bandwidth, and hands-free interface available.

Moreover, verbal communication has the potential to enable more intuitive and efficient interaction between FRs and robotic systems, reduce operator workload, and support time-critical decision-making in high-stress environments, by enabling rapid task specification and adaptive behavior without relying on manual controllers or line-of-sight interfaces.

Verbal interaction with civilians represents a complementary dimension of HRI, where the objective is not operational control but communication, reassurance, and support during highly stressful and often disorienting situations. Studies in emergency-response robotics show that spoken dialogue can help stabilize civilian behavior, provide clear procedural instructions, and facilitate rapid triage by enabling robots to gather essential information about injuries, symptoms, or immediate needs. These studies also highlight that civilians frequently rely on robots for guidance when human responders are not immediately available, and that well-designed verbal communication can help maintain calm, provide orientation, and support decision-making under stress.

In TRIFFID, speech processing and LLM-enabled verbal HRI support the interpretation of basic spoken commands under harsh operating conditions. These capabilities allow FR crew members to issue natural-language instructions to the UGV and enable the system to perform verbal assessments of the needs of potentially stranded civilians, resulting in more context-aware robot behavior within complex and dynamic disaster environments.

Verbal HRI is built on a set of complementary components and methodologies that together provide the required interaction capabilities. The following sections review the relevant state of the art across these components, outlining the methods, architectures, and datasets that inform the development of TRIFFID's verbal HRI stack.

4.5.1 First responder robot interaction

Verbal interaction between FRs and robots spans a broad spectrum of communicative functions, from simple spoken triggers to fully contextualized instructions. At the lower end of this spectrum, speech functions as a direct control interface, where short, operationally critical commands must be detected with minimal latency and executed without ambiguity. At the upper end, beyond predefined commands, spoken instructions may encode spatial references and temporal dependencies. In these cases, the robot must interpret natural language in conjunction with its perceptual state, ongoing actions, and the surrounding operational context. This enables more adaptive forms of interaction in which the robot can adjust its behavior and align its actions with the responder's intent and situational requirements.

4.5.1.1 Relevant public datasets

General-purpose spoken/natural language understanding datasets

General-purpose SPLU/NLU datasets are designed for task-oriented dialogue and provide explicit, schema-based semantic annotations. Semantics are encoded through intent labels, slot/value pairs, and sometimes frame-like hierarchical structures, enabling supervised training of semantic parsing models but without reference to perception or physical environments. On the other hand, robotics-oriented SPLU/NLU datasets must explicitly encode the crucial link between language and the physical world, moving beyond abstract semantic schemes to address the symbol grounding problem. These multimodal resources are structured to couple linguistic commands with sensor observations (e.g., 3D coordinates, visual states) and associated robot control signals.

Table 31 Summary of the available datasets regarding SPLU/NLU

No	Dataset	Year	Source	Domain	Classes	Samples	Annotation
1	NLU-Benchmark [Liu21B]	2021	Crowd	General	64 intent, 54 entities	25,716	Crowd
2	NLU++ [Casanueva22]	2022	Crowd	Banking, hotels	62 intent, 17 entities	3,080	NLU experts
3	MASSIVE [FitzGerald23]	2023	Crowd	General	60 intent, 55 slots	1 million	Manual annotation

NLU-Benchmark [Liu21B] provides a collection of 25,716 user utterances annotated with 64 intents and 54 entity (slot) labels across 21 task-oriented domains. It contains manually curated and corrected utterances collected via Amazon Mechanical Turk, encompassing a wide range of domains such as alarm, calendar, IoT, music, weather, email, takeaway food, and transportation.

NLU++ [Casanueva22] is a multi-domain, multi-label dataset developed to address limitations of traditional task-oriented NLU corpora, especially the restricted slot diversity and domain generalisation issues. It contains 3,080 utterances spanning two dialogue domains (BANKING and HOTELS), each annotated with multi-label intents and a rich set of 17 slots. Utterances are annotated using a modular approach where "intent modules" are combined to express complex, simultaneous communicative goals. The ontology is strategically divided into domain-specific and generic modules to promote cross-domain generalization. The dataset is constructed through a combination of crowdsourcing, domain-specific prompt design, and expert annotation to ensure semantic consistency across domains. The publication introduces several baseline models, including BERT-based multi-label intent classifiers and joint transformers for intent–slot prediction.

MASSIVE [FitzGerald23] is a large-scale multilingual NLU dataset created to support cross-lingual and multilingual semantic parsing research. It contains 1 million utterances mapped to 60 intents and 55 slot types, covering 51 typologically diverse languages. All utterances originate from a single English seed set of task-oriented commands, which was translated and validated using a multi-stage pipeline involving professional translators and automated consistency verification.

Given these conclusions on the available datasets, and to facilitate their comparison, Table 31 summarizes their main properties.

Command detection datasets

Google Speech Commands [Warden18] dataset contains 105,829 one-second WAV recordings of 35 isolated words, produced by 2,618 speakers. The dataset includes a fixed training/validation/test split defined via deterministic hashing of file names, ensuring stable comparisons across models. The vocabulary includes digits, control words (“yes”, “no”, “up”, “down”, “stop”, “go”), and “confusing” distractor words (“tree”, “cat”, “house”), along with several minutes of labeled background noise.

Recordings were collected through a web-based microphone interface using the WebAudio API. Contributors read randomized prompts in natural acoustic conditions through consumer microphones. A multi-stage cleaning pipeline was applied onto the raw audio including automatic filtering, temporal alignment (aligning the keyword to the center of a 1-second window) and crowdsourced manual verification. The paper provides reproducible baselines for CNN, DNN, and RNN architectures trained on log-Mel features. The dataset became the standard for evaluating DS-CNN, TC-ResNet, MobileNet-KWS, and subsequent TinyML models.

SiDi KWS dataset [Maneses22] is a public large-scale multilingual dataset currently composed of 24.3 million audio recordings, which corresponds to which 791 thousand represent unique keywords. The recordings that compose that dataset were extracted from popular public transcribed speech datasets (i.e., LibriSpeech [Panayotov15], Mozilla Common Voice [Ardila19] and MultiLingual LibriSpeech [Pratap20]). Given the original speech audio files and their transcriptions, the segmentation of the single keywords was performed via forced alignment, by using the public tool Montreal Forced Aligner [McAuliffe17]. Forced Alignment refers to the task of aligning a speech recording with its phonetic transcription, which is subsequently used to isolate the exact acoustic region corresponding to each keyword.

SynTTS-commands [Gan25] is a fully synthetic multilingual dataset generated to support training and evaluation of on-device keyword-spotting models. It comprises over 110 hours of speech corresponding to 384,621 utterances across 48 command classes in English and Chinese. All audio was synthesized using the CosyVoice 2 [Du24] text-to-speech system. Speaker diversity is achieved through zero-shot voice cloning, with speaker embeddings drawn from VoxCeleb 2 [Chung18], resulting in more than sixteen thousand synthetic speakers. Command sets were defined for typical voice-assistant control domains, and acoustic variation was introduced by modifying parameters such as pitch, speaking rate, and SNR.

Table 32 Overview of publicly available datasets for command detection

No	Dataset	Year	Source	Environment type	No. Classes	No. Samples
1	Google Speech Commands [Warden18]	2018	Phone & laptop microphones	Noisy indoor environments	35	105,829
2	SiDi KWS dataset [Maneses22]	2022	Public transcribed speech datasets	General	791	24,329,253
3	SynTTS-Commands [Gan25]	2017	Synthetic	General	48	384,621

Situation aware human-robot interaction datasets

ALFRED [Shridhar20] is a benchmark for learning a mapping from natural language instructions and egocentric vision to sequences of actions for household tasks. ALFRED includes 25,743 english language directives describing 8,055 expert demonstrations averaging 50 steps each, resulting in 428,322 image-action pairs. These directives contain both high-level goals like “Rinse off a mug and place it in the coffee maker.” and low-level language instructions like “Walk to the coffee maker on the

right.” Each directive includes a high-level goal and a set of step by-step instructions. Each expert demonstration can be deterministically replayed in the AI2-THOR 2.0²¹ simulator.

	Pick & Place	Stack & Place	Pick Two & Place	Clean & Place	Heat & Place	Cool & Place	Examine in Light
item(s)	Book	Fork (in) Cup	Spray Bottle	Dish Sponge	Potato Slice	Egg	Credit Card
receptacle	Desk	Counter Top	Toilet Tank	Cart	Counter Top	Side Table	Desk Lamp
scene #	Bedroom 14	Kitchen 10	Bathroom 2	Bathroom 1	Kitchen 8	Kitchen 21	Bedroom 24
expert demonstration							

	Annotation # 1	Annotation # 2	Annotation # 3
Goals	Put a clean sponge on a metal rack.	Place a clean sponge on the drying rack	Put a rinsed out sponge on the drying rack
Instructions	Go to the left and face the faucet side of the bath tub. Pick up left most green sponge from the bath tub. Turn around and go to the sink. Put the sponge in the sink. Turn on then turn off the water. Take the sponge from the sink. Go to the metal bar rack to the left. Put the sponge on the top rack to the left of the lotion bottle.	Turn around and walk over to the bathtub on the left. Grab the sponge out of the bathtub. Turn around and walk to the sink ahead. Rinse the sponge out in the sink. Move to the left a bit and face the drying rack in the corner of the room. Place the sponge on the drying rack.	Walk forwards a bit and turn left to face the bathtub. Grab a sponge out of the bathtub. Turn around and walk forwards to the sink. Rinse the sponge out in the sink and pick it up again. Turn left to walk a bit, then face the drying rack. Put the sponge on the drying rack.

Figure 94 Overview of ALFRED task types and annotation structure

The ALFRED benchmark facilitates the development of embodied agents by demanding the joint, co-attentive encoding of visual and linguistic modalities to generate executable action sequences. The model architecture proposed by the authors is designed to entangle the hidden representations of the egocentric visual stream (processed by a CNN) with the natural language instructions (processed by an LSTM). This continuous fusion process, often managed by soft-attention mechanisms weighted by the decoder’s hidden state, allows the agent to dynamically prioritize language tokens relevant to the current visual observation and environmental state.

The NatSGD [Shrestha24] dataset is designed to bridge the gap between multimodal HRI commands and complex, executable robotic policies in intricate domains like food preparation and cleaning. The dataset couples natural human commands in both speech and gestures directly with synchronized, demonstrated robot trajectories as the supervisory signal. The dataset provides rich, multi-perspective data streams essential for learning grounded, multimodal policies.

Figure 95 Overview of the NatSGD experimental setup

²¹ <https://ai2thor.allenai.org/>

NatSGD defines two benchmark tasks that operationalize multimodal policy learning. The first, language-and-gesture-based instruction following, represents the core imitation-learning objective in the dataset, where models receive natural spoken commands together with human gestures and must map this multimodal input directly to the demonstrated action trajectory. The second benchmark, Human Task Understanding, targets symbolic goal specification, where natural multimodal instructions are translated into Linear Temporal Logic formulas, yielding a structured and machine-executable representation of long-horizon task intent.

PARTNR [Chang24] dataset is a large-scale benchmark designed to evaluate embodied planning and multi-agent reasoning in realistic HRC scenarios. It contains 100,000 natural-language task instructions instantiated across 60 richly populated, multi-room homes featuring 5,819 unique objects, accompanied by evaluation functions (predicate-based programs that assess task completion). Tasks span everyday household activities and emphasize challenges central to collaborative autonomy, including spatial reasoning, temporal ordering, constraint satisfaction, and heterogeneous agent capabilities. A central challenge addressed by PARTNR is the problem of grounding natural-language, long-horizon tasks into 3D, partially observed, multi-agent environments. To support this, the benchmark evaluates several distinct grounding methodologies. The primary grounding mechanism for LLM-based planners in PARTNR is a privileged, fully observed textual world graph. This representation is a hierarchical, symbolic encoding of the full 3D scene state. Each node is annotated with semantic category labels, continuous 3D metadata such as positions and bounding boxes, and object specific state variables. This graph is directly injected into the LLM prompt and serves as an explicit grounding substrate that affords high-fidelity spatial and semantic queries. Because the graph captures the complete geometric and relational state of the environment, the planner can perform deterministic high-level reasoning. In contrast to privileged grounding, PARTNR also evaluates perception-driven grounding using ConceptGraphs, which approximate environment state exclusively from RGB-D sensory observations. As the agent navigates and interacts, ConceptGraphs incrementally build an open-vocabulary 3D scene graph through category prediction, geometric reconstruction, and canonicalization of object instances. Together, these grounding methodologies make PARTNR a focused setting for analysing how embodied agents integrate environmental information and coordinate with human partners. Given these conclusions on the available datasets, and to facilitate their comparison, Table 33 summarizes their main properties.

Table 33 Summary of the available datasets regarding situation-aware HRI

No	Dataset	Year	Environment type	Domain	Tasks	No. Samples	Annotation
1	ALFRED [Shridhar20]	2020	AI2-THOR 2.0 simulator	Household activities	7 tasks, 84 objects	25,743	Expert demonstrations
2	NatSGD [Shrestha24]	2024	Unity3D custom simulator	Household activities	11 actions, 8 objects	1,143	NLU Experts
3	PARTNR [Chang24]	2024	Habitat 3.0	Household activities	5,819 objects, 7 linguistic types	100,000	LLMs, simulation, and expert demonstrations

While the datasets presented in this section do not constitute SLPU/NLU benchmarks in the traditional sense (where the objective is often explicit text decoding or slot-filling) they fundamentally address the challenge of Embodied Grounding. In these environments, language is not a static input to be parsed, but a dynamic signal to be mapped to physical actions and spatiotemporal constraints. Consequently, deep learning architectures trained on these datasets implicitly perform a pragmatic form of NLU. They learn to fuse linguistic information with robot perception to produce latent representations that are semantically rich and can provide executable outputs in the physical world.

4.5.1.2 Command detection

Command detection (or alternatively keyword spotting) in speech-based HRI relies primarily on two methodological approaches. The first is closed-vocabulary spoken command detection, in which a model directly maps short audio segments to a predefined inventory of command classes and rejects non-command audio. The second is ASR-based command detection, in which a general-purpose speech recognition model produces textual hypotheses or latent representations that are subsequently searched for target keywords. Closed-vocabulary systems offer low computational cost and deterministic behaviors, whereas ASR-based methods enable greater linguistic flexibility and open-vocabulary operation.

Closed-vocabulary spoken command detection

A modern deep keyword spotting system pipeline is composed of three main blocks: 1) the speech feature extractor converting the input signal to a compact speech representation, 2) the deep learning-based acoustic model producing posteriors over the different keyword and filler (non-keyword) classes from the speech features and 3) the posterior handler processing the temporal sequence of posteriors to determine the possible existence of keywords in the input signal [Lopez21]. Most prominent approaches included fully connected DNNs, RNNs and CNN-based model architectures (DS-CNN, TC-ResNet, small-footprint CNN variants) for acoustic modeling. The frame-level posterior probabilities output by the acoustic model are temporally unstable due to noise, speaker variability, and non-stationarity of speech. To come up with a final decision about the presence or not of a keyword in an audio stream, the sequence of posteriors needs to be processed. Posterior smoothing applies a convolutional or sliding-window filter over the posterior sequence to suppress short-lived spikes and reinforce consistent activations. Dynamic thresholding adapts the decision boundary based on background posterior statistics. Other approaches include Voice Activity detection (VAD) gating, where a VAD module suppresses posterior evaluation during non-speech segments.

Transfer learning has emerged as a highly effective strategy for enhancing closed-vocabulary performance, especially in low-resource conditions. Wav2KWS [Seo21] demonstrates that Wav2Vec 2.0 [Baevski20], pretrained via a self-supervised contrastive objective on tens of thousands of hours of unlabelled speech, provides representations with strong phonetic granularity and robustness to acoustic distortions. In this method, the Transformer encoder is either frozen or partially fine-tuned, while a lightweight classifier is appended for the mapping of contextualised embeddings to keyword classes. Wav2KWS reports state-of-the-art performance on Google Speech Commands V1/V2, outperforming CNN baselines. The study shows that leveraging contextualised speech embeddings stabilises learning, reduces overfitting, and enhances generalisation across speakers and environments.

Query-by-Example (QbE) Keyword Spotting facilitates user-defined command vocabularies without the need for model retraining. In contrast to standard approaches of closed-set vocabulary, QbE systems project user-provided enrollment examples into an embedding space and detect keywords via distance-

based similarity metrics. A prominent realization of this paradigm is presented in the work on Parnami et al. [Parnami22], where a neural encoder is optimized via metric learning to map audio segments into a discriminative vector space. During the enrollment phase (introduction of unseen command classes), a class 'prototype' is constructed by simply averaging the embeddings of a few user-provided support samples. Consequently, detection during inference is reduced to a nearest-neighbour search between the incoming query and these prototypes, effectively bypassing the need for gradient-based updates or fine-tuning.

Automatic speech processing for command detection

ASR-based architectures decouple acoustic modelling from keyword detection, treating the latter as a lexical search problem over ASR outputs. Rather than optimizing a dedicated classifier, the ASR backbone generates 1-best hypotheses (the single most probable word sequence generated by the decoder) or word lattices (directed acyclic graph where nodes represent time boundaries and edges represent word hypotheses weighted by model probabilities) and detection is executed via contextual biasing, substring matching or semantic similarity scoring. This approach inherently supports open-vocabulary keyword spotting and leverages the strong linguistic priors of large-scale ASR models.

Contextual biasing is the problem of modifying an ASR system's decoding process so that hypotheses containing a given set of context-relevant words or phrases receive extra score (positive bias). Weighted Finite-State Transducers (WFST) approaches implement contextual biasing by augmenting or rescaling the decoding graph so that paths containing contextually relevant words are preferred [Aleksic15]. Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) based systems apply contextual biasing within their prefix search procedure. Because CTC decoding operates on partial prefixes rather than full word hypotheses, contextual information is used to adjust scores as prefixes begin to resemble items from the bias list [Fox22]. Sequence-to-sequence models generally employ beam-search-driven [Beam] contextual biasing, where bias terms are introduced directly into the hypothesis scoring stage. Rather than manipulating graphs or prefix structures, these models track how closely each beam candidate matches any phrase in the bias list and add a score bonus to those that do [Wang23F].

4.5.1.3 Spoken language understanding

SPLU extends beyond command detection by extracting structured semantic information from natural language utterances. Formally, given an input audio sequence X , the goal is to predict the user's intent I (a global classification label) and a sequence of semantic slots S (local argument spans typically via BIO or IOB formatting²²). In more complex scenarios, this evolves into semantic parsing, where the system maps the utterance to a logical form or machine-understandable representation. In contrast to ASR, which outputs a sequence of lexical tokens, SPLU requires the model to identify what the speaker is trying to achieve (e.g., issuing a command, asking a question, providing information) and which entities or parameters are relevant to that meaning.

As noted in the survey by Qin et al. [Qin21], the literature can be categorized along two orthogonal axes:

- Task coupling: Whether intent detection and slot filling are modeled independently or via Joint Task Modeling.

²² [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inside%E2%80%93outside%E2%80%93beginning_\(tagging\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inside%E2%80%93outside%E2%80%93beginning_(tagging))

- Modality integration: Whether the system operates on ASR-generated text (Cascaded/Pipeline) or optimizes the mapping from audio to semantics directly (End-to-End).

In the cascaded paradigm, SPLU is treated as a downstream NLU task operating on ASR transcripts. Historically, ID and SF were treated as separate problems, sentence classification and sequence labeling, respectively, which ignored the strong statistical coupling between intents and their arguments.

Modern text-based systems overwhelmingly adopt Joint Task Modeling. As detailed by Qin et al., these architectures utilize a shared encoder to learn a unified representation, branching into task-specific heads only at the final layers. A representative state-of-the-art architecture is JMBSF (Joint Model based on BERT with Semantic Fusion) by Chen and Luo [Chen23B]. Their architecture processes tokenized text through a BERT backbone. Crucially, rather than relying solely on the final hidden state, JMBSF introduces a Semantic Feature Fusion layer. This aggregates representations from multiple BERT layers to capture complementary linguistic features (e.g., combining low-level syntax with high-level semantics). The architecture couples the tasks explicitly: the slot-filling head (typically a Conditional Random Field (CRF)) and the intent classification head are optimized via a joint loss function. While highly effective on clean text, these models suffer from error propagation, as they are conditioned on immutable, potentially erroneous ASR hypotheses.

To mitigate the impact of recognition errors without abandoning the modular structure of pipelines, recent works have introduced differentiable neural interfaces. This approach, exemplified by FANS [Radfar21] (Fusing ASR and NLU), replaces the discrete "hard text" bottleneck with a "soft" hidden representation. Rao et al. [Rao20] demonstrate that by connecting a shared audio encoder to parallel NLU decoders (for intents and slots) via continuous vectors, the system can be trained end-to-end. This allows the NLU components to be exposed to recognition ambiguity (ASR confusions) during training, thereby improving robustness. End-to-End aims to map directly to semantics ($X \rightarrow I, S$), bypassing the text generation step entirely. Haghani et al. [Haghani18] formalized this domain by evaluating sequence-to-sequence architectures ranging from direct semantics prediction to multi-task setups. Their findings established that architectures that retain an internal transcript representation (via multi-task learning or intermediate supervision) consistently outperform those that do not. The most recent evolution in SPLU leverages large-scale self-supervised FMs. WhiSLU [Wang23G] adapts the Whisper ASR model by casting SPLU as a sequence generation task, concatenating transcripts and semantic labels into a single output string.

Concurrently, Agrawal and Ganapathy [Agrawal25] explored the zero-shot capabilities of Speech-Text LLMs. They introduced Symbol Fine-Tuning, a technique where the model is trained to map audio-text pairs to randomized symbolic outputs. This process teaches the model generic "slot-filling mechanics" without overfitting to a specific ontology, enabling rapid adaptation to unseen SPLU tasks via in-context prompting alone. This marks a shift toward Task-Agnostic SPLU, where a single generic model can replace bespoke architectures for specific domains.

Zero-shot SPLU aims to extract semantic structures (intents I and slots S) from utterances in novel domains without task-specific labeled data. Unlike classic supervised approaches, which rely on large, annotated corpora to learn statistical dependencies, zero-shot methods exploit the general linguistic knowledge encoded in LLMs or the cross-modal alignment in Speech-Text FMs. A recent realization of this approach is GPT-SLU [Zhu24B], which reformulates the SPLU task as a Schema-Guided Question Answering (QA) problem. To emulate the cross-task coupling of supervised joint models, GPT-SLU employs a decomposition-and-refinement prompting strategy. In the first stage, the LLM infers intents and slots independently, while in the second, these initial predictions are fed back into the

prompt as context. This "mutual guidance" allows the predicted intent to constrain slot extraction (and vice versa) purely through inference-time reasoning.

4.5.1.4 Situation-aware human-robot interaction

One fundamental challenge in situation-aware HRI is the symbol grounding problem, which requires the mapping of abstract linguistic symbols to perceptual representations of the physical environment and continuous action primitives. Blukis et al. [Blukis22] proposed Hierarchical Language-conditioned Spatial Model (HLSM), a hierarchical approach that uses a spatial semantic representation of the world from robot observations as a long-term memory to solve long-horizon tasks Figure 96.

Figure 96 HLSM architecture with observation model and hierarchical controllers

The persistent spatial semantic representation is a 3D voxel map that retains spatial properties and object relations observed over time. This representation acts as a long-term memory that supports a hierarchical policy: a high-level controller that generates subgoals, and a low-level controller that generates sequences of actions to accomplish them. A subgoal g is a tuple $(\text{type}, \text{arg}^C, \text{arg}^M)$, where type is an interaction type (e.g., OPEN, PICKUP), arg^C is the semantic class of the interaction argument (e.g., SAFE, CD), and arg^M is a 3D mask identifying the location of the argument instance. High-level controller at timestep t , when invoked for the k -th time, the input to high-level controller is the instruction L , the sequence of past subgoals and the current state representation. The output is a probability over subgoals for the next subgoal.

Figure 97 The high-level controller architecture

The architecture of the High-Level Controller (Figure 97) processes heterogeneous inputs into compact vector representations using three distinct encoders: a language encoder, a state encoder and a subgoal history encoder. State Encoder: The 3D semantic voxel map V_t is condensed into a state embedding ϕ_t . This is achieved by performing a max-pooling operation over the spatial dimensions of the map to identify the presence of object classes, which is then concatenated with the agent's inventory vector v_t (indicating what object class the agent is holding at timestep t). Language Encoder: The natural language instruction L is processed by a fine-tuned BERT model. The system uses the CLS token embedding as the global task embedding ϕ_L . Subgoal History Encoder: To enable temporal reasoning, the sequence of past subgoals is processed by a two-layer Transformer autoregressive encoder. This produces a history embedding ϕ_{k-1g} that captures the sequential context of the task execution. To determine what action to take next, the controller concatenates the three embeddings and passes them through a dense MLP. To ground the action spatially, the chosen argument class is used to "slice" the semantic map; this slice is combined with state affordances and history features to create a bird's-eye view representation. Finally, this representation is transformed to the agent's egocentric frame and processed by the REFINER (LingUNet) [Misra18] to generate a precise 3D argument mask, completing the subgoal tuple.

Modern architectures have shifted toward leveraging massive vision-language pre-training, such as CLIPort [Shridhar22] to project language and visual inputs into a shared embedding space, enabling robots to resolve complex referring expressions (e.g., "the block closest to the gripper") in a zero-shot manner without explicit object detection models. This grounding extends beyond static objects to action parametrization, where verbs must be translated into kinematic constraints.

Furthermore, situational awareness requires temporal grounding to resolve the mismatch between dynamic language and static perception. Human instructions frequently reference past states (e.g., "go back to where you saw the mug") or future conditions, which traditional SPLU pipelines operating on single-frame snapshots fail to process. In practice, constructing a world model that tracks the metric-semantic states of all of the entities in the robot's workspace over an extended period of time and performing grounding inference in its context is computationally expensive and therefore prohibits effective HRC in non-trivial dynamic environments.

A representative line of work addresses this by a learned model of language and perception that facilitates the construction of temporally compact but semantically sufficient models of dynamic worlds. Patki et al. [Patki23] propose Language Guided Temporally Adaptive Perception (LGTAP), where the utterance is used to infer (i) which perceptual classifiers are relevant and (ii) an initial temporal window over observations, after which a grounding step is executed on the resulting compact world model. If the inferred groundings do not match the expected semantic structure of the utterance, the system expands the temporal bounds and re-runs grounding until constraints are satisfied or history is exhausted.

Rahman et al. [Rahman24] extend this paradigm to instructions that require future grounding. Their architecture generalizes the "temporal bounds" concept so that the environment model can be extended backward and/or forward in time depending on linguistic cues and introduces a Perception/Simulation component that simulates the future state of only those objects deemed relevant by language, and only when future-directed semantics are present.

Finally, temporally grounded instruction following benefits from episodic memory mechanisms that support reliable access to past events, especially for retrospective queries or instructions that depend on previous interactions. Bärman et al. [Bärman25] focus on episodic memory verbalization and propose

a hierarchical episodic history tree that compresses long multimodal experience streams into multiple abstraction levels, from raw observations and robot state up to events, goals, and recursively generated summaries. An LLM agent is used to interactively expand and search the tree, retrieving only the relevant temporal segments to answer questions such as last-seen object locations or action outcomes at particular times.

4.5.2 Civilians robot interaction

LLM-enabled verbal communication must support two core requirements: (a) reliable verbal assessment of stranded civilians in uncertain, safety-critical environments, and (b) alignment with human-factors to ensure safe, predictable, and context-appropriate interaction. These needs map directly to three major research domains: LLM alignment and safety, which provides mechanisms ensuring that model outputs remain harmless, honest, and policy-conformant; RAG-based grounding, which ensures that responses are actionable and anchored to verified information rather than hallucinated content; and agentic AI, which structures LLMs into controllable workflows capable of multi-step reasoning, tool use, and decision support.

4.5.2.1 Alignment and safety methods for LLMs

Lu et al. [Lu25] provide a comprehensive taxonomy of alignment methodologies designed to ensure that LLM outputs respect safety, helpfulness, and honesty objectives. These methodologies can be categorized into Training-Phase Alignment (establishing behavior) and Inference-Time Controls (guiding behavior).

Techniques adhering to training-phase alignment modify the model's internal parameters to fundamentally shape how it processes and generates responses. Supervised Fine-Tuning (SFT) acts as the foundational step for instruction following. By training the model on curated datasets of safe demonstrations and ideal responses, core behavioral priors can be established, such as clarity, polite refusals, and consistency. Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) extends SFT by introducing a feedback loop based on human preferences. A separate "reward model" is trained to grade responses (e.g., distinguishing safe outputs from unsafe ones), and the LLM is fine-tuned to maximize these scores. This approach is currently the dominant industrial method because it allows models to navigate nuanced, context-dependent safety situations that static datasets cannot capture. Emerging as a robust alternative to RLHF, Direct Preference Optimization (DPO) treats alignment as a supervised contrastive problem. Instead of training a complex separate reward model, DPO optimizes the model directly based on preferred versus dispreferred outputs. This reduces computational complexity and improves training stability, making it highly attractive for iterative deployment in safety-critical applications.

Complementing parameter-level training, prompt engineering functions as a vital inference-time control layer that enhances honesty and safety without modifying the model's weights. This approach primarily relies on system-prompt and role design to encode high-level interaction policies.

4.5.2.2 LLM response grounding

LLM groundedness refers to the architectural capacity of a model to anchor its generated outputs in verifiable, external evidence rather than relying solely on its internal, pre-trained parametric memory.

The primary mechanism for achieving this is RAG [Gao23], which introduces a non-parametric memory layer by retrieving relevant data chunks from an external source. In a standard RAG workflow,

the system encodes a user's query into a high-dimensional vector space and performs a semantic similarity search against a vector database, injecting the top-matching text segments into the model's context window to serve as the factual basis for the response.

While standard RAG is effective for local query-answer tasks, it often treats retrieved segments as isolated islands of information, failing to capture the global structure or interdependencies within acknowledge base. To address this, GraphRAG (Graph Retrieval-Augmented Generation) enhances groundedness by structuring the external knowledge base into a knowledge graph, where entities are nodes and their relationships are edges. This allows the retrieval mechanism to traverse connections between disparate concepts, enabling the model to perform multi-hop reasoning and answer complex questions.

Extending the principles of GraphRAG, ROG [Luo23] represents an evolutionary step from passive retrieval to active, planned reasoning over structured knowledge. By grounding the generation in these explicitly traced valid reasoning paths, the model shifts from merely synthesizing retrieved text to executing verifiable, multi-hop logic, significantly enhancing both the faithfulness of the answer and the interpretability of its derivation.

4.5.2.3 LLM agents and agentic workflows

Based on the conceptual framework proposed by Xi et al. [Xi25], the evolution of LLMs into autonomous agents represents a structural shift from passive text generation to active system control, defined by a “bionic” architecture comprising three core components: the Brain, Perception, and Action.

In this model, the Brain serves as the CPU where the LLM is responsible not only for language processing but for high-level cognitive functions, including knowledge storage in memory (parametric memory), complex reasoning, and the generation of executable plans to solve open-ended problems.

This cognitive core is supported by a Perception module that extends the agent’s sensory capabilities beyond text, utilizing multimodal encoders to translate visual, auditory, and other environmental data into unified representations that the model can process.

Consequently, the agent bridges the gap between internal reasoning and external effect through the Action module, which interfaces with tools, APIs, and physical actuators to execute specific tasks rather than simply outputting tokens.

4.5.3 Sound and speech analysis engine

In this section, the current status of the work on environmental sound analysis and speech processing for HRI is presented. The focus is on the design and implementation of the TRIFFID Sound/Speech Analysis Engine as a ROS 2 package (Figure 98) that enables both perception of the acoustic environment and verbal interaction with FRs and civilians. The architecture is designed to support three distinct, concurrent operational capabilities:

- SED: A continuous acoustic monitoring pipeline responsible for classifying non-speech events (e.g., alarms, glass breaking, machinery noise). This component provides the robot with environmental situational awareness, allowing the navigation stack to react to acoustic anomalies independent of verbal input.
- Deterministic command recognition: An open-vocabulary Keyword Spotting (KWS) system that detects a set of configurable navigation and operation commands with high recall.
- SPLU: A dialog system designed for complex HRI.

During the initial reporting period, development focused on architectural validation with the following primary objectives:

- System interoperability: To deliver a stable interface that ensures seamless message exchange with the wider TRIFFID architecture via ROS actions.
- Extensibility and modularity: To implement a configuration-driven codebase that decouples audio processing logic from specific model backends. This design allows for the seamless interchange of inference engines (e.g., swapping ASR or SED models) and permits independent experimentation.

Future development phases will transition from architectural integration to inference optimization, specifically targeting latency reduction, resource efficiency on edge hardware, and domain-specific fine-tuning of the underlying DL models.

Figure 98 Sound and speech engine ROS2 package

Audio capture

To support the full development lifecycle, from offline benchmarking to deployment, the node is implemented utilizing python-sound device²³ to support three distinct input configurations:

- Simulation mode (wav file): This mode ingests pre-recorded .wav files and streams them at real-time. This is critical for regression testing and validating the pipeline against ground-truth datasets without hardware variance.

²³ <https://python-sounddevice.readthedocs.io/en/0.5.3/>

- Standard interface (monophonic microphone): This mode interfaces with standard devices for single-channel capture, enabling development on generic hardware such as laptops and standard USB microphones.
- Deployment Interface (ReSpeaker microphone array): The node is specifically configured to interface with the ReSpeaker Mic Array, the target sensor for the UGV. This configuration a) handles the specific sample rate and channel mapping requirements of the sensor and b) consumes and propagates the results of the sensor embedded DSP capabilities.

Raw audio is continuous, but deep learning models require discrete, fixed-length tensor inputs. Audio capture node implements a sliding overlapping window mechanism to bridge this gap. The overlap is necessary due to the risk of sound events spanning over sequential buffers if arbitrary segmentation is implemented. It ensures that every acoustic feature appears in the center of at least one frame, preserving signal quality and ensuring "boundary invariance" for the downstream SED and ASR nodes.

To avoid "clock drift," where the time a message is processed differs significantly from when the physical event occurred, Audio Capture Node encapsulates raw audio data into a custom `AusioSegment` ROS message enriched with traceability metadata. Key metadata fields include:

- `capture_wall_time`: The precise nanosecond-resolution timestamp when the audio block entered the hardware buffer. This remains immutable as the message traverses the ROS graph.
- `UUID & sequence_num`: A unique identifier and a monotonically increasing sequence number for every segment.
- `source_info`: Metadata indicating whether the stream originated from live hardware or a specific simulation file.

All segmentation outputs are logged via `rosviz`, enabling the replay of specific acoustic scenarios for post-processing analysis and model fine-tuning.

Sound event detection

The SED node functions as the system's environmental sound analysis component, operating in parallel with the speech analysis pipeline. Its primary objective is to provide non-verbal auditory cues of possible hazardous sound events (such as alarms, glass breaking or debris falling) and also indications of trapped victims, that are critical for autonomous navigation and situational awareness. SED node utilizes a distilled version of an AST model fine-tuned on AudioSet dataset. Knowledge Distillation (KD) is a model compression technique where a small, efficient "student model" is trained to emulate the behavior of a large, high-performing "teacher model". The core of the method involves using the teacher's full probability distribution (soft targets), rather than just the hard ground-truth labels, as the supervisory signal. This ensures that the node retains high classification accuracy while significantly reducing the inference latency and memory footprint required on the edge computing hardware.

Voice activity detection

Continuous ASR inference is prohibitively expensive. Without VAD, the ASR engine would attempt to transcribe silence or background noise, leading to two modes of failure:

- Resource saturation: Wasting GPU/NPU cycles on null data.
- Hallucination: Generative ASR models (like Whisper) often "hallucinate" strings when forced to transcribe silence or non-speech noise.

This node is essentially performing VAD Gating by analyzing incoming audio buffers to distinguish human speech from silence or background noise, preventing irrelevant data from "polluting" the downstream, computationally intensive ASR queues.

The current implementation is utilizing NVIDIA's MarbleNet [Jia21]. It is a frame-based model that outputs a speech probability for each 20-millisecond frame of the input audio. The model has 91.5K parameters, making it lightweight and efficient for real-time applications.

Speech recognition

To achieve near-real-time performance without offloading data to the cloud, this node utilizes faster-whisper²⁴, a reimplement of OpenAI's Whisper model using CTranslate2²⁵ library. To prevent blocking the ROS 2 executor loop, the inference workload is offloaded to a dedicated background thread. The main thread handles ROS callbacks and buffering, while the worker thread consumes the audio queue. While the VAD node filters silence upstream, the ASR node requires a more sophisticated accumulator to handle "utterance windows" that preserve context. It buffers incoming chunks and applies a secondary, rule-based endpoint detection (silent tail of audio signal) logic to determine when to terminate inference and flush the buffer.

- The **streaming ASR node** (agreement policy) receives partial transcription outputs from the upstream speech recognition node and applies LocalAgreement-2 policy [Liu20], a streaming policy that outputs the longest common prefix of the model on n consecutive source chunks, or an empty segment when less than n chunks are available.
- The **command detection node** is responsible for recognizing a predefined, closed set of navigation commands. At the moment two interchangeable backends have been developed: a decoding-based Keyword Spotting (KWS) system and a text-based matching system. Audio-Based Keyword Spotting implementation treats command detection as a tiny ASR problem focused solely on a set of target keywords. The system leverages a beam search decoder over ASR output, enhanced by specific keyword-boosting parameters (Hotwords Contextual Biasing). The second implementation utilizes the validated transcripts received from the upstream ASR pipeline and performs exact and fuzzy matching at the normalized text. This method sacrifices the extremely low latency of direct audio KWS for the increased accuracy offered by the larger ASR model's context.
- The **LLM agent node** is responsible for two main functionalities: a) performing verbal assessment of the needs of potentially encountered stranded civilians and b) providing adaptive robot response to HRI inputs, utilizing TRIFFID's Semantic Map. The agent's reasoning processes is implemented using LangGraph²⁶, enabling the creation of complex, stateful workflows. A foundational dialogue agent has been successfully integrated to validate the end-to-end processing pipeline. This Proof-of-Concept establishes the necessary interfaces, demonstrating the system's capability to ingest live transcripts and synthesize coherent initial responses within the ROS 2 framework. The next development phase will focus on evolving this component into a stateful, reasoning agent. Development will center on implementing symbol grounding, allowing the agent to query TRIFFID's semantic map to ensure verbal outputs are factually consistent with the environment.

²⁴ <https://github.com/SYSTRAN/faster-whisper>

²⁵ <https://github.com/OpenNMT/CTranslate2/>

²⁶ <https://www.langchain.com/langgraph>

Additionally, specific interaction protocols will be developed to facilitate the verbal assessment of stranded civilians, enabling the robot to autonomously triage needs based on dynamic HRI inputs.

- **Text-to-Speech node** closes the HRI loop by converting the textual responses generated by the LLM agent into audible speech waveforms. Coqui TTS²⁷, a SOTA open-source deep learning library for text-to-speech synthesis, has been utilized to provide onboard speech generation capabilities for the UGV. Its lightweight inference engine enables the system to run entirely on the vehicle's hardware, ensuring that verbal interaction remains functional even in communication-denied environments. On top of that it utilizes neural vocoders to generate natural-sounding prosody and intonation, which is critical for maintaining user trust and clarity during high-stress interactions with civilians. The node subscribes to the response topics published by the LLM agent. Upon receipt of a text payload, it performs low-latency inference to synthesize the corresponding audio, which is then routed to the robot's hardware speakers.

4.5.3.1 Acoustic sensor and raw audio input digital signal processing

TRIFFID will utilize ReSpeaker v2.0 (Figure 99) as its acoustic sensor mounted on the UGV, which integrates a circular array of four high-performance digital microphones.

Figure 99 Seeed studio ReSpeaker mic array v2.0

Unlike a standard omnidirectional microphone which captures sound with equal gain from all directions, a microphone array consists of multiple microphones arranged in a known geometric configuration. Because each microphone receives the same sound wave at slightly different times and intensities, the array provides spatial information that a single microphone cannot capture. This spatial information enables a range of advanced signal-processing techniques, including beamforming, direction-of-arrival estimation, sound source localization and tracking, dereverberation, and spatial noise reduction. In practice, microphone arrays can enhance a desired source, suppress interfering noise, estimate where a sound is coming from, or reconstruct a spatial acoustic scene. The XMOS chipset on the ReSpeaker provides a suite of onboard DSP algorithms that condition the signal before it reaches the sound/speech analysis module, namely:

- **Acoustic echo cancellation:** Removes the audio signal played back by the robot's own speakers from the input stream. This allows the robot to "listen" while "speaking" (barge-in capability) without feedback loops.

²⁷ <https://github.com/coqui-ai/TTS>

- Beamforming: Automatically steers the sensitivity lobe of the array towards the active speaker, improving the SNR of the target voice.
- Noise suppression: Applies spectral subtraction to reduce stationary background noise (e.g., fan hum or wind).
- Direction of arrival: continuously calculates the angle (0° - 360°) of the incoming sound source.

5 Intuitive AR-based human-computer interfaces

5.1 Balance between situational awareness and cognitive load

In such augmented reality (AR) applications, the objective is to maintain an optimal balance between the user's awareness of the operational environment and their cognitive effort in processing information. For FRs and mission operators, this means being able to perceive, interpret, and act upon spatial information quickly, without being overwhelmed by visual elements.

The prototype follows an adaptive and minimalist design philosophy supported by Cognitive Load Theory, which suggests that interfaces must minimize extraneous load to prevent performance declines in high-pressure scenarios. Both in desktop and AR modes, the interface provides only the essential interaction elements, such as loading and navigating the scene, and highlighting key Points of Interest (POIs) detected by UAVs and UGVs. Research on emergency response indicates that providing such a “detail-in-context” view significantly improves situational awareness (SA) by helping operators construct a more accurate mental model of the remote environment [Bakzadeh25].

To strictly enforce these objectives, the interface design aligns with fundamental human-computer interaction (HCI) principles, particularly Nielsen's Usability Heuristics [Nielsen94]. The adoption of MRTK 3²⁸ strengthens these principles in practice by providing a unified interaction framework across mixed reality modalities. Through its standardized input system, spatial user interface (UI) components, and well-established interaction patterns, MRTK 3 ensures consistency and standards, significantly reducing the operator's learning curve during high-pressure situations.

Additionally, by explicitly highlighting POIs and presenting contextual information directly within the user's field of view, the system prioritized recognition rather than recall. This design choice reduces the operator's cognitive burden, allowing them to allocate mental resources to situational assessment and decision-making rather than navigating or remembering interface elements. Combined with real-time visual feedback and clear system status indicators, the interface adheres to core usability heuristics that support fast, error-resistant interaction in mission-critical settings.

This visualization strategy directly enhances coordination by establishing common ground, a shared mental model required to coordinate interdependent actions. By visualizing the disaster environment in 3D, the system serves as a cognitive artifact that facilitates mutual understanding between the operator and field teams. Virtual reality (VR) technologies eliminate geographical barriers, enabling remotely distributed personnel to experience the same scenario simultaneously, which is critical for mitigating the performance degradation caused by the stress of facing unfamiliar environments [Migliorini21]. Consequently, the interface supports performance quality, as evidence suggests that high-fidelity computational simulations allow operators to better comprehend the complexity of disaster scenes, such as collapsed buildings or fire hazards [Zhu21D].

As this is an early prototype, further refinements and additions will be made following feedback sessions with FRs, focusing on improving usability, cognitive ergonomics, and the integration of adaptive visualization techniques. These evaluations will guide the next development cycle toward a

²⁸ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/mrtk-unity/mrtk3-overview/>

more user-centered design that maximizes HRC efficiency and validates the benefits of augmented remote collaboration.

5.2 Real-time dynamic map updates

The Unity AR dashboard is built to stay in sync with an evolving 3D environment, not by loading a single static map at mission start, but by continuously incorporating new Gaussian Splatting reconstructions as they arrive [Kerbl23]. From the frontend’s perspective, the system behaves like a live “map feed” [Huang25C]: the client maintains a persistent connection (via WebSockets) and receives event-driven update messages whenever a new model or model patch becomes available [Wang25E]. Each update includes the data needed to apply it safely at runtime (binary payload and/or remote reference) plus lightweight descriptors such as the update timestamp, the update’s spatial extent (bounding region), and basic integrity/quality flags. This enables the AR dashboard to visualize the latest available geometry with minimal operator intervention and without disruptive reloading cycles.

5.2.1 Unity update process for stable augmented reality

A key frontend requirement is that map updates must not destabilize AR tracking or overlays. To achieve this, the Unity client treats reconstruction updates as content changes that occur within a stable world frame, rather than as a full scene reset. The dashboard keeps a persistent “Map Root” transform (aligned to the AR session’s anchor / world origin strategy) and applies updates beneath that root so that:

- Existing AR UI elements and overlays remain anchored and readable.
- Spatial alignment stays consistent as models are replaced or refined.
- The operator’s viewpoint doesn’t “jump” when new geometry arrives.

This flexibility lets the dashboard remain responsive: operators can keep working while updates stream in, and the client can prioritize what matters right now rather than loading everything.

Finally, the Unity client is designed to fail softly. If updates arrive late, out of order, or are temporarily unavailable, the dashboard can keep the latest known map active. This ensures the AR dashboard remains operational through intermittent connectivity and variable update rates.

5.2.2 Frontend rendering and performance

Because Gaussian Splatting can be dense, the Unity client manages both GPU memory and frame time carefully. Typical frontend strategies include:

- Binary decoding optimized for runtime: parse compact model payloads into Unity-native buffers (compute buffers / native arrays) with minimal allocations.
- LOD and density throttling: dynamically reduce splat count or shading complexity based on device capability and current FPS.
- Background loading: stream and prepare new chunks while keeping the current map active, then promote the update only when safe.

The result is that the visualization remains interactive even during frequent updates.

On the dashboard UI, live updates should be visible and understandable, not silent or confusing. The frontend surfaces map state with clear, low-friction indicators such as:

- Freshness state: Live / Syncing / Stale / Offline

- Last update timestamp and source (e.g., UAV identity or stream label)

These UI cues help operators trust the visualization and understand whether an area is fully reconstructed or still evolving.

5.2.3 Non-visual cues integration

The Unity frontend also supports mission-relevant annotations that evolve alongside the map. Non-visual cues (GPS/IMU tracks, LiDAR-aligned references, detected acoustic events, hazard markers, etc.) are treated as spatial layers anchored to the same coordinate frame as the 3DGS map. In practice, this means the dashboard can render event markers with time windows (e.g., “impact detected at T+03:12”) that remain pinned to the correct location. Because these overlays are layered above the reconstructed scene and updated independently, they remain usable even while the underlying geometry is being refined.

5.3 Implemented solution

The developed system is a PC-based mixed reality application built with Unity. The Unity engine is selected as it provides stability and wide compatibility with modern VR hardware. The application is capable of running on desktop computers connected to VR headsets such as Meta Quest 3 via Link²⁹, allowing immersive visualization while maintaining high computational performance. This specific setup is selected as it allows an intuitive and real-time interaction between the user and the simulated environment.

It visualizes 3D environmental data reconstructed through Gaussian Splatting (Figure 100), leveraging an open-source rendering framework in Unity [Kleinbeck25] as its foundation. This framework builds upon the “Toy Gaussian Splatting” visualization tool [Pranckevičius23], extending the original codebase with specific modifications to the shaders and the rendering pipeline to ensure seamless compatibility with VR interfaces.

²⁹ <https://www.meta.com/help/quest/1517439565442928/>

Figure 100 Image of the 3D map with the functionalities

For performance optimization, the application runs entirely on the PC, rather than as a standalone headset build. This approach allows the rendering workload to be handled by the host GPU (Figure 102), ensuring higher frame rates, improved memory management, and greater visual integrity compared to standalone AR execution. The reconstruction of large-scale disaster environments involves rendering millions of Gaussian Splats. Processing such a high-density dataset directly on a standalone headset is sub-optimal due to the limited GPU throughput and memory constraints of the mobile processors (Figure 101). A detailed experimental analysis supporting these findings is presented in Section 5.4.

Figure 101 FPS and memory allocation based on the VR headset

Figure 102 FPS and memory allocation based on the PC

A minimal graphical user interface (GUI) is available in both desktop and AR modes, providing essential functionality for loading, navigating, and interacting with the 3D scene. The control panel is designed as a floating menu within the environment. Crucially, to prevent visual obstruction during critical observation tasks, the menu is not statically fixed. The operator can instantly toggle its visibility or summon it to a comfortable interaction distance using dedicated buttons on the touch controllers. In that way, it remains accessible to the operator without obstructing the primary field of view, allowing the operator to focus entirely on the 3D environment.

When active, the menu, as can be seen in Figure 104, comprises five core functions essential for mission management:

- **Load:** Once the user triggers the “load” command from the interface, the corresponding dataset is automatically fetched and visualized from the server without requiring local file selection, making it possible for near real-time integration of newly reconstructed data generated by UAV and UGV subsystems.
- **Remove:** Clears the currently visualized dataset from the active scene, leaving the main menu. This function allows the operator to instantly declutter the view or prepare the system for loading a new 3D map without requiring a full application restart.
- **Reset:** Restores the visualization and user orientation to their default states. This is particularly useful for resetting the interaction parameters to their baseline values.
- **Panoramic View:** Toggles the visualization between a focused mode and an expanded view. By default, the system employs a masking technique to restrict the visual field to a specific central area, aiming to reduce cognitive load by filtering out peripheral distractions. Activating this function removes the mask, exposing the broader environmental map. However, this feature is currently in an early experimental stage. The trade-off between utility and information overload is under review, with the feature’s final inclusion subject to user validation.
- **Filters:** Open a submenu for managing visual layers. This function allows the operator to selectively toggle the visibility of specific POIs, such as fire hazards, smoke, or detected civilians, thereby sticking to the principle of displaying only task-relevant information (Figure 103).

Figure 103 Image of the filter menu with some illustrative POIs based on the corpus

From an implementation perspective, the GUI was constructed using the MRTK3, offering a familiar interaction scheme for VR users. The main control panel and the filters submenu leverage the “Near Menu” prefab to facilitate intuitive near-field interactions.

Figure 104 Main menu displayed from the VR headset

To facilitate intuitive exploration of the reconstructed environment, users can navigate the 3D map using the controller's analog sticks, utilizing smooth locomotion for continuous movement and snap turning for discrete rotation. This implementation aims to maximize navigation efficiency while mitigating potential motion sickness, a known limitation of VR movement mechanisms identified in disaster risk reduction simulations [Migliorini21].

Furthermore, the interface empowers the operator to manipulate the 3D map structure directly. Users can rescale, rotate, and translate the model in real-time to inspect specific areas of interest from optimal angles.

At this stage, the system represents a functional prototype that demonstrates the feasibility of real-time visualization for the ground-station operator. Further iterations will incorporate user feedback from FRs to refine the interface design, extend multi-platform support and integrate additional functionalities in future versions.

To complement the desktop and VR headset implementations, a mobile AR interface is under design. Given the computational limitations (Figure 105), the evidence from the experimental evaluation in Section 5.4 and field-user requirements of mobile devices, this view is expected to present a 2D or semi-AR map representation of the same dynamic 3D data, allowing rapid situational overview and interaction on-site.

Figure 105 3D map displayed in mobile showing FPS and memory usage

5.4 Experimental evaluation

Experimental setup

To determine the optimal deployment platform for the developed visualization system, a comparative performance study was conducted across three distinct hardware configurations:

- Mobile device
- AR headsets (Meta Quest 3)
- Desktop

The primary metric for evaluation was FPS, which is critical for ensuring user comfort and interaction flexibility, particularly in immersive environments (VR/AR).

The benchmark scene utilized for this evaluation was a high-fidelity 3D reconstruction based on Gaussian Splatting, comprising a total of **1.144.277 splats**. This specific dataset was selected as it serves as a representative demonstration of a complex disaster environment, effectively capturing the unstructured geometry, debris fields, and dense spatial details typical of real-world emergency scenarios. Furthermore, the spatial extent of the reconstructed area provides a realistic approximation of a field operations zone, ensuring that the performance benchmarks reflect the scale of data expected in actual emergency response missions (Figure 106).

Rendering was performed using the open-source Unity Gaussian framework by [Pranckevičius23]. As specified in this implementation, efficient rendering depends heavily on compute-shader-based rasterization. Therefore:

- Mobile and standalone VR deployments rely on Vulkan, due to API support for compute operations.
- Desktop deployment utilizes DirectX 12 to maximize GPU throughput.

Figure 106 Image of the 3D map inside the Unity Editor

The hardware specifications and graphics APIs utilized for each test case are detailed below:

Table 34 Comparative performance analysis across different hardware architectures

Machine	GPU	Graphics API	Average FPS
Mobile (Samsung S4 FE)	Samsung Xclipse 940	Vulkan	<= 7
VR Headset (Meta Quest 3)	Adreno (TM) 740	Vulkan	<= 9
Desktop	NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 Ti	DirectX 12	= 72

Performance analysis and limitations

The **mobile platform**, utilizing the Samsung Xclipse 940 GPU via the Vulkan API, demonstrated insufficient performance for real-time interaction, achieving a maximum of 7 FPS. At this performance level, real-time interaction is not feasible. The combination of high splat count and compute-heavy rasterization results in GPU saturation, making the mobile platform unsuitable for dense semantic map visualization using full 3DGS.

As a **standalone VR headset** Meta Quest 3 was used (equipped with the Adreno 740 GPU) and yielded similarly poor results, capping at 9FPS or below. In VR, low frame rates (below 72Hz) are a primary cause of motion sickness (simulator sickness). While standalone execution offers portability, the current hardware cannot handle the rendering load of large-scale disaster reconstructions. However, it is theoretically possible to run lighter scenes on the headset, provided the dataset is optimized. Research indicates that performance in Gaussian Splatting is linearly dependent on the number of splats. For instance, scenes with up to 400k can maintain stable frame rates (approximately 72 FPS on mid-range hardware), but performance degrades sharply as the splat count increases beyond this threshold [Pranckevičius23]. Given that disaster scenes often require millions of splats for accurate detail, standalone rendering remains a bottleneck.

Finally, the **Desktop** configuration, powered by an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 Ti using DirectX 12, achieved a stable 72 FPS (matching the refresh rate cap of the tethered headset used in the experiment).

The desktop GPU possesses the necessary CUDA³⁰ cores and memory bandwidth to handle the sorting and rasterization of massive Gaussian Splat datasets in real-time. This confirms that a PC (via Link) app is currently the only viable solution for high-fidelity, large-scale emergency visualization.

Concluding, the experimental results dictate the architectural decisions for the system prototype. While mobile and standalone VR platforms offer deployment flexibility, their current inability to render complex Gaussian Splat scenes at acceptable frame rates excludes them from being the primary visualization nodes for semantic mapping. Consequently, the system adopts a PC-based processing model, where the heavy rendering workload is offloaded to a powerful host machine, streaming the result to the VR headset. This ensures a stable more than 72 FPS, guaranteeing operator comfort and the precise visualization required for critical decision-making; hence, simpler representation, visualization and abstraction schemes are foreseen to be developed.

³⁰ <https://developer.nvidia.com/cuda/>

6 Conclusions and future work

The current document has presented the initial outcomes of WP4. It demonstrates the progress made to achieve robust perceptual and multimodal understanding and interactive abilities to enable autonomous robotic systems to behave appropriately in post-disaster conditions. WP4 tasks laid down a strong methodological and experimental foundation responsive to the defined objectives, in order to facilitate the FR's time-critical duties inside the field of operations.

The aforementioned objectives include the systematic evaluation of SOTA ground-level and EO-based perception methods. The extensive experimental results reported in this deliverable provide clear insights into the trade-offs between accuracy, robustness, and computational efficiency across CNNs, transformer-based, and FM-driven architectures. In this context, the creation of the Incidents1M-Seg dataset represents a major contribution to the project and to the disaster resilience community in general. By addressing the lack of high-quality, pixel-level annotated data for the challenging post-disaster scenes, this benchmark enables rigorous evaluation of segmentation and detection methods under realistic conditions and serves as a cornerstone for future developments within WP4 and beyond.

Beyond visual perception, non-visual sensing and information fusion techniques have been investigated through advanced 3D semantic mapping, LiDAR-based SLAM, and traversability analysis, demonstrating their potential to improve situational awareness. Furthermore, the integration of environmental SED provides a vital non-visual layer for situational awareness, allowing for the detection of emergency or hazardous events and human presence even in visually obstructed environments. In particular, the reported results showcase that 3DGS is the most suitable method for accurately reconstructing a post-disaster scene in near real-time. LiDAR-based perception and mapping modules will be further refined to enhance robustness in visually degraded conditions, with particular emphasis on accurate 3D reconstruction, traversability estimation, and reliable localization in cluttered and dynamically changing environments. To convert the outputs of the separate perception modules into utilizable intelligence, knowledge representation and reasoning techniques were applied. This approach of semantically enhancing perception data enables the dynamic construction of a knowledge graph. Using the graph, TRIFFID applies logic reasoning to arrive at conclusions about critical scenarios, as well as the prioritization of missions based on the capability of the available resources.

Finally, the development and evaluation of audio and visual gesture-based HRI mechanisms and AR-based HCI solutions confirm the feasibility of intuitive interaction paradigms well-suited for FRs under stressful and challenging situations. Moreover, the introduction of a task-specific gesture command dataset, and extended experiments confirm that efficient, transferable models can support intuitive UGV control without imposing excessive cognitive or operational burden on users, while enabling higher-level abstraction of commands and interaction cues for intuitive HRC.

Looking forward, work in WP4 will be continued in a number of complementary directions. First, the presented perception and mapping algorithms will be further optimized for real-time performance and robustness under adverse sensing conditions and computational constraints, required from the defined pilots. Second, more sophisticated multi-modal fusion strategies will be explored, to efficiently integrate visual, LiDAR-based information into a shared representational framework that will support higher-level reasoning. Third, the HRI and HCI modules will be further optimized through a series of user-centric design iterations and validation tests with FR end-users, ensuring that the proposed set of gestures remains intuitive under the time and safety-critical nature of post-disaster rescue operations.

To conclude, the results presented in deliverable D4.1 indicate that WP4 work is on the correct trajectory for achieving robust and multimodal post-disaster scene understanding and intuitive HRC. The main target of these outcomes is to allow TRIFFID's multirobot agents to cooperate with the FRs and to enhance their operational processes. In this way WP4 deliverables will be incrementally integrated to the TRIFFID robotic platform and ground station infrastructure, setting the stage for large-scale field trials during the subsequent phases of the project.

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